

UNIVERSITEIT VAN PRETORIA
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**The mycobiota of Eastern Cape dairy pastures, including
the characterisation and implications of novel *Fusarium*
species**

by

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Submitted in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree

Philosophiae Doctor

in the Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Science

University of Pretoria

June 2025

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Declaration of originality

University of Pretoria

I, **Claudette Dewing**, declare that the thesis, which I hereby submit for the degree Philosophiae Doctor at the University of Pretoria, is my own work and has not previously been submitted by me for a degree at this or any other tertiary institution.

SIGNATURE:

DATE: 17 June 2025

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Acknowledgements

I would like to acknowledge my supervisors for the support and time they provided to my project throughout my PhD.

To **Prof. Cobus Visagie** and **Dr Neriman Yilmaz** – Thank you for your guidance, mentorship and support throughout the course of my PhD. Your expertise, critical insight and encouragement contributed greatly to the quality of this thesis. I am especially thankful for the opportunity you provided me with Mycobiomics, which enriched both my personal and academic journey, and allowed me to grow as a researcher. Thank you for your continued encouragement, especially during the more challenging moments when the end of this PhD journey seemed so far away. I also appreciate how you always celebrate the small achievements along the way, creating meaningful memories for all of us in the Applied Mycology group to look back on. It has been a great privilege to be one of your postgraduate students.

To **Prof. Emma Steenkamp** and **Prof. Brenda Wingfield** – Thank you for being part of my postgraduate journey since my MSc. Your continued guidance and support have been greatly appreciated. I am especially grateful for the many years of expertise you shared during Friday meetings, which greatly contributed to the quality of my PhD. Your constructive feedback contributed to shaping my development as a researcher. It has been a privilege to have you on my supervisory committee, and I sincerely appreciate the knowledge, encouragement, and inspiration you have shared with me throughout this journey.

I would like to thank the members of the admin, culture collection and sequencing facility teams at FABI at the University of Pretoria.

I am grateful for the research funding received from the National Research Foundation (NRF) of South Africa (grant number: 137791), the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (RISE) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101008129, project acronym "Mycobiomics", and the Future Leaders - African Independent Research fellowship program (FLAIR, FLR\R1\201831). I would

also like to acknowledge the postgraduate funding I received from the UP Doctoral Research Bursary (University of Pretoria) and the Oil and Protein Seeds Development Trust.

To my parents and family – Thank you for your endless love, continued support and encouragement throughout my PhD journey. Thank you for your never-ending patience and for believing in my ability to successfully complete this degree. What a journey it has been!

Preface

The fungal diversity in South African dairy pastures, including those in the Eastern Cape province, remains critically understudied. This significant knowledge gap limits our understanding of the mycotoxin-producing species present in pastures and their potential negative impact on dairy cattle health. Chronic exposure to mycotoxins compromises cattle's immune function, reduces their fertility and reduces milk production, which has serious economic consequences for the South African milk industry. Comprehensive research characterising the fungi present in pastures and their ability to produce mycotoxins is needed to start unravelling fungi's impact on the South African dairy industry.

The first chapter of this thesis provides a literature review on pastures, fungi and mycotoxins. It offers an overview of the South African milk industry, compares the grass species commonly used for grazing on dairy farms, explores fungal communities previously reported from pastures, examines disease outbreaks associated with these fungi and highlights the importance of accurate fungal identification. The chapter concludes by identifying gaps in our understanding of pasture-associated fungal communities and their potential effects on cattle health.

The second chapter focusses on characterising the fungal communities associated with Eastern Cape dairy pastures where Sporidesmin-Induced Liver Disease (SILD) is suspected in grazing cattle. The aim of this chapter is to determine if species that could impact cattle health are present in these communities. This includes the SILD causal species *Pseudopithomyces toxicarius* (formerly *Ps. chartarum*). The fungi are characterised by implementing modern taxonomic approaches using DNA sequence data to achieve robust species identifications.

The third chapter focusses on describing three new *Fusarium* species in the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC) isolated during the fungal survey conducted in chapter 2. The species descriptions will be performed by using both a morphological approach and by sequencing different DNA gene regions. This chapter

will also include a detailed morphological description of *F. goeppertmayerae* because the original protologue did not include one.

The fourth chapter focuses on mycotoxins and their associated secondary metabolite biosynthesis gene clusters in the newly described *Fusarium* species from chapter 3. Current knowledge on mycotoxins and their biosynthesis gene clusters within the FIESC is limited. To address this, chemical analyses will be integrated with both newly generated and existing genomic data to assess the mycotoxin production potential of these species in comparison to other *Fusarium* lineages.

This thesis consists of four chapters of which the first is a literature review, followed by three research chapters. Each chapter is presented as a stand-alone study, with the second chapter submitted for publication prior to examination and the third already published. Additionally, the results of this study contribute to ongoing research on the fungal species present in South African dairy pastures and their ability to produce mycotoxins. A summary of the thesis is provided at the end of the document.

Chapter 1:

Pastures, fungi and mycotoxins

Introduction

Various grass species (family *Poaceae*) are commonly utilised for grazing purposes (Charlton and Stewart 1999; Lowe 2009; Truter et al. 2015). In South Africa, the milk industry relies on *Cenchrus clandestinus* (kikuyu), *Lolium multiflorum* (annual ryegrass), and *Lolium perenne* (perennial ryegrass) as preferred pasture species due to their nutritional value and quality (Truter et al. 2015). As production rates of kikuyu and annual ryegrass are seasonal, milk farmers typically incorporate perennial ryegrass into kikuyu pastures to increase the forage availability throughout the year (Van der Colf et al. 2015). Such management practices often also emphasise the positive interactions between grass and beneficial microbes that enhance the nutrient quality and productivity of pastures (Andrews et al. 2011). However, the microbial associates of grasses also have the potential to negatively affect the health of grazing livestock. This is particularly true for fungal communities associated with pastures that could include a range of species capable of producing harmful secondary metabolites known as mycotoxins.

The aim of this review is to 1) provide a brief overview of the role of the milk industry in South Africa, 2) compare the grass species commonly used for grazing on dairy farms in South Africa, 3) explore the fungal species previously reported from pastures and 4) examine disease outbreaks associated with these fungal species. In the conclusion, the importance of understanding the diversity of fungal species associated with pastures is discussed and the existing gaps in the current knowledge highlighted.

The milk industry in South Africa

Global milk production plays an important role in supporting nutritional needs, economic development, and food security for people worldwide, making it an essential component of the agricultural and food sectors. In 2023, for example, South Africa's 891 commercial and small-scale dairy farms produced 0.4% of global milk, which added R 4 627 billion to the gross domestic product (GDP) (Figure 1; Milk Producers' Organisation (2024)). Milk production is produced in eight of South Africa's nine provinces, with the highest milk production reported from the Eastern Cape, Western

Cape and KwaZulu-Natal (Milk Producers' Organisation 2024). Milk producers play an important role in their region by supporting local employment and making major contributions to the economy (Smith 2021).

Given its scale, the milk industry holds a crucial responsibility in ensuring the production of safe and nutritious milk products. These products provide South African households with a rich source of protein, calcium and many other nutrients, which are important to maintain good health (Górska-Warsewicz et al. 2019). Unprocessed milk produced in South Africa is mostly used to manufacture butter, cheese and yoghurt which are popular dairy products among consumers (Milk Producers' Organisation 2024). The need for some basic dairy products with adequate nutrition therefore drives the demand for milk production.

The dynamic milk industry continues to evolve through research and technological innovation, improving efficiency and sustainability (Food For Mzansi 2024). Advancements like automated milking, precision feeding and data-driven tools have reduced labour, ensured product consistency and enhanced animal monitoring (Jacobs and Siegford 2012; Food For Mzansi 2024). Precision feeding delivers optimal nutrients, while digital systems help farmers track herd health and productivity (Francis 2024). These technologies rely on robust data collection and analytics, enabling informed decisions to boost productivity and animal welfare.

Figure 1. An overview of milk production in South Africa within a global context based on data collected by Milk Producers' Organisation (2024) and Smith (2021).

Dairy pastures

A pasture is an area of land specifically managed for growing grasses and other forage plants to provide food for grazing animals such as cows, sheep and goats (Charlton 2008). Pastures create a sustainable source of high-quality, nutritious forage that supports animal health and productivity. In South Africa, common pasture grass species include kikuyu, annual ryegrass and perennial ryegrass (Truter et al. 2015).

Kikuyu and ryegrass, however, have distinct ecological benefits and challenges as pasture species (Table 1). Kikuyu offers excellent erosion control, weed suppression and soil structure improvement through its deep-root system (Phohlo 2016). However, its dormancy in cool months, frost sensitivity, high oxalate levels affecting calcium absorption and risks of nitrogen over-supplementation necessitate careful management (Fulkerson et al. 1998; Sanford 2008). Ryegrass species are favoured for their fast germination, strong erosion control and adaptability to various soils and cool-season climates (Sustainable Agriculture Research and Education 2007). Their rapid regrowth supports sustainable grazing, but high water needs, low tolerance to extreme temperatures and allelopathic effects can limit biodiversity and suitability in arid regions (Hannaway et al. 1999; United States Department of Agriculture 2002; McCarty et al. 2010).

To therefore maintain high-quality pastures all year round, kikuyu pastures are often overseeded with annual ryegrass or legumes to compensate for kikuyu's dormancy during cooler months (Sanford 2008). During these cooler months, kikuyu growth is restricted, leading to suboptimal nutritive forage, reduced palatability and digestibility, and subsequently, poor milk production (Marais 2001). Annual ryegrass is generally preferred over perennial ryegrass due to its better persistence and higher nutritive value, which supports greater milk yields (Van der Colf et al. 2015; Milk SA 2024c). Overseeding not only improves forage quality, palatability and digestibility during winter, but also extends the grazing season, enhances soil structure and suppresses weeds (Waller 2008). Kikuyu pastures are often overseeded with clovers (*Trifolium* spp.) for their robust growth in cooler months and high protein content, improving both forage quality and animal performance (Rawnsley et al. 2002; Pontes et al. 2007;

Botha et al. 2008b; Amiri and Shariff 2012; Heuzé et al. 2019). Furthermore, legumes play a crucial role in enhancing soil health by improving soil structure, encouraging microbial activity, increasing organic matter content and optimising nutrient cycling (Yan et al. 2023). Deep-rooted legumes contribute to improved soil aeration and water infiltration, reducing soil erosion and enhancing overall soil fertility (Findlay and Manson 2011).

Eastern Cape dairy pastures primarily consist of ryegrass (mostly annual ryegrass) and kikuyu (Milk SA 2024a). These pastures are established or enhanced using various soil preparation methods, which may cause minimal to moderate soil disturbance. A common practice is to oversow ryegrass into kikuyu using a minimum-till system (Van der Colf 2011). This approach offers several advantages, such as improved forage quality and increased production during the dormancy of kikuyu (Bellotti and Blair 1989; Botha et al. 2008a; Van der Colf 2011). However, effective grazing management after ryegrass emergence is important for ensuring its successful establishment within the kikuyu-based pasture (Fulkerson et al. 2010). One challenge is competition-induced stress from kikuyu, which can negatively impact the young ryegrass seedlings and reduce overall production (Bellotti and Blair 1989). Cultivation or other disturbance methods can help alleviate this issue by reducing competition from the existing kikuyu pasture, thereby allowing the oversown ryegrass more time to establish (Bellotti and Blair 1989).

Milk farmers in the Eastern Cape, however, may occasionally experience challenges with kikuyu-ryegrass-based pastures due to factors such as low rainfall, poor ryegrass persistence, high nitrogen fertilisation requirements and low forage quality in winter (see Table 1). Research suggests that incorporating alternative species, such as legumes, could improve milk yield, increase forage quality and provide better resilience under adverse environmental conditions (Milk SA 2024b). The optimal grass-to-legume ratio in mixed pastures is typically around 3:1, as legumes enhance soil fertility by fixing nitrogen, thereby reducing the reliance on synthetic fertilisers and improving overall soil health (Crop Guide 2024).

Table 1. Comparison of kikuyu and ryegrass as dairy forage species.

Attribute	Kikuyu	Ryegrass
Scientific name	<i>Cenchrus clandestinus</i>	<i>Lolium multiflorum/L. perenne</i>
Origin	East Africa (Parker 2008)	Europe (Popay 2013)
Climate preference	Warm, temperate; 6–21°C (Mears 1970; Clark 2007)	Cool-season; 10–25°C (Waller 2008; Lin et al. 2018)
Soil preference	Well-drained, fertile; tolerates various soil types (Clark 2007)	Deep, fertile, moist soils (Dickinson 2004)
Rainfall needs	Moderate; shows drought tolerance once established (Clark 2007)	High; optimal with >900 mm/year (Fulkerson and Slack 1994)
Germination and establishment	Quick germination, vegetative spread (Marais 2001)	Fast establishment; annual needs resowing, perennial lacks persistence
Growth season	Spring–Autumn	Winter
Dry matter yield¹	Average 49 t DM ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹ (Minson et al. 1993); Range: 6–35 t DM ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹ (Whitney 1974; Pearson et al. 1985; Evans and Hacker 1992; Fulkerson et al. 1999; Cruywagen et al. 2007; Gherbin et al. 2007; Botha et al. 2008a)	Average 22 t DM ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹ (Minson et al. 1993)
Carrying capacity	Up to 12 cows per hectare (Minson et al. 1993)	Approximately 5.5 cows per hectare (Minson et al. 1993)
Milk yield per cow per day	Lower due to lower energy content (Fulkerson et al. 1998)	Annual: 15–21 kg; Perennial: 16–22 kg (Lowe et al. 2000)
Crude protein and digestibility	Moderate; declines with maturity	High; declines over season but perennial has higher crude protein (Thom and Bryant 1996)

¹t = tonnes; DM = dry matter; ha = hectare; t DM ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ = tonnes of dry matter per hectare per year

Fungal diseases associated with pasture

Fungi play important roles in pasture health, both beneficially as decomposers and symbionts, and detrimentally as pathogens (Talbot et al. 2008; Fraç et al. 2018). Even though pastures are often grazed without serious consequences, it can sporadically become toxic and cause disease in grazing animals (Kellerman et al. 2005; Bourke 2007). For example, ergotism, staggers, kikuyu poisoning and Sporidesmin-Induced Liver Disease (SILD) have all been linked to disease outbreaks associated with fungal infestation and their mycotoxins present in pastures.

Ergotism and staggers

Ergot is a seed replacement disease where species from *Claviceps* target grass florets, replacing the host's reproductive structures with hardened dark brown to purple sclerotia containing alkaloids. The primary economic impact of ergot contamination arises from a reduced grain quality grade, as healthy kernels on infected spikes have lower weights compared to those on uninfected spikes (Harper and Seaman 1980). In rye, the presence of just one to six sclerotia on spikes has been shown to increase yield losses by up to 51% (Ponomareva et al. 2016). Surveillance efforts have identified several species capable of inducing ergot (Van der Linde et al. 2016; Liu et al. 2020; Van der Linde et al. 2022), with *Claviceps purpurea* the most common and important in terms of human and animal health (Kren and Cvak 1999). Other notable species include *Claviceps paspali* and *Claviceps africana*, known to infect sorghum crops (Little et al. 2011).

Sclerotia contain indole-diterpenoid alkaloids, known as tremorgenic compounds that disrupt neuromuscular function, causing tremors and impaired grazing in livestock (Knaus et al. 1994; Imlach et al. 2008). These toxins are produced by members of *Clavicipitaceae*, *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* (Saikia et al. 2008). Within *Claviceps*, compounds such as lolitrems, paspalitrems and paspalinine are linked to syndromes commonly termed “perennial ryegrass staggers” or “paspalum staggers”, depending on the host plant associated with the fungal infection (Botha et al. 1996; Imlach et al. 2008).

The ergot fungus *C. paspali* is a known producer of indole-diterpene toxins and is responsible for staggers in cattle grazing on infected paspalum grasses (Kellerman et al. 2005). Similarly, *Cynodon dactylon* (Bermuda grass) is also often associated with a tremorgenic condition referred to as “Bermuda grass staggers” due to the presence of the ergot fungi *Claviceps cynodontis* and *C. purpurea* (Porter et al. 1974; Kellerman et al. 2005). Both *C. cynodontis* and *C. purpurea* form visible sclerotia, making infections relatively easy to identify. Despite its association with Bermuda grass, *C. purpurea* itself is not known to produce tremorgenic mycotoxins (Porter et al. 1974; Conway and Shelby 1992). Instead, the tremorgenic effects experienced by cattle after grazing on Bermuda grass pastures are more likely attributed to *C. cynodontis* (Uhlig et al. 2009). However, research on the metabolites produced by *C. cynodontis* remains limited and no conclusive evidence has yet shown that it produces tremorgenic mycotoxins. Uhlig et al. (2009) confirmed the presence of paspalitrems, paspaline and paspalinine in ergot-infected Bermuda grass linked to a 2006 outbreak in South Africa, supporting the role of tremorgenic mycotoxins in livestock illness and highlighting the need for better monitoring of toxin-producing fungi associated with pastures.

Fescue toxicosis

Fescue toxicosis is a condition in beef and dairy cattle linked to grazing on tall fescue (*Lolium arundinaceum*) infected with the endophyte *Neotyphodium coenophialum* (formerly known as *Acremonium coenophialum* and *Epichloë coenophiala*) (Bacon et al. 1977; Bacon 1995; Salvat and Godoy 2001; Schnitzius et al. 2001). This fungus has been found to cause a negative economic impact in the United States of America, with approximately \$2 million in annual losses documented (Kallenbach 2015). *Neotyphodium coenophialum* lives symbiotically within the plant, where its presence enhances plant survival through alkaloid production, which deters herbivory and supports stress tolerance, including nematode resistance (Kimmons et al. 1990; Joost 1995). Despite the importance of *N. coenophialum*, it occasionally produces toxic ergopeptine alkaloids – particularly ergovaline – which cause health issues in livestock (Lyons et al. 1986; Strickland et al. 1993).

Symptoms of fescue toxicosis include lameness, tissue necrosis in extremities, weight loss, infertility and reduced milk yield (Botha et al. 2004). These effects are due to the

vasoconstrictive and hormonal-disrupting actions of alkaloids like ergovaline, which interfere with blood flow and prolactin regulation (Strickland et al. 1993). In warm weather, reduced heat dissipation leads to “summer syndrome,” while cold-induced vasoconstriction in winter causes dry gangrene (Strickland et al. 1993). Ergopeptines also reduce prolactin secretion and prolactin serum concentrations, which results in lower conception rates and infertility (Lyons et al. 1986; Arnold et al. 2014).

In South Africa, fescue toxicosis was first reported in 2004 in Brahman cattle in Mpumalanga, where ergovaline-contaminated pastures led to lameness and tail loss (Botha et al. 2004). Similar outbreaks occurred in the Eastern and Western Cape, including a “summer slump” in dairy cows fed ryegrass-barley mixtures contaminated with *Claviceps purpurea* sclerotia (Schneider et al. 1996). Another similar condition was observed in dairy cattle on the South African Highveld after the consumption of maize silage or teff hay contaminated with *Cyperus esculentus* (yellow nutsedge) where these feed sources were heavily infested with sclerotia from the fungus *Claviceps cyperi* (Naude et al. 2005). This was also the first documented case of bovine ergotism not associated with *Poaceae* infected with *C. purpurea* or endophytes but rather with *Cyperaceae* and this particular fungal phytopathogen (Naude et al. 2005). All findings mentioned here underscore the need for awareness of ergotism risk in similar agricultural settings.

Sporidesmin-Induced Liver Disease

Commonly referred to as facial eczema or pithomycototoxicosis, Sporidesmin-Induced Liver Disease (SILD) is a liver-related photosensitivity disorder in sheep and cattle caused by ingesting the mycotoxin sporidesmin, produced by *Pseudopithomyces toxicarius* (formerly *Ps. chartarum*) (Cunningham et al. 1942; Clare 1944; Brook 1969; Weir et al. 2025). Sporidesmin disrupts liver function, preventing the breakdown of phylloerythrin, a chlorophyll by-product (Quin et al. 1935; Di Menna et al. 2009). This leads to phylloerythrin accumulation in the blood, causing sunlight-induced skin lesions – primarily on the face but also on other exposed areas (Quin et al. 1935; Clare 1944; Kellerman and Coetzer 1985). Other clinical signs associated with SILD include reduced fertility, weight loss, poor growth and subsequent poor milk supply (Di Menna et al. 2009). As a result of impaired health and productivity of animals diagnosed with

SILD, the New Zealand agricultural sector faces an annual economic loss of \$332 million (Heiser 2024).

The fungus responsible for SILD was first isolated in New Zealand in 1958 (Percival and Thornton 1958) and underwent several taxonomic revisions – from *Stemphylium* to *Sporidesmium bakeri*, then *Pithomyces chartarum* (Ellis 1960). In 1986, Roux (1986) reported *Leptosphaerulina chartarum* as the teleomorph of *Pithomyces chartarum*, isolated from various South African substrates in a natural Karoo pasture. Later, with the application of phylogenetic studies, it was shown that the genus *Pithomyces* is polyphyletic, with species distributed across multiple families within *Pleosporales* (Da Cunha et al. 2014; Pratibha and Prabhugaonkar 2015). *Pithomyces flavus*, the type species of *Pithomyces*, was placed in *Astrosphaeriellaceae* (Pratibha and Prabhugaonkar 2015), while *Leptosphaerulina chartarum* was shown to belong to *Didymellaceae* distinct of all *Pithomyces* (Da Cunha et al. 2014). *Pithomyces chartarum*, *P. maydicus* and *P. sacchari* formed a distinct group within *Didymosphaeriaceae* and were subsequently reclassified under the newly established genus *Pseudopithomyces* (Ariyawansa et al. 2015), with *Ps. chartarum* designated as the type species. The strain MUCL 15905 was selected as a reference strain for *Ps. chartarum*, as the holotype is a dried specimen with no living culture or available sequence data. Weir et al. (2025) further refined the taxonomy of *Ps. chartarum*, revealing that strains previously classified as this species belong to two distinct phylogenetic clades. The clade containing MUCL 15905 was largely non-sporidesmin-producing and was considered to represent *Ps. chartarum*. Meanwhile, the second clade, responsible for sporidesmin production, was named *Ps. toxicarius*, now recognised as the primary causative agent of SILD.

Following its identification in New Zealand, SILD was reported in several other countries, including Argentina, Australia, China, France, the Netherlands, Portugal, South Africa, Spain, Turkey, the United States of America and Uruguay (Edwards et al. 1983; Bezille et al. 1984; Hansen et al. 1994; Pinto et al. 2005; Van Wuijckhuise et al. 2006; Ozmen et al. 2008; Di Menna et al. 2009; Riet-Correa et al. 2013; Liu et al. 2023). The first confirmed outbreak of SILD in South African dairy cattle was recently reported by Davis et al. (2025). Although SILD had previously been well documented in sheep from the Eastern Cape (Marasas et al. 1972), the case reported by Davis et

al. (2025) involved a severe outbreak in an Eastern Cape dairy herd, with substantial clinical and economic consequences. Affected cows showed classical signs of hepatogenous photosensitivity and elevated liver enzymes, with *Ps. toxicarius* spores confirmed in pasture samples.

The report by Davis et al. (2025) builds on earlier South African evidence of sporidesmin-induced hepatobiliary damage, particularly in sheep, as comprehensively described by Kellerman and Coetzer (1985), who reviewed various hepatogenous photosensitisation syndromes caused by fungi, plants and algae. Their work highlighted *Ps. chartarum* as a major causative agent of bile duct necrosis and periductal fibrosis in sheep grazing ryegrass/clover pastures. Further complexity in diagnosing hepatogenous photosensitivity in South African livestock was demonstrated by Davis et al. (2021), who reported a separate outbreak in dairy cows grazing immature *Brassica rapa* (turnip) crops. Although the clinical presentation mimicked SILD, the mechanism of disease was determined to be brassica-associated liver disease (BALD), not sporidesmin toxicity. Together, these studies underscore the importance of accurate differential diagnosis and highlight sporidesmin as a newly recognised threat to South African dairy herds, especially under conducive climatic and pasture conditions. The risk is further supported by the fact that the first reported outbreak of SILD took place in the Eastern Cape province where sheep grazed on perennial ryegrass (Marasas et al. 1972). Although most studies associating *Ps. toxicarius* with SILD involved perennial ryegrass, it was found that kikuyu grass in some areas harbours *Ps. toxicarius* (Brook 1963), suggesting a broader risk across different pasture types.

Kikuyu poisoning

Kikuyu poisoning is considered a ruminitis syndrome in cattle resulting in dehydration, forestomach necrosis, neuromuscular symptoms, tremors and incoordination (Bryson 1982; Newsholme et al. 1983; Kellerman et al. 2005; Bourke 2007). Though suspected to be a mycotoxicosis, the exact causal agent remains unknown (Martinovich et al. 1972).

Bryson and Newsholme (1978) identified *Fusarium* species in the fungal community during a kikuyu poisoning outbreak in Natal, South Africa. While the species were classified based on their morphology, their specific role in the poisoning event was not determined. Similarly, Wong et al. (1987) identified *F. incarnatum* and *F. subglutinans* from kikuyu grass during a poisoning outbreak in New South Wales, Australia, but did not define the role of these species in the incident.

In 2007, *Fusarium torulosum* was isolated from kikuyu pastures during a kikuyu poisoning outbreak in Australia (Ryley et al. 2007). The authors considered *F. torulosum* as the causal agent since this fungus was isolated from affected pastures and is reported to produce wortmannin and butenolide. Exposure to these compounds results in clinical and pathological symptoms similar to those reported in cattle experiencing kikuyu poisoning (Tookey et al. 1972; Abbas and Mirocha 1988; Gunther et al. 1989). Botha et al. (2014a) subsequently surveyed Eastern Cape kikuyu pastures during an outbreak of cattle intoxication that potentially resembled kikuyu poisoning. They did not detect *F. torulosum*, but did isolate other *Fusarium* species from the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC), *Fusarium oxysporum* species complex (FOSC), *Fusarium sambucinum* species complex (FSAMSC) and *Fusarium redolens* species complex (FRSC) that are reported to produce several mycotoxins that could affect cattle health. Neither Ryley et al. (2007) nor Botha et al. (2014a) could confirm if the kikuyu poisoning was indeed due to *Fusarium* mycotoxins as neither study conducted analytical screening for these fungal metabolites.

More recently, Coelho et al. (2024) investigated the fungal community associated with kikuyu during a poisoning outbreak in Portugal and identified *Fusarium* species from the FSAMSC and FIESC, along with *F. heterosporum*, *F. graminearum* and *F. avenaceum* among all isolated fungi. Unfortunately, Coelho et al. (2024) did not conduct mycotoxin analysis, so the role of these *Fusarium* species in the kikuyu poisoning outbreak remains unclear. This ongoing lack of toxin data leaves the role of *Fusarium* in kikuyu poisoning unresolved and highlights a critical knowledge gap in pasture-associated mycotoxicosis.

Major mycotoxigenic fungi and associated toxins

Mycotoxins are toxic secondary metabolites produced by filamentous fungi, typically by species of *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* (Scudamore and Livesey 1998; Sweeney and Dobson 1998; Placinta et al. 1999; Yiannikouris and Jouany 2002; Overy et al. 2003). These toxins can contaminate food and feed, posing significant risks to human and animal health (Fink-Gremmels 2008b; Zain 2011). They are often produced under conditions of environmental stress, such as high humidity and temperature, which favour fungal growth (Medina et al. 2017).

When consumed, mycotoxins can lead to a variety of acute and chronic health effects, ranging from poisoning and immune suppression to carcinogenicity and reproductive toxicity (Morgavi and Riley 2007). Due to their persistence in the food supply and their potential for widespread contamination, mycotoxins represent a major concern for global food safety (Magan et al. 2011; Bryden 2012; Streit et al. 2012). To date, only some mycotoxins are well studied and regulated due to sufficient information on their toxicity. These mycotoxins include aflatoxins, citrinin, trichothecenes (deoxynivalenol, nivalenol and their derivatives), patulin, ochratoxin A, fumonisins and zearalenone (Figure 2). These toxins have wide-ranging effects which we summarise in Table 2.

Figure 2. Major mycotoxins that are associated with health problems in cattle.

Aspergillus mycotoxins

Aspergillus species are known to be both pre- and post-harvest pathogens, producing mycotoxins in the field as well as during storage, transportation and processing (Storm et al. 2008). *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus* thrive in high-moisture environments and produce key mycotoxins, including aflatoxins. These toxins have been occasionally detected at low levels, which can contribute to increased intake of aflatoxin B1 in lactating dairy cows (Garon et al. 2006; Richard et al. 2009). Once ingested, aflatoxins are rapidly absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract and appear in both the blood (Gallo et al. 2008) and milk (Masoero et al. 2007; Battacone et al. 2012) within minutes. Sheep and dairy cows exposed to aflatoxin-contaminated feed experience reduced feed intake, liver dysfunction and immune suppression, even at relatively low levels of mycotoxin exposure (Fernandez et al. 2000; Tripathi et al. 2008). Additionally, replacement heifers (young female cattle raised to replace older or less productive cows in a herd) provided with feed contaminated with both aflatoxins and fumonisins showed significant delays in reproductive development and slower growth (Abeni et al. 2014).

In addition to aflatoxins, *A. flavus* produce several other mycotoxins, such as kojic acid, cyclopiazonic acid and β -nitropropionic acid (Chang et al. 2009; Storm et al. 2010). Cyclopiazonic acid disrupts calcium balance and leading to liver degeneration and necrosis, myocardial lesions, cell death and neurotoxic effects (Huang and Chu 1993). However, the effects of these mycotoxins on ruminants remain understudied (Council for Agricultural Science 2003). Prolonged or short-term exposure to β -nitropropionic acid in sheep and cattle may lead to emphysema and impaired mobility (James et al. 1980).

Aspergillus species such as *A. westerdijkiae*, *A. niger*, *A. fresenii*, *A. carbonarius* and *Penicillium* species such as *P. verrucosum* and *P. nordicum* (Samson et al. 2004; Meca and Ritieni 2009) produce ochratoxin, although its presence in forages is rare (Driehuis et al. 2008; Storm et al. 2014). Sheep exposed to ochratoxin have shown reduced feed intake (Höhler et al. 1999).

In South Africa, two outbreaks of neuromycotoxicosis in cattle were linked to feed that was contaminated with *A. clavatus* (Botha et al. 2014b). High concentrations of patulin, along with other metabolites like pseurotin A and tryptoquivaline F, were detected and thought to contribute to the neurotoxic symptoms, including tremors. In a similar study, Niederberger et al. (2011) found patulin and maltoryzin (Suzuki et al. 1971) during another neuromycotoxicosis outbreak. These findings suggest that multiple mycotoxins, rather than a single toxin, may play a role in the observed clinical signs in cattle.

Studies on fungal communities during disease outbreaks in pastures (Gabbedy et al. 1974; Bryson and Newsholme 1978; Van der Merwe et al. 1979; Wong et al. 1987), did not identify *Aspergillus* species. However, Penagos-Tabares et al. (2021) examined pastures in Austria and detected sterigmatocystin, a mycotoxin produced by *Aspergillus* species such as *A. flavus*, *A. glaucus*, *A. nidulens*, *A. ustus* and *A. versicolor*. The detection of sterigmatocystin in these pastures was linked to diarrhoea and death in dairy cattle, although the specific role of sterigmatocystin in the intoxication remains unclear and requires further investigation (Penagos-Tabares et al. 2021). Toxicological studies have shown that sterigmatocystin can cause kidney and liver damage and diarrhoea in laboratory animals (Ciegler and Vesonder 1983).

Fusarium mycotoxins

Fusarium species produce both type A and type B trichothecenes (Eckard et al. 2011; McCormick et al. 2011; Storm et al. 2014). Of these, type B trichothecenes have a higher toxicity to ruminants than type A (Schollenberger et al. 2006). Type A trichothecenes, which include diacetoxyscirpenol, T-2 toxin and HT-2 toxin, and their deacetylated analogues are primarily produced by *F. poae*, *F. sporotrichioides* and *F. langsethiae* (Munkvold et al. 2021). These toxins have been reported in animal feed (Schollenberger et al. 2006; Eckard et al. 2011; Storm et al. 2014). In contrast, type B trichothecenes are more commonly found in animal feed, with deoxynivalenol being the most studied. Other type B trichothecenes include nivalenol, fusarenon-X (also known as 4-acetyl-nivalenol) and their acetylated and deacetylated analogues (e.g. 3-acetyl-deoxynivalenol, 15-acetyl-deoxynivalenol). Type B trichothecenes are mainly

produced by *F. graminearum* and *F. culmorum* (Chelkowski 2014; Munkvold et al. 2021).

Symptoms associated with deoxynivalenol exposure include gastrointestinal problems, immunosuppression and feed refusal resulting in a decline in animal performance (Trenholm et al. 1985; European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) 2004; Fink-Gremmels 2008b). Despite reports that dairy cattle showed a higher sensitivity to deoxynivalenol than beef cattle or sheep, milk production does not seem to be affected by dairy cows (Charmley et al. 1993; Winkler et al. 2014). Ruminants are reportedly less sensitive to nivalenol, as ruminal microbiota can detoxify this mycotoxin (Hedman and Pettersson 1997). Despite EFSA providing exposure levels for nivalenol in lactating dairy cows and beef cattle, data on its specific effects in livestock remain limited, as does information on fusarenon-X (EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM) 2013).

The effects of type A trichothecenes – specifically T-2 and HT-2 toxins – have been mostly studied in calves and lambs, with limited research on their impact on lactating dairy cows (Hsu et al. 1972; Yoshizawa et al. 1981; Mann et al. 1984). Clinical symptoms associated with T-2 and HT-2 toxin exposure include internal bleeding, enteritis, metabolic changes, immunosuppression and reduced fertility in bulls (Alm et al. 2002). Diacetoxyscirpenol-contaminated feed typically leads to feed refusal and weight loss. The extent of weight loss depends on the specific mycotoxins involved, with animals consuming a diet contaminated with both aflatoxins and diacetoxyscirpenol experiencing the highest weight loss compared to when diacetoxyscirpenol is the only contaminant (Harvey et al. 1995).

Fusarium annulatum and *F. verticillioides* (Chelkowski 2014) are the primary producers of fumonisins, with fumonisins B1 being the most commonly reported in feed (Yu et al. 1999). Fumonisins are cytotoxic, hepatotoxic and nephrotoxic to animals (Spotti et al. 2001; Bernabucci et al. 2011), causing symptoms such as reduced appetite and diarrhoea (Richard et al. 1996). At high levels, fumonisins exposure can result in death (Edrington et al. 1995).

Zearalenone is frequently detected in a variety of feed types. In the rumen, zearalenone is converted to α -zearalenol and β -zearalenol, with majority of zearalenone being converted to α -zearalenol (Kiessling et al. 1984; Kennedy et al. 1998; Fink-Gremmels 2008a). The former is more estrogenic than zearalenone itself, though it is slowly absorbed in the liver, where it can be converted to the less potent β -zearalenol (Santos et al. 2013). While experimental studies on zearalenone's effects in livestock are scarce, case reports suggest that high doses of zearalenone can lead to reproductive issues. These include decreased embryo survival, genital oedema and hypertrophy in pre-pubertal females, hormonal disruptions, changes in uterine morphology, feminisation of young males and general infertility (Minervini and Dell'Aquila 2008; Santos et al. 2013). In studies involving heifers and dairy cows, pure zearalenone was found to reduce conception rates but did not cause major changes in reproductive organs or progesterone levels (Weaver et al. 1986). In contrast, heifers provided with feed contaminated with both zearalenone and deoxynivalenol exhibited reproductive problems, such as unsynchronised ovarian cycles and vaginitis (Coppock et al. 1990). However, some studies did not find a direct correlation between zearalenone exposure and estrogenic effects, suggesting that the impact may vary based on how zearalenone is metabolised in the rumen.

Other *Fusarium*-derived toxins, such as beauvericin, enniatins and moniliformin are also present in feed but at much lower levels than other mycotoxins. No toxicological information is currently available regarding the effects of these mycotoxins (Storm et al. 2008; Santos et al. 2015).

Penicillium mycotoxins

Penicillium paneum and *P. roqueforti* are often associated with silage contamination (Auerbach et al. 1998), whereas *P. roqueforti* is known as a contaminant of feed grain (Hägglom 1990). Both these species are considered to pose a risk to cattle health as they can produce toxins such as roquefortine C (neurotoxic), PR toxins (nephrotoxic, hepatotoxic), patulin (carcinogenic, hemorrhagic) and mycophenolic acid (immunosuppressive) (Auerbach et al. 1998; Driehuis et al. 2008; Mansfield et al. 2008). Roquefortine C has been identified as a potential causal factor in several cases of paralysis, abortion and placental retention in cattle (Hägglom 1990; Auerbach et

al. 1998). However, roquefortine C is also considered as a mycotoxin with low toxicity since the disease symptoms seem to reverse and disappear as soon as the cows are fed with grain lacking fungal contamination (Hägglom 1990). It is therefore suggested that cattle health issues rather arise from the ingestion of multiple toxins, which may interact and collectively impact animal health (Pfohl-Leszkowicz et al. 2002). Specifically, during the post-harvest transportation or storage of forage under various environmental conditions, *P. roqueforti* and *P. paneum* present in silages produce roquefortine C, mycophenolic acid, along with other toxins such as andrastin A, roquefortines A, B, and D, PR-toxin, festuclavine, marcfortine A and agroclavine (O'Brien et al. 2006).

Penicillium species have been identified as part of the fungal community during disease outbreaks in pastures in Australia but were only identified to genus level (Gabbedy et al. 1974; Wong et al. 1987). No *Penicillium* species were identified from a disease outbreak in South African pastures (Bryson and Newsholme 1978) and could be attributed to a combination of environmental factors.

Table 2. Major mycotoxins from *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* species and their effects on livestock.

Genus	Species	Mycotoxins ¹	Effects on livestock	References
<i>Aspergillus</i>	<i>A. flavus</i> , <i>A. parasiticus</i>	Aflatoxins (especially B ₁)	Liver damage, immunosuppression, reduced feed intake, toxin in milk	(Garon et al. 2006; Richard et al. 2009)
	<i>A. flavus</i>	Cyclopiazonic acid, β -nitropropionic acid (β -NPA)	Cyclopiazonic acid: neurotoxic, liver and myocardial damage; β -NPA: emphysema, movement issues	(James et al. 1980; Huang and Chu 1993)
	<i>A. westerdijkiae</i> , <i>A. niger</i> , <i>A. carbonarius</i> , <i>A. fresenii</i>	Ochratoxin	Reduced feed intake in sheep	(Höhler et al. 1999)
	<i>A. clavatus</i>	Patulin, pseurotin A, tryptoquivaline F	Neurotoxic effects: tremors, neuromycotoxicosis	(Botha et al. 2014b)
	<i>A. flavus</i> , <i>A. glaucus</i> , <i>A. nidulens</i> , <i>A. ustus</i> , <i>A. versicolor</i>	Sterigmatocystin	Diarrhoea, kidney, liver damage (in animals); unclear effects in cattle	(Penagos-Tabares et al. 2021)
<i>Fusarium</i>	<i>F. poae</i> , <i>F. sporotrichioides</i> , <i>F. langsethiae</i>	Type A trichothecenes (T-2, HT-2, DAS)	Internal bleeding, enteritis, immunosuppression, fertility issues	(Hsu et al. 1972; Alm et al. 2002)
	<i>F. graminearum</i> , <i>F. culmorum</i>	Type B trichothecenes (DON, NIV, Fus-X)	Gastrointestinal issues, feed refusal, immunosuppression	(Trenholm et al. 1985; European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) 2004)

Table 2. (continued)

Genus	Species	Mycotoxins¹	Effects on livestock	References
Fusarium	<i>F. annulatum</i> , <i>F. verticillioides</i>	Fumonisin (especially B ₁)	Reduced appetite, diarrhoea, cytotoxicity, death at high doses	(Edrington et al. 1995)
	Various species	Zearalenone	Reproductive disruption, hormonal effects, feminisation	(Coppock et al. 1990; Santos et al. 2013)
	Various species	Beauvericin, enniatins, moniliformin	Unknown effects in livestock	(Storm et al. 2008)
Penicillium	<i>P. paneum</i> , <i>P. roqueforti</i>	Roquefortine C, PR toxins, patulin, mycophenolic acid	Neurotoxic, hepatotoxic, immunosuppressive, reproductive issues	(Auerbach et al. 1998)
	<i>P. roqueforti</i> , <i>P. paneum</i>	Andrastin A, festuclavine, marcfortine A, agroclavine	Possible synergistic toxic effects	(O'Brien et al. 2006)

¹T-2 = T-2 toxin, HT-2 = HT-2 toxin, DAS = diacetoxyscirpenol, DON = deoxynivalenol, NIV = nivalenol, Fus-X = fusarenon-X or 4-acetylnivalenol

Other fungi

Other less reported genera such as *Myrothecium*, *Phoma* and *Rhizoctonia* can also cause mycotoxicosis in animals grazing on pasture (Morehouse 1979). *Myrothecium roridum* and *Phoma* (unidentified species) were identified as part of the fungal community investigated by Wong et al. (1987) during a kikuyu poisoning outbreak in Australia, whereas Bryson and Newsholme (1978) and Gabbedy et al. (1974) only identified *Myrothecium* to genus level as part of their isolated fungal communities during disease outbreaks in cattle grazing on pasture. However, no mycotoxin analysis was conducted during these studies and could not confirm the role of these fungi during the disease outbreaks. Members of *Myrothecium* are known to produce the toxic trichothecenes verrucarin A and roridin B, which may induce severe haemorrhagic enteritis and high mortality (Morehouse 1979). Symptoms such as diarrhoea, feed refusal and muscle weakness in cattle have been reported after ingestion of toxins brefeldin A and cytochalasin B produced by members of *Phoma* (Morehouse 1979). Furthermore, *Rhizoctonia* members can produce the toxin slaframine, which may induce symptoms in cattle such as diarrhoea, feed refusal, lacrimation, profuse salivation and reduced milk production (Crump 1973; Morehouse 1979).

Fungal identification

Fungal species estimates range between 611 000–10 million species (Hawksworth 1991, 2001; O'Brien et al. 2005; Schmit and Mueller 2007; Blackwell 2011; Mora et al. 2011; Hawksworth 2012), with a more recent estimate of 2.2–3.8 million species (Hawksworth and Lücking 2017). Despite the large range of estimates, they all agree that with only about 150 000 fungal species formally recognised, the majority of the fungi remain undescribed (Costello et al. 2013; Hawksworth and Lücking 2017; Phukhamsakda et al. 2022). This highlights the urgent need for innovative approaches and increased efforts to accelerate the documentation and understanding of fungal biodiversity.

Fungal identification is the process of determining the specific identity of strains along the taxonomic hierarchy, ideally to species level. Identification entails comparing observed features, whether DNA sequence data or morphology of a strain, to known characteristics of described species (Pitt and Barer 2012). Methods used are typically guided by the species concepts adopted at the time. For example, when species are classified using a morphological species concept, identification relies on characterising strains based on colony diameter, texture and colour, mycelia, soluble pigments, size and colour of conidia, branching of conidiophores and the presence of fruiting bodies, amongst many others, and comparing these with existing descriptions.

While the morphological species concept has been widely applied in the past, it has limitations. One of these is the fact that morphological characters can be influenced by different environmental factors such as nutrients, temperature, lightning and humidity, making it difficult to compare results across studies (Larone 1995). This has previously been observed in important genera such as *Alternaria* (Andersen et al. 2002; Pryor and Michailides 2002), *Aspergillus* (Okuda 1994; Okuda et al. 2000; Samson et al. 2014), *Fusarium* (Zachariah et al. 1956; Leslie and Summerell 2006; Crous et al. 2021) and *Penicillium* (Okuda 1994; Okuda et al. 2000; Samson 2013; Visagie et al. 2014). The second limitation includes observed morphological characters that are difficult to interpret, even for experienced taxonomists (Guarro et al. 1999). In addition, morphology does not allow for the differentiation between cryptic species. This has, for example, been observed in *Fusarium* species from the FOOSC where, based on DNA sequence data and phylogenetics, many more species were introduced in the clade (Lombard et al. 2019). Previous studies have been largely based on morphological identifications, and as a result, it is difficult to establish what species truly occur on what substrates or where they occur based on studies that used morphology.

The shift towards phylogenetic species concepts for fungi has necessitated the adoption of DNA-based identification methods. These sequence-based approaches depend heavily on the availability of reference sequence databases, which are often derived from taxonomic revisions. One of the most widely used methods for fungal identification is DNA sequencing, particularly of the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region, which serves as the universal barcode marker for fungi (Schoch et al. 2012).

While ITS sequencing is not always ideal for achieving precise identification at species level, it remains the most commonly employed marker for higher-level fungal classifications due to its ease of amplification (Lücking et al. 2020). Consequently, the ITS region continues to be the most frequently sequenced gene region in fungal studies (Lücking et al. 2020). However, ITS has limitations, particularly in distinguishing closely related species within certain groups. To overcome these challenges, it is often recommended to sequence alternative barcode markers for more accurate identification. These include, for example, calmodulin (*CaM*) for *Aspergillus* (Samson et al. 2014), glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (*GAPDH*) for *Alternaria* (Woudenberg et al. 2013), RNA polymerase second largest subunit (*RPB2*) for *Epicoccum*, *Neosascochyta* and *Pseudopithomyces* (Hou et al. 2020), translation elongation factor 1- α (*TEF*) for *Cladosporium* (Bensch et al. 2012) and *Fusarium* (O'Donnell et al. 2015) and β -tubulin (*BenA*) for *Penicillium* (Visagie et al. 2014).

GenBank is the most common DNA sequence repository and accepts data from various sources worldwide (Clark et al. 2015). Due to this, some sequences may lack thorough validation or curation, along with incorrect names associated with them (Nilsson et al. 2006). Since GenBank is a public database, it does not allow for name changes or sequence annotations from third parties. Following this, NCBI initiated RefSeq as a curated collection of not only reference sequences for genomes, transcriptomes and proteomes (Pruitt et al. 2006), but also a subset of ITS and large subunit of the nuclear ribosomal RNA (LSU) sequences generated for ex-type strains that therefore serve as reference points of the species (Schoch et al. 2014). Sequences added to RefSeq are also documented in scientific publications to support their inclusion (Lücking et al. 2020). This would expand the database, improve the quality of reference sequences and allow for a more comprehensive genetic understanding of various species.

While RefSeq is an invaluable resource for fungal identification, its focus on ITS sequences and ex-type sequences still leaves several gaps when it comes to distinguishing closely related species. For more accurate species identification, it is essential to circumvent misidentifications by utilising a multi-locus approach, incorporating not just ITS but also other genetic markers previously mentioned (β -

tubulin, calmodulin, RNA polymerase second largest subunit and translation elongation factor 1- α). This approach can enhance precision, especially for genera like *Alternaria*, *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium*, where ITS alone often fails to differentiate species effectively. To achieve proper identifications, it is useful to combine these markers with phylogenetic analysis, where sequence data from multiple loci can be used to build more robust species trees. Additionally, expanding sequence databases beyond RefSeq to include sequences from non-type strains and a broader range of fungal species would allow for a more comprehensive approach to identification.

Gaps in our understanding of fungal communities in pastures and their impact on cattle health

Fungi can have major implications for the quality and safety of food and feed. This includes crop contamination, contamination during storage, mycotoxin production and food and feed quality deterioration (Abass et al. 2017; Mateus et al. 2021). It is therefore important to correctly identify and characterise fungal species associated with pastures to understand which species are present and the potential roles they play.

Studies regarding fungal communities associated with dairy pastures are lacking. Over the years, some studies, both local and global, attempted to identify the fungal communities associated with pastures during cattle disease outbreaks (Gabbedy et al. 1974; Bryson and Newsholme 1978; Van Heerden et al. 1978; Bryson 1982; Newsholme et al. 1983; Wong et al. 1987; Peet et al. 1990; Botha et al. 2014a). A limiting factor of these studies is that more incorporated only a morphological approach for identification. This resulted in many fungi only being identified to a genus level, making it challenging to compare data across studies. The use of morphology alone in earlier surveys could also result in misidentifications making it even more difficult to speculate on the role these fungi play in pastures in terms of mycotoxin production, as an example.

To date, only one pasture-oriented study in South Africa has used molecular data, where *Fusarium* was identified using *TEF* sequences (Botha et al. 2014a). Botha et

al. (2014a) identified several new *Fusarium* species, but they were never described or further characterised. Unfortunately, since this was the first study looking at the role of *Fusarium* species during a kikuyu poisoning outbreak, it is not possible to reliably link the results from Botha et al. (2014a) with studies looking at the overall fungal diversity during kikuyu poisoning outbreaks (Gabbedy et al. 1974; Bryson and Newsholme 1978; Wong et al. 1987). The previous studies did not share the proportions in which the fungal communities were identified and only reported on the overall genera. These results would have been interesting to compare with what previous studies found based on morphological identifications compared to what Botha et al. (2014a) discovered with molecular data.

Identifying the fungal species in pastures is the first step toward understanding their mycotoxin production potential and effects on cattle health. There is a current knowledge gap regarding the fungi in pastures and their impact on grazing animals. For instance, *Ps. toxicarius* which produces sporidesmin, is a well-known health risk. However, many other pasture fungi may also produce mycotoxins, but their prevalence, toxin profiles and effects on cattle health remain poorly understood.

Conclusions

The sustainability and productivity of the South African milk industry are heavily dependent on the quality and availability of healthy pastures. Kikuyu and ryegrass species, which are integral to the country's dairy pastures, play an important role in ensuring consistent milk yields. Healthy pastures are essential for maintaining the overall well-being of dairy cattle, as the quality of the pasture directly impacts animal health, milk production and the industry's long-term viability. However, the fungal communities in these pastures can present significant challenges to both the health of the cattle and the productivity of the milk industry.

The fungal communities in pastures are crucial factors that influence the health of dairy cattle and the quality of milk production. Fungal colonisation in pastures is often closely linked to environmental conditions, with warm and moist environments promoting fungal proliferation (Colhoun 1973; Froelich and Snow 1986). Environmental

stressors, such as drought or fluctuating temperatures (Bucci et al. 2016; Hossain et al. 2019), can weaken plant defence mechanisms, making pastures more vulnerable to fungal infections. Fungal threats not only impact pasture health but also pose risks to cattle, potentially compromising animal health, leading to disease outbreaks and affecting milk quality. Understanding the dynamics between grass species and fungal species in these environments is important for developing effective strategies to mitigate these risks.

There is a significant gap in our understanding of the fungal communities associated with dairy pastures in South Africa, especially in regions like the Eastern Cape, where research is particularly limited. This lack of information makes it difficult to develop effective prevention and management strategies to protect dairy cattle from harmful fungi. Ongoing research is necessary to identify fungal species, understand their role in pasture ecosystems and assess their impact on cattle health and productivity. Research focusing on fungal diversity in pastures will help fill critical knowledge gaps, enabling the development of sustainable solutions to reduce mycotoxin contamination and ultimately enhance the productivity and health of the South African dairy industry. Such studies will be essential to overcome the challenges posed by climate change (St-Pierre et al. 2003; Hammami et al. 2013; Nguyen et al. 2016; Lee et al. 2019), environmental stress such as drought (Kachergis et al. 2014; McClaran and Wei 2014) and disease outbreaks (Cutler et al. 2010; Ahmed et al. 2019).

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Chapter 2:

Capturing the fungal diversity hidden in Eastern Cape dairy pastures

This chapter was accepted for publication in *Mycological Progress*

Abstract

Fungi in dairy pastures impact cattle health, yet the diversity of fungal species present in South African pastures remains understudied. Following an outbreak of Sporidesmin-Induced Liver Disease (SILD; caused by the mycotoxin sporidesmin produced by *Pseudopithomyces toxicarius*) in the Eastern Cape in 2020, we collected mixed pasture samples from 14 dairy farms affected by this disease. Our aim was to investigate what fungal species are present in communities and whether species like *Ps. toxicarius* are present that may play a role in cattle health. A total of 708 strains were isolated from 95 mixed pasture samples and identified based on DNA sequence data to 132 species representing 55 genera. *Fusarium* was the most isolated (207 strains; 21 species; 55 samples), followed by *Penicillium* (75 strains; 22 species; 27 samples), *Pseudopithomyces* (69 strains; 2 species; 21 samples), *Cladosporium* (54 strains; 6 species; 23 samples), *Epicoccum* (52 strains; 6 species; 24 samples) and *Bipolaris* (38 strains; 3 species; 19 samples). Several strains could not be identified and represent 28 potentially new or previously uncharacterised species. Additionally, phylogenetic analyses revealed the presence of *Ps. palmicola* and *Ps. toxicarius* in the Eastern Cape dairy pastures. Our findings underscore the ecological complexity of pasture environments and raise important questions about the role of fungal diversity in livestock health.

Key words

Cattle health, Facial eczema, Fungal diversity, Mycotoxins, *Pithomyces chartarum*

Introduction

The Eastern Cape province of South Africa has a diverse agricultural landscape and plays an important role in the country's citrus, wool and dairy industries. Grasslands and pastures are important in supporting the province's livestock sector, providing forage that sustains the largest proportion of South Africa's goats (39%), sheep (30%) and cattle (25%) populations (Department of Agriculture Land Reform and Rural Development 2023). The Eastern Cape, Western Cape and KwaZulu-Natal provinces are the joint largest milk producers, with each contributing around 29% of South Africa's total milk production (Milk Producers' Organisation 2024). The milk industry in South Africa contributes about 0.4% to global milk production while also creating jobs, supporting rural developments and promoting food security (Smith 2021).

Dairy pastures in the Eastern Cape are typically planted with kikuyu (*Cenchrus clandestinus*), annual ryegrass (*Lolium multiflorum*) and perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*) (Truter et al. 2015). These species are selected for their adaptability to the local climate and their nutritional value and quality, including factors like taste and yield (Truter et al. 2015; MilkSA 2023). Kikuyu is known for its lower digestibility compared to other grasses, such as perennial ryegrass, which can limit its forage quality (Marais 2001; Van der Colf et al. 2015). To overcome this, pastures are often overseeded with ryegrass and clover to enhance productivity and quality (Botha et al. 2008b, a; Swanepoel et al. 2014; Van der Colf et al. 2015; MilkSA 2024). These mixed pastures combine the benefits of both grass species, aiming to extend the grazing season and improve pasture quality in order to enhance cattle health and optimal milk production (Botha et al. 2008b, a; Van der Colf et al. 2015).

Grasses are colonised by a wide range of fungi (Sánchez Márquez et al. 2012), some of which are associated with diseases in cattle. Notable examples include kikuyu poisoning (Bourke 2007; Di Menna et al. 2009) and Sporidesmin-Induced Liver Disease (SILD, previously known as facial eczema or pithomycotoxicosis).

Kikuyu poisoning is a ruminitis syndrome in cattle resulting in dehydration, forestomach necrosis, neuromuscular symptoms, tremors and incoordination (Bryson

1982; Newsholme et al. 1983; Kellerman et al. 2005; Bourke 2007). Since the first outbreak of kikuyu poisoning, it was hypothesised that kikuyu poisoning may present a mycotoxicosis. In Australia, *Fusarium torulosum* was consistently isolated from pastures where cattle displayed kikuyu poisoning symptoms (Martinovich et al. 1972; Bourke 2007; Ryley et al. 2007). This fungus can produce wortmannin and butenolide, compounds linked to similar disease symptoms to kikuyu poisoning (Tookey et al. 1972; Abbas and Mirocha 1988; Gunther et al. 1989; Bourke 2007). In South Africa, Botha et al. (2014a) surveyed Eastern Cape dairy pastures during several kikuyu poisoning outbreaks between 2008–2010. Although *F. torulosum* was not detected during the survey, several other *Fusarium* species were identified, including *F. culmorum*, *F. redolens*, *F. oxysporum* and species from the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC) (Botha et al. 2014a). These species can produce various mycotoxins such as aurofusarin, beauvericin, butenolide, culmorin, deoxynivalenol, enniatins, fusaric acid, fusarins, fumonisins, moniliformin, nivalenol and zearalenone (Munkvold et al. 2021).

SILD is a secondary photosensitisation of ruminants caused by the mycotoxin sporidesmin produced by the fungus *Pseudopithomyces toxicarius* (formerly considered *Ps. chartarum*) (Weir et al. 2025). It occurs when phylloerythrin, a chlorophyll by-product, accumulates in the bloodstream due to impaired breakdown, leading to sunlight sensitivity, sunburn and skin lesions, alongside symptoms like reduced fertility, weight loss, poor growth and decreased milk production (Kellerman et al. 2005; Di Menna et al. 2009). SILD has been reported in Argentina, Australia, China, France, South Africa, the Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Turkey, the United States and Uruguay (Marasas et al. 1972; Riet and Diaz 1974; Edwards et al. 1983; Bezille et al. 1984; Hansen et al. 1994; Fuertes et al. 2004; Pinto et al. 2005; Van Wuijckhuise et al. 2006; Ozmen et al. 2008; Riet-Correa et al. 2013; Liu et al. 2023; Davis et al. 2025). In New Zealand, SILD has caused significant production losses for over a century, exceeding NZD 100 million annually (Pollock et al. 2015). While the majority of *Ps. toxicarius* isolates from New Zealand produce sporidesmin (Weir et al. 2025), the proportion of sporidesmin-producing isolates in other countries are often lower or is unknown (Di Menna et al. 2009). In South Africa, SILD was first reported in sheep (Marasas et al. 1972). This was followed by more reports from sheep and other animals like dairy cows (Van der Merwe et al. 1979; De Wet and Erasmus 1984;

Kellerman and Coetzer 1985; Davis et al. 2025). Considering the recent taxonomic revision of *Ps. chartarum* and the introduction of the toxin-producing *Ps. toxicarius* (Weir et al. 2025), knowledge on what species occurs in South African dairy pastures and the risk they pose to cattle health are unknown.

Recent increases in SILD reports from Eastern Cape dairy farms suggest growing awareness about the disease. However, knowledge on the fungal communities associated with dairy pastures in the region remains limited. The study aimed to survey Eastern Cape dairy pastures affected by SILD to determine the presence of *Pseudopithomyces* species and identify other fungi that may impact cattle health.

Materials and methods

Sampling and isolations

A total of 95 mixed grass pasture samples (mainly consisting of kikuyu and annual and perennial ryegrass) were collected across 14 dairy farms in the Eastern Cape province of South Africa during May 2020 from where cattle displayed potential SILD symptoms. Samples were kept dry in brown paper bags at low temperatures. For isolations, plant material was cut into 4 mm pieces and plated directly onto potato dextrose agar (PDA; 213400; Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), dichloran 18% glycerol agar (DG18; CM0729B; Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and water agar (WA). Chloramphenicol (100 ppm) was added to both the PDA and WA to prevent bacterial growth. The plates were incubated for 7–10 d at 25 °C and checked regularly for fungal growth. Colonies were transferred to pure cultures on quarter strength PDA supplemented with chloramphenicol (100 ppm). Where possible, strains were identified to genus level based on their morphological characteristics. All strains were accessioned in a working culture collection (CN) of the Applied Mycology group at the Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI) at the University of Pretoria, South Africa. Cultures were preserved as agar blocks or spore suspensions in cryovials containing 10% glycerol and stored at –80 °C. Representative strains were deposited to the CMW and CMW-IA culture collections of FABI (Table S1).

DNA extraction, PCR and sequencing

Genomic DNA was extracted from 7–10 d old colonies. DNA from pigmented fungi was extracted using the Quick-DNA Fungal/Bacterial Miniprep kit (Zymo Research, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol. PrepMan Ultra Sample Preparation Reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) was used for *Fusarium* and other hyaline fungi following the manufacturer's instructions.

PCR amplifications were prepared in 25 μ L total volumes containing 5 μ L BioLine 5X MyTaq Reaction Buffer (Meridian BioScience, USA), 0.50 μ L of each primer (10 μ M), 17.85 μ L demineralised sterile water and 0.15 μ L BioLine MyTaq DNA Polymerase (Meridian BioScience, USA). Loci targeted are those known to provide species level identifications in respective genera and included the nuclear ribosomal internal transcribed spacer region ITS1-5.8S-ITS2 (ITS) and the large subunit of the nuclear ribosomal RNA (LSU) for strains that could not be identified to a genus based on morphology (Schoch et al. 2012), β -tubulin (*BenA*) for *Penicillium* (Visagie et al. 2014), calmodulin (*CaM*) for *Aspergillus* (Samson et al. 2014), glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (*GAPDH*) for *Alternaria* (Woudenberg et al. 2013) and other *Pleosporales* (Manamgoda et al. 2012; Hernández-Restrepo et al. 2018), RNA polymerase second largest subunit (*RPB2*) for *Epicoccum*, *Neoascochyta* and *Pseudopithomyces* (Hou et al. 2020) and translation elongation factor 1- α (*TEF*) for *Cladosporium* (Bensch et al. 2012), *Fusarium* (O'Donnell et al. 2015) and *Trichoderma* (Samuels 2006). Information regarding the primers and PCR conditions used during this study were obtained from previous studies (Vilgalys and Hester 1990; Rehner and Samuels 1994; Glass and Donaldson 1995; Masclaux et al. 1995; O'Donnell and Cigelnik 1997; De Hoog and Van den Ende 1998; O'Donnell et al. 1998; Berbee et al. 1999; Carbone and Kohn 1999; Liu et al. 1999; Reeb et al. 2004; Hong et al. 2006; Yilmaz et al. 2021) and are provided in Table 1.

Amplified fragments were purified using the ExoSAP-IT PCR Product Cleanup Reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) and sequenced in both directions using the BigDye terminator sequencing kit v. 3.1 (Applied Biosystems, USA) with the same primers used for PCR amplification. Reactions were analysed on an ABI PRISM 3100 DNA sequencer (Applied Biosystems, USA) at the DNA sequencing facility at the

University of Pretoria. Contigs were assembled and edited in Geneious Prime v. 2019.0.4 (BioMatters Ltd., New Zealand). Newly generated sequences were submitted to GenBank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>), with accession numbers provided in Table S1.

BLASTn analysis was performed to compare obtained sequences against the NCBI (National Centre for Biotechnology Information, USA) GenBank nucleotide database (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) to obtain identifications. All ITS comparisons were made against the NCBI Fungal ITS Reference Sequence Targeted Loci Project database (Schoch et al. 2014). For *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* strains, identifications were made based on comparisons with a locally curated DNA sequence database largely based on Houbraken et al. (2020), *Alternaria* against data largely based on Woudenberg et al. (2013), *Cladosporium* against data largely based on Bensch et al. (2012), *Trichoderma* against data largely based on Bissett et al. (2015) and *Fusarium* was identified using data on www.fusarium.org. All additional data files containing the reference datasets, alignments and tree files were uploaded to Figshare (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.27936900>) hosted by the University of Pretoria research data repository.

Phylogenetic analysis of *Pseudopithomyces*

To assess the phylogenetic relationships for our *Pseudopithomyces* strains, we compiled a reference sequence dataset consisting of ITS, *RPB2*, *ACT* (actin), *GAPDH* and *TEF* sequences based on the dataset of Weir et al. (2025) (see Table S2). Sequence alignments were performed using MAFFT v. 7.427 (Kato and Standley 2013) with the G-INS-I option selected. Alignments were concatenated with each gene region treated as distinct partitions in the subsequent analysis. A Maximum Likelihood (ML) tree was made in IQ-TREE v. 2.1.2 (Nguyen et al. 2015) applying the most suitable model parameters calculated using ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy et al. 2017) incorporated into IQ-TREE. Support in nodes were calculated with an ultrafast bootstrap analysis with 10 000 replicates. The tree was visualised in FigTree v. 1.4.4 and edited for publication using Affinity Designer v. 1.6.1 (Serif (Europe) Ltd, Nottingham, UK).

Results

Fungal identifications

Isolations from the 95 mixed pasture samples resulted in 708 strains accessioned and stored in the FABI culture collection. We generated 886 new DNA reference sequences and submitted them to GenBank [ITS (n = 328), *BenA* (n = 80), *CaM* (n = 22), *GAPDH* (n = 48), LSU (n = 39), *RPB2* (n = 88) and *TEF* (n = 281)] (Table S1).

Strains were identified to 132 species, representing 55 genera, 38 families, 15 orders and seven classes. The fungal community is presented as a pie chart with the proportion sizes calculated corresponding to the number of strains isolated per taxon (Figure 1). The numbers represented with each taxon are given as 'x (y), z': x = the number of strains; y = the number of species identified; and z = the number of samples that a taxon was isolated from (Figure 1). At the genus level, *Fusarium* (55/95 samples; 207 strains), *Penicillium* (27/95; 75 strains), *Pseudopithomyces* (21/95; 69 strains), *Cladosporium* (23/95; 54 strains), *Epicoccum* (24/95; 52 strains) and *Bipolaris* (19/95; 38 strains) were the most frequently isolated fungi in mixed pastures. *Penicillium* had the highest species diversity (n = 22), followed by *Fusarium* (n = 21), *Epicoccum* (n = 6), *Cladosporium* (n = 6), *Bipolaris* (n = 3) and *Pseudopithomyces* (n = 2). The most common species were *Fusarium croceum* [*Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC); 32/95; 56 strains], *Pseudopithomyces toxicarius* (20/95; 66 strains), *Fusarium mariecurieae* (FIESC; 20/95; 33 strains), *Epicoccum italicum* (18/95; 26 strains), *Cladosporium pseudocladosporioides* (15/95; 31 strains), *Fusarium culmorum* [*Fusarium sambucinum* species complex (FSAMSC); 15/95; 22 strains], *Bipolaris zeae* (13/95; 29 strains), *Penicillium rubens* (section *Chrysogena*; 13/95; 17 strains), *Fusarium pascuum* (FIESC; 12/95; 17 strains) and *Fusarium clavus* (FIESC; 10/95; 19 strains).

Several strains could not be accurately identified using morphological or DNA sequence data and may represent undescribed species. These include *Absidia* (n = 3, 1 species), *Alternaria* (n = 18, 1 species), *Ceratobasidium* (n = 1, 1 species), *Chaetomium* (n = 2, 1 species), *Cladosporium* (n = 2, 1 species), *Epicoccum* (n = 2, 1

species), *Fusarium* (n = 4, 3 species), *Geotrichum* (n = 5, 1 species), *Neoacremonium* (n = 1, 1 species), *Neosascochyta* (n = 12, 2 species), *Neurospora* (n = 1, 1 species), *Nigrospora* (n = 1, 1 species), *Pararamichloridium* (n = 1, 1 species), *Penicillium* (n = 5, 3 species), *Preussia* (n = 9, 2 species), *Rousoella* (n = 1, 1 species), *Sordaria* (n = 1, 1 species), *Sphaeronaemella* (n = 1, 1 species), *Trichoderma* (n = 4, 1 species) and *Valsonectria* (n = 2, 1 species). Results from homology searches of their sequences against NCBI's Fungal ITS Reference Sequence Targeted Loci Project database are listed in Table 2.

Some strains (CN049F9 and CN103F1) could only be identified at the order level within *Pleosporales*. These strains will be subjected to further investigation in the future.

Phylogenetic analysis of *Pseudopithomyces*

The aligned dataset contained 68 ingroup taxa, with *Bimuria novae-zelandiae* (ICMP24821^T) selected as the outgroup (Figure 2). The alignment was 6 343 bp long (*ACT* = 1 604; *GAPDH* = 1 254; *ITS* = 551; *RPB2* = 953; *TEF* = 1 981). The most suitable nucleotide substitution models were K2P+FQ+G for *ITS*, TN+F+G for *ACT*, *GAPDH*, TN+F+I+G for *TEF*, and TNe+FQ+G for *RPB2*. Our strains clearly belong to *Ps. toxicarius* (n = 66) and *Ps. palmicola* (n = 3).

Discussion

Dairy pastures can harbour a wide variety of fungi. In this study, we characterised the fungal community of 95 mixed grass samples from dairy pastures collected at 14 farms in the Eastern Cape of South Africa. The samples were collected when cattle showed signs of SILD symptoms in May 2020. The fungal communities detected were relatively diverse, with a total of 132 species identified across 55 genera. The most commonly detected genera were *Fusarium*, *Penicillium*, *Pseudopithomyces*, *Cladosporium*, *Epicoccum* and *Bipolaris*. Additionally, 28 isolates require further study that we could not identify with confidence at species level. These isolates may

potentially belong to new species, represent new sequence variation within a species, or be described species that have not yet been sequenced. Two of these were recently described as new *Penicillium* species, *Pe. pascuigraminis* and *Pe. viridipigmentum*, in Visagie et al. (2024a).

The causal agent of SILD, *Ps. toxicarius*, was detected from 21 samples collected at two out of 14 farms. The taxonomy of *Pseudopithomyces*, and especially *Ps. chartarum*, had been complex until the recent revision by Weir et al. (2025). Previously, Da Cunha et al. (2014) and Pratibha and Prabhugaonkar (2015) showed that the genus *Pithomyces* was polyphyletic, with species resolved across several families in *Pleosporales*. The type of *Pithomyces*, *Pithomyces flavus*, belong to *Astrosphaeriellaceae* (Pratibha and Prabhugaonkar 2015), while *Leptosphaerulina chartarum*, erroneously thought to be the sexual morph of *P. chartarum* (Roux 1986), was shown to be a distant relative in *Didymellaceae* (Da Cunha et al. 2014). *Pithomyces chartarum*, *P. maydicus* and *P. sacchari* formed a unique group in *Didymosphaeriaceae*, with these species transferred into the newly described *Pseudopithomyces* (Ariyawansa et al. 2015). *Pseudopithomyces chartarum* was the designated type, with strain MUCL 15905 used as a reference strain, as the holotype (FH00781082) is a dried specimen on paper that has no living culture or sequence available. Weir et al. (2025) found that *Ps. chartarum* strains resolved in two clades in their phylogenetic analyses. The clade containing MUCL 15905 was found to mostly not produce sporidesmin and was considered to represent *Ps. chartarum*. The sporidesmin-producing clade was described as *Ps. toxicarius*, now considered the primary causative species responsible for SILD in New Zealand. Our limited survey suggests that *Ps. toxicarius* is similarly the causative species in South Africa, with *Ps. palmicola* not reported to produce sporidesmin.

Fusarium was the most commonly isolated genus, recovered from 55 of the 95 samples collected across 13 of the 14 dairy pastures. We expected a high number of *Fusarium*, belonging to several species, as it is known to colonise grasses (*Poaceae*) and can function in this niche as either an endophyte or plant pathogen (Leslie and Summerell 2006; Bentley et al. 2007; Nor Azliza et al. 2014; Laurence et al. 2016; Chehri et al. 2017). Most of the identified *Fusarium* species belonged to the FIESC, including *F. brevicaudatum*, *F. clavus*, *F. coffeatum*, *F. croceum* and three new species

described as *F. cumulatum*, *F. mariecurieae* and *F. pasuum* (Dewing et al. 2025). Other species identified included those from the FSAMSC (*F. culmorum*, *F. graminearum*, *F. poae*), *Fusarium oxysporum* species complex (FOSC) (*F. fabacearum*, *F. glycines*, *F. wimaladesilvae* and two potentially new species), *Fusarium chlamydosporum* species complex (FCSC) (*F. chlamydosporum*) and *Fusarium fujikuroi* species complex (FFSC) (*F. terricola*). In line with our data, Botha et al. (2014a) previously reported the presence of *F. culmorum* and *F. oxysporum* in Eastern Cape kikuyu pastures, while Gabbedy et al. (1974) and Newsholme et al. (1983) reported *Fusarium* isolated from kikuyu from Australia and South Africa, respectively, identifying it only to the genus level. *Fusarium torulosum*, which was reported by Ryley et al. (2007) to be linked to kikuyu poisoning in Australia, was not isolated during our survey. We also did not isolate the previously reported *F. verticillioides* (= *F. moniliforme*) (Newsholme et al. 1983), *F. incarnatum* (= *F. semitectum*) and *F. subglutinans* (\equiv *Fusarium moniliforme* var. *subglutinans*) (Wong et al. 1987) from Australian kikuyu grass. Some earlier studies from South Africa (Van der Merwe et al. 1979) and Australia (Peet et al. 1990) did not detect *Fusarium* in their surveys of grass pastures. In contrast, we identified several species not previously reported from pastures, including *F. brevicaudatum*, *F. cerealis*, *F. chlamydosporum*, *F. clavus*, *F. coffeatum*, *F. croceum*, *F. graminearum*, *F. poae* and *F. terricola*. Several of the species we identified are reported as mycotoxin producers (Villani et al. 2019; Munkvold et al. 2021).

Some mycotoxins produced by *Fusarium clavus* (zearalenone), *F. culmorum* (butenolide, deoxynivalenol, zearalenone), *F. graminearum* (butenolide, deoxynivalenol, zearalenone) and *F. poae* (butenolide) have been linked to cattle diseases (Tookey et al. 1972; Trenholm et al. 1985; Weaver et al. 1986; Mathur et al. 2001; Munkvold et al. 2021). Deoxynivalenol exposure can lead to abortion and chronic toxicity, manifesting as stunted growth, reduced weight gain, weakened immunity and increased susceptibility to disease (Trenholm et al. 1985; Biscoto et al. 2022; Toutouchi et al. 2022). Zearalenone has been shown to induce hypoestrogenism, leading to issues such as infertility (Weaver et al. 1986; Fushimi et al. 2015; Gruber-Dorninger et al. 2021). Additionally, butenolide has the potential to cause lethal acute inflammation in the forestomach of cattle, a condition typically observed during kikuyu poisoning (Tookey et al. 1972). Although some mycotoxins

produced by certain *Fusarium* species have been reported to be associated with kikuyu poisoning (Tookey et al. 1972; Ryley et al. 2007), no kikuyu poisoning symptoms were observed in the cattle during our survey in the Eastern Cape, and *F. torulosum* was not isolated during our survey. The lack of kikuyu poisoning symptoms during our survey highlights the fact that the presence of mycotoxigenic fungi does not necessarily provide evidence of mycotoxin production, while mycotoxin occurrence and concentration levels can vary considerably under suitable conditions (Gallo et al. 2015). Despite an increased awareness of *Fusarium* mycotoxin occurrences in pastures, data remain very limited to accurately assess the risk of *Fusarium* mycotoxin exposure in cattle.

Other mycotoxigenic species affecting cattle health and productivity were also identified in Eastern Cape pastures. *Aspergillus clavatus* is a known producer of patulin (Lopez-Diaz and Flannigan 1997; Varga et al. 2007; Houbraken et al. 2020), while *Penicillium* species such as *Pe. chrysogenum*, *Pe. coprophilum* and *Pe. crustosum* produce roquefortine C (El-banna et al. 1987; Frisvad and Filtenborg 1989; Häggblom 1990; Frisvad et al. 2004; Houbraken et al. 2012; Houbraken et al. 2016). Roquefortine C is a very common compound produced by many *Penicillium* species, including the blue cheese related *Pe. roqueforti* (Frisvad and Samson 2004). *Penicillium crustosum* also produces penitrem A–G (Frisvad et al. 2004; Botha et al. 2019), while *Pe. citrinum* produces citrinin (Lai et al. 2013). These mycotoxins have been shown to adversely affect cattle health, causing a range of issues such as fever, diarrhoea and skin irritation (citrinin); neurotoxicosis (patulin and penitrem A); incoordination and diaphoresis (penitrem A) and reversible paralytic effects (roquefortine C) (Häggblom 1990; Griffiths and Done 1991; Sabater-Vilar et al. 2004; Botha et al. 2014b; Botha et al. 2019). We did not confirm whether these compounds are produced by the strains isolated, but we can confirm that these strains were not widespread in the pastures based on the low numbers they were isolated from in our study. For example, *As. clavatus* was only represented by 12 strains, *Pe. crustosum* by 11 strains, *Pe. chrysogenum* by two strains and both *Pe. coprophilum* and *Pe. citrinum* by one strain each. Although these strains were present in low numbers, prolonged exposure to low levels of these mycotoxins could still negatively impact cattle health. The presence of these mycotoxigenic species in Eastern Cape pastures

emphasises the need for vigilant monitoring and management practices to mitigate their impact on cattle health and productivity.

Our study reports more diverse communities than previous surveys conducted during outbreaks of SILD or kikuyu poisoning (Marasas et al. 1972; Bryson and Newsholme 1978; Van der Merwe et al. 1979; Newsholme et al. 1983; Wong et al. 1987; Ryley et al. 2007; Botha et al. 2014a). This could be attributed to earlier species identifications that relied on morphological characters, which often led to misidentifications, especially in groups containing cryptic species, thus underestimating overall fungal diversity. The incorporation of DNA sequencing in modern taxonomy has resulted in an increased number of species described in several genera (Hawksworth and Lücking 2017). In particular, genera such as *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium* and *Penicillium* have seen a sharp increase in the rate of species descriptions in the past decade, with many that are considered cryptic (Houbraken et al. 2020; Crous et al. 2021; Visagie et al. 2024b). For example, the FOOSC was recently studied by Lombard et al. (2019) who provided new species names for the 15 lineages that they considered represented cryptic species. These findings highlight the importance of incorporating molecular techniques such as DNA sequencing to accurately assess fungal diversity in general, particularly in complex genera like *Fusarium*.

Our study provides baseline knowledge of the fungi present in Eastern Cape dairy pastures. With the use of molecular data, we discovered a more diverse fungal community than previously reported, including 28 potentially undescribed species. We also confirmed the presence of several mycotoxigenic species from the genera *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Penicillium* and *Pseudopithomyces*, which are known to potentially impact cattle health. Furthermore, we confirmed the presence of *Ps. toxicarius* in dairy pastures of the Eastern Cape, the causative species of SILD. Future work will focus on: 1) describing the new species identified in our study, 2) investigating their mycotoxin production potential and 3) analysing the secondary metabolite profiles of these new species to determine their potential effects on cattle health.

Data availability

All sequence data generated for this work can be accessed via GenBank: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>. Other additional data files containing the reference datasets, alignments, and tree files were uploaded to Figshare (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.27936900>).

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Figures

Figure 1. Pie chart summarising the fungal community associated with dairy pastures in the Eastern Cape. The proportions are based on the number of strains. The numbers in the legends stand for [x (y), z] x = the number of strains; y = the number of species identified; and z = the number of samples that a taxon was isolated from.

Figure 2. Maximum likelihood tree of *Pseudopithomyces* based on a concatenated dataset of *ACT*, *GAPDH*, *ITS*, *RPB2* and *TEF*. Strains of species isolated from this study are shown in bold text. The tree was rooted to *Bimuria novae-zelandiae*. Branch support in nodes higher than 80% are indicated at relevant branches (^T = ex-type; ^R = reference strain).

Tables

Table 1. Primers and PCR conditions used in this study.

Locus	Target genus	PCR amplification protocol	Primer	Primer sequence 5'–3'	Reference
<i>BenA</i>	<i>Penicillium</i>	94°C 5 min; 35 cycles of 94°C 45s, 56°C 45s, 72°C 60s; 72°C 7min; 10°C ∞	T10	ACGATAGGTTCCACCTCCAGAC	O'Donnell and Cigelnik (1997)
			Bt2b	ACCCTCAGTGTAGTGACCCTTGGC	Glass and Donaldson (1995)
<i>CaM</i>	<i>Aspergillus</i>	94°C 5 min; 35 cycles of 94°C 45s, 56°C 45s, 72°C 60s; 72°C 7min; 10°C ∞	cmd5	CCGAGTACAAGGARGCCTTC	Hong et al. (2006)
			cmd6	CCGATRGAGGTCATRACGTGG	
<i>GAPDH</i>	<i>Alternaria/other Pleosporales</i>	94°C 5min; 30 cycles of 94°C 45s, 52°C 60s, 72°C 60s; 72°C 7min; 10°C soak	gdp1	CAACGGCTTCGGTGCATTG	Berbee et al. (1999)
			gdp2	GCCAAGCAGTTGGTTGTGC	
ITS	General	94°C 5 min; 35 cycles of 94°C 45s, 55°C 45s, 72°C 60s; 72°C 7min; 10°C ∞	V9G	TTACGTCCCTGCCCTTTGTA	De Hoog and Van den Ende (1998)
			LS266	GCATTCCCAAACAACCTCGACTC	Masclaux et al. (1995)
<i>TEF</i>	<i>Cladosporium/Trichoderma</i>	94°C 5 min; 35 cycles of 94°C 45s, 52°C 45s, 72°C 60s; 72°C 7min; 10°C ∞	728F	CATCGAGAAGTTCGAGAAGG	Carbone and Kohn (1999)
			986R	TACTTGAAGGAACCTTACC	
	<i>Fusarium</i>	94°C 5 min; 35 cycles of 94°C 45s, 53°C 45s, 72°C 60s; 72°C 7min; 10°C ∞	EF1	ATGGGTAAGGARGACAAGAC	Yilmaz et al. (2021);
			EF2	GGARGTACCAGTSATCATG	O'Donnell et al. (1998)
<i>RPB2</i>	<i>Epicoccum/Pseudopithomyces/Neosascochyta</i>	95 °C 5 min; 40 cycles of 94 °C 30 s, 51 °C 90 s, 68 °C 2 min; 68 °C 5 min; 10 °C ∞	5F2	GGGWGAYCAGAAGAAGGC	Reeb et al. (2004)
			7Cr	CCCATRGCTTGYTTRCCCAT	Liu et al. (1999)
LSU	General	94 °C 5 min; 40 cycles of 94 °C 45s, 48 °C 30s, 72 °C 90s; 72 °C 6min; 10 °C ∞	LR5	ATCCTGAGGGAACTTC	Vilgalys and Hester (1990)
			LROR	GTACCCGCTGAACTTAAGC	Rehner and Samuels (1994)

Table 2. Data obtained from homology searches using ITS sequences against NCBI's Fungal ITS Reference Sequence Targeted Loci Project database.

Genus	Strains	Closest species	GenBank information
<i>Absidia</i>	CMW 61050; CMW 61068; CN049G6	<i>Absidia aguabelensis</i>	strain URM 8213, GenBank NR_189383.1; Identities = 552/635 (87%), 31 gaps (4%)
<i>Ceratobasidium</i>	CN071G9	<i>Ceratobasidium ramicola</i>	strain CBS 133.82, GenBank NR_138368.1; Identities = 516/584 (88%), 26 gaps (4%)
<i>Chaetomium</i>	CN040E2; CMW 61055	<i>Chaetomium spirochaete</i>	strain CBS 730.84, GenBank NR_144823.1; Identities = 615/616 (99%), no gaps
<i>Epicoccum</i>	CMW 61078; CN049H1	<i>Epicoccum</i> sp. 1	strain NV-2016, GenBank LT593066.1; Identities = 798/825 (97%), no gaps
<i>Geotrichum</i>	CMW 61038; CMW 61356; CN050A4; CN050A6; CN056A6	<i>Geotrichum pandrosion</i>	strain BRIP 74954a, GenBank NR_189975.1; Identities = 228/231 (99%), no gaps
<i>Neoacremonium</i>	CMW 60726	<i>Neoacremonium vitellinum</i>	strain CBS 792.69, GenBank NG_058556.1; Identities = 224/228 (98%), no gaps
<i>Neoascochyta</i>	CN041C6; CMW 61348; CMW 61349; CN049G8; CN098F7; CN099B6	<i>Neoascochyta argentina</i>	strain CBS 112524, GenBank MT018302.1; Identities = 540/595 (91%), no gaps
	CN049H8; CN049H9; CN099A9	<i>Neoascochyta</i> sp. 3 LH-2020	strain CBS 140547, GenBank MT018308.1; Identities = 590/596 (99%), no gaps
<i>Neurospora</i>	CN110D3	<i>Gelasinospora brevispora</i>	strain CBS 547.94, GenBank NR_159858.1; Identities = 687/695 (99%), two gaps (0%)
<i>Nigrospora</i>	CMW 61524	<i>Nigrospora sacchari-officinarum</i>	strain CGMCC 3.19335, GenBank NR_165926.1; Identities = 530/536 (99%), one gap (0%)

Table 2. (continued)

Genus	Strains	Closest species	GenBank information
<i>Pararamichloridium</i>	CN107C2	<i>Pararamichloridium aquisubtropicum</i>	strain GZAAS 21-0382, GenBank NR_185675.1; Identities = 591/602 (98%), five gaps (0%)
<i>Preussia</i>	CMW 61034; CMW 61041; CN048G1; CN049C4; CN049D9	<i>Preussia polymorpha</i>	strain CBS 117679, GenBank NR_137729.1; Identities = 387/414 (93%), nine gaps (2%)
	CMW 61079	<i>Preussia persica</i>	strain CBS 117680, GenBank NR_137730.1, Identities = 468/474 (99%), one gap (0%)
	CN115F1; CN115F2; CN115F3	<i>Preussia procaviae</i>	strain CBS 146827, GenBank NR_171769.1; Identities = 513/546 (94%), 12 gaps (2%)
<i>Rousoella</i>	CMW 61022; CN048E3	<i>Rousoella chinensis</i>	strain HKAS 125555, GenBank NR_189903.1; Identities = 451/471 (96%), three gaps (0%)
<i>Sordaria</i>	CMW 61042	<i>Sordaria equicola</i>	strain CBS 146992, GenBank NR_173047.1; Identities = 568/573 (99%), two gaps (0%)
<i>Sphaeronaemella</i>	CN128H6	<i>Candidozyma duobushaemuli</i>	strain CBS 7798, GenBank NR_130694.1; Identities = 264/337 (78%), 12 gaps (3%)
<i>Valsonectria</i>	CN041F7; CN041F8	<i>Valsonectria whitehaneyae</i>	strain BRIP 69038b, GenBank NR_191303.1; Identities = 610/644 (95%), nine gaps (1%)

Supplementary tables

All data and supporting materials are available on Figshare (<https://figshare.com/s/a2be3a1690af79826843>).

Table S1. Strains isolated from mixed dairy pastures in the Eastern Cape, South Africa.

Table S2. *Pseudopithomyces* strains used for the phylogenetic study, based on the dataset from Weir et al. (2025).

Chapter 3:

Three new species of *Fusarium* (*Nectriaceae*, *Hypocreales*) isolated
from Eastern Cape dairy pastures in South Africa

This chapter was published in MycoKeys
(<https://doi.org/10.3897/mycokeys.115.148914>)

Abstract

A survey of the fungal diversity associated with mixed pastures from Eastern Cape dairy farms in South Africa led to the isolation of 155 *Fusarium* strains that belong to the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC). Using single and multigene phylogenies based on partial sequences of the translation elongation factor 1-alpha (*TEF*), calmodulin (*CaM*) and the partial RNA polymerase second largest subunit (*RPB2*) genes, we identified 11 species. They included *F. brevicaudatum*, *F. clavus*, *F. coffeatum*, *F. croceum*, *F. goeppertmayerae* and *F. heslopieae*, with five species that were found to be new. Based on morphological and phylogenetic data, three new species are formally described here as *F. cumulatum*, *F. mariecurieae* and *F. pascuum*. We also provided a description for *F. goeppertmayerae*, as the authors who identified and named this species did not include one. We have chosen to not describe the remaining species, as our cultures lack proper morphological structure development. This study shows that mixed pastures harbour a diverse range of *Fusarium* species and highlights the need for further studies into their potential to impact animal health.

Key words

Fusarium camptoceras, GCPSR, Molecular phylogenetics, Morphology, Mycotoxins

Introduction

Well-maintained pastures are important for promoting the well-being of cattle, as they directly impact the animals' nutrition, overall health and productivity (Marais 2001; Neal et al. 2007; Botha et al. 2008b, a; Doxey 2014; Van der Colf et al. 2015). Several grass species from *Poaceae* are used for grazing worldwide (Charlton and Stewart 1999; Lowe 2009; Truter et al. 2015). In South Africa, the preferred species are *Cenchrus clandestinus* (formerly known as *Pennisetum clandestinum*; kikuyu), *Lolium multiflorum* (annual ryegrass) and *L. perenne* (perennial ryegrass) (Truter et al. 2015). Despite the obvious nutritional value of pastures, they can also pose health risks to grazing animals under certain circumstances, e.g., kikuyu poisoning in cattle (Bryson and Newsholme 1978; Newsholme et al. 1983; Wong et al. 1987; Bourke 2007; Ryley et al. 2007; Botha et al. 2014) or when the growth of mycotoxigenic fungi leads to mycotoxin build-up in pastures (Golinski et al. 2003; Driehuis et al. 2008; Skládanka et al. 2011; Penagos-Tabares et al. 2021).

Among the various factors that could affect the health of grazing cattle, *Fusarium* species and their mycotoxins pose a significant risk. The genus *Fusarium* comprises a diverse group of filamentous fungi that play significant roles in various ecological and agricultural contexts because of the range of lifestyles they exhibit, including saprotrophic and endophytic modes, often associated with various grass hosts (Leslie et al. 2004; Bentley et al. 2007; Summerell et al. 2010; Nor Azliza et al. 2014; Laurence et al. 2016). Some *Fusarium* species are also well-known pathogens to animals, humans and plants, and are important producers of mycotoxins (Desjardins 2006; Leslie and Summerell 2006; O'Donnell et al. 2013; Gallo et al. 2022). *Fusarium* mycotoxins that are particularly important from a toxicological standpoint include deoxynivalenol (Reed and Moore 2009; Skládanka et al. 2011; Burkin and Kononenko 2015; Penagos-Tabares et al. 2021), fumonisins (Reed and Moore 2009; Gott et al. 2017) and zearalenone (Di Menna et al. 1987; Reed et al. 2004; Reed and Moore 2009; Skládanka et al. 2011; Burkin and Kononenko 2015; Nichea et al. 2015; Penagos-Tabares et al. 2021). These toxins can cause severe health issues in animals, including abnormal foetal development, disruptions in cell division and membrane function, reduced feed intake leading to body weight loss, fertility problems,

immunosuppression, inhibition of protein synthesis, impaired mitochondrial function and, in severe cases, death (Trenholm et al. 1985; Weaver et al. 1986; Smith et al. 1990; Edrington et al. 1995; Moretti et al. 2013; Eskola et al. 2018; Aranega and Oliveira 2022). Furthermore, certain *Fusarium* species and their associated mycotoxins have been suggested as potential contributors to kikuyu poisoning cases in South Africa and Australia (Ryley et al. 2007; Botha et al. 2014). However, this connection remains hypothetical and unconfirmed due to limited availability of supporting data.

In 2020, cattle in the Eastern Cape province of South Africa showed symptoms of facial eczema, a type of hepatogenous photosensitivity caused by the mycotoxin sporidesmin A, produced by the fungus *Pseudopithomyces chartarum* (= *Pithomyces chartarum*) (Brook 1963; Di Menna et al. 1970; Marasas and Schumann 1972; Kellerman et al. 1980; Kellerman and Coetzer 1985; Davis et al. 2021). A fungal survey was subsequently conducted at 14 dairy farms to first determine whether *P. chartarum* was present in affected pastures and second to identify other culturable fungi that may also be present (Dewing et al. 2025). The survey revealed *Fusarium* as the most commonly isolated genus, particularly species within the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC). However, some strains in the complex could not be satisfactorily identified to species level. Here we report on the FIESC species present in Eastern Cape dairy pastures and describe three new species using macro- and micro-morphological characterisation with support of multigene phylogenetic approaches. We also supply *F. goeppertmayerae* with the necessary macro- and micro-morphological characterisation information, as this was not supplied by Tan and Shivas (2023), who identified and named this species.

Materials and methods

Sampling and isolations

A total of 95 mixed pasture grass samples (primarily a mixture of kikuyu and ryegrass) were collected from 14 dairy farms in the Eastern Cape province of South Africa in

May 2020, with a specific focus on identifying *Fusarium* species (Table 1). These pastures were potentially associated with a facial eczema outbreak in cattle. Plant material was cut into smaller pieces (± 4 mm) and plated onto potato dextrose agar (PDA; Becton, Dickinson and Company (BD), Franklin Lakes, USA) and water agar (WA). Both were supplemented with chloramphenicol (100 ppm). The plates were incubated for 7–10 d at 25 °C and checked regularly for fungal growth. Colonies were transferred to pure cultures onto $\frac{1}{4}$ PDA supplemented with chloramphenicol (100 ppm). Single spore cultures were prepared for all *Fusarium* strains following Leslie and Summerell (2006). Strains were accessioned and preserved in cryovials containing 10% glycerol and stored at -80 °C in the Applied Mycology working culture collection (CN) housed at the Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI) at the University of Pretoria, South Africa. Additionally, representative strains were deposited in the culture collections of FABI (Collection Mike Wingfield (CMW) and Collection Mike Wingfield at Innovation Africa (CMW-IA)) and the Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute (CBS) in Utrecht, the Netherlands (Table 1).

DNA extraction, PCR and sequencing

Genomic DNA was extracted from 7-d-old fungal cultures grown on $\frac{1}{4}$ PDA and incubated at 25 °C, using the PrepMan Ultra Sample Preparation Reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions. PCR amplification of the translation elongation factor 1-alpha (*TEF*), calmodulin (*CaM*), RNA polymerase largest subunit (*RPB1*) and RNA polymerase second largest subunit (*RPB2*) loci was conducted using primer pairs and thermal cycle conditions as described in Table 2. The PCR reactions were set up in 25 μ L volumes by using 17.3 μ L Milli-Q water (Millipore Corporation, Burlington, USA), 2.5 μ L 10 \times FastStart Taq PCR reaction buffer containing 20 mM MgCl₂ (Sigma-Aldrich, Roche Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany), 2.5 μ L of 100 mM of each deoxynucleotide (New England Biolabs, Inc, Ipswich, USA), 0.5 μ L forward primer (10 μ M), 0.5 μ L reverse primer (10 μ M), 0.5 μ L 25 mM MgCl₂ (Sigma-Aldrich, Roche Diagnostics), 0.2 μ L of 5 U/ μ L FastStart Taq DNA Polymerase (Sigma-Aldrich, Roche Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany), and 1 μ L template DNA. PCR products were prepared for sequencing using 2 μ L ExoSAP-IT PCR clean-up reagent (1 U/ μ L FastAP Thermosensitive Alkaline

Phosphatase, 20 U/μL Exonuclease I (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA)) and 5 μL PCR product. Sequencing was done bi-directionally using the BigDye terminator sequencing kit v. 3.1 (Applied Biosystems, Forster City, USA) with the same primers used for PCR amplification. Reactions were analysed on an ABI PRISM 3100 DNA sequencer (Applied Biosystems, Forster City, USA). Contigs were assembled and edited in Geneious Prime v. 2019.2.1 (BioMatters Ltd., Auckland, New Zealand). All sequences generated in this study were deposited in GenBank, with accession numbers provided in Table 1.

Phylogenetic analyses

Initial identifications of all *Fusarium* strains relied on BLAST search comparisons against the *Fusarium*-MLST database (<https://fusarium.mycobank.org>). These results were then used to produce a reference dataset for the FIESC using previously deposited sequences obtained from the NCBI nucleotide database, largely based on O'Donnell et al. (2009) and Xia et al. (2019) (Table S1). Several phylogenetic trees were computed. The first included selected reference and newly generated sequences, using *TEF*, *CaM* and *RPB2*. Multi- and single-gene trees were calculated from these datasets, with final identifications being based on these trees. We also computed a phylogeny using a more comprehensive dataset based on *TEF*. This phylogeny included all strains obtained from our study, as well as those strains from Avila et al. (2019), Botha et al. (2014), Crous et al. (2021), Lombard et al. (2022), O'Donnell et al. (2009), O'Donnell et al. (2012), Tan and Shivas (2023), Tan and Shivas (2024) and Xia et al. (2019) that contained highly similar identities to ours. The datasets were aligned using MAFFT v. 7.427 (Katoh and Standley 2013) with the G-INS-I option selected in Geneious Prime. For the concatenated dataset, each gene region was treated as separate partitions. Maximum Likelihood (ML) trees were calculated in IQ-TREE v. 2.1.2 (Nguyen et al. 2015) with the General Time Reversible nucleotide substitution model with gamma distribution with invariant sites (GTR+G+I) applied to each partition. Support of nodes was calculated with a standard nonparametric bootstrap analysis with 1 000 replicates (Felsenstein 1985). The resulting trees were visualised using Figtree v. 1.4.4 and edited in Affinity Designer v. 1.7.3 (Serif (Europe) Ltd, Nottingham, UK).

Morphological characterisation

Fusarium strains were characterised based on macro- and micromorphological features (Leslie and Summerell 2006; Aoki et al. 2013; Sandoval-Denis et al. 2018; Yilmaz et al. 2021). After a 7 d incubation on synthetic nutrient-poor agar (SNA) (Gams and Nirenberg 1976) at 25 °C, agar plugs were removed from the colony edges with a 5 mm diameter cork borer and transferred to PDA, oatmeal agar (OA) and SNA for colony morphology and pigmentation assessment. The plates containing the agar plugs were incubated under different light conditions for 7 d, which included 24 h darkness, 24 h near-ultraviolet (nUV) light and a 12/12 h dark/nUV light cycle. Colony colour and codes used in descriptions followed the Methuen Handbook of Colour (Kornerup and Wanscher 1978). Colony growth rates were evaluated on PDA incubated for 7 d at 10–35 °C with 5 °C intervals in 24 h darkness. Colony measurements were recorded daily in four perpendicular directions. Colony images were captured with a Sony FE 90 mm f/2.8 Macro G OSS lens (Tokyo, Japan). Sporodochial formation was evaluated after a 7 d incubation period at 25 °C under a 12/12 h dark/nUV light cycle on SNA and WA, both supplemented with sterilised pieces of carnation leaves. Micromorphological characteristics were examined with a Zeiss AXIO Imager.A2 compound and AXIO Zoom.V16 microscopes equipped with an AxioCaM 512 colour camera driven by Zen Blue 3.2 software (Carl Zeiss CMP, Göttingen, Germany). Conidia and other morphological structures were measured using up to 50 measurements each in NIS-Elements Basic Research software v. 4.30.00 (Nikon Europe B.V.). Photographic plates were prepared using Affinity Designer v. 1.7.3 (Serif (Europe) Ltd, Nottingham, UK).

Results

Identifications and phylogenetic analyses

Isolations from the 95 mixed pastures grass samples collected in the Eastern Cape resulted in 708 strains isolated, with 55 genera and 133 species identified (Dewing et al. 2025). Of the 207 strains identified as *Fusarium* isolated from 12 of the 14 farms,

155 belonged to the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC) (Table 1). The aligned concatenated dataset included 120 taxa and was 2 954 bp long (*CaM*: 1–644; *RPB2_1*: 645–1 471; *RPB2_2*: 1 471–2 334; *TEF*: 2 335–2 954). *Fusarium concolor* (NRRL 13459^T) was selected as the outgroup. The obtained ML tree resolved strains into three main clades, including the *Incarnatum*-clade, *Equiseti*-clade and *Camptoceras*-clade (O'Donnell et al. 2009; Xia et al. 2019; Han et al. 2023) (Figure 1). Strains isolated from pastures represented 11 species, with five well-supported clades representing new species. Individual gene phylogenies for *CaM*, *RPB2* and *TEF* were used to assess these clades applying genealogical concordance phylogenetic species recognition (GCPSR: Taylor et al. (2000)) (Figures S1–3). In all analyses, strains of the new species showed no discordance, noting that the branches holding *F. mariecurieae* did not have support in the *CaM* and *RPB2* phylogenies.

Incarnatum-clade — We identified five species in the *Incarnatum*-clade, including *F. coffeatum* (FIESC 28; n = 7), *F. goeppertmayerae* (n = 14) and the clade we introduce as *F. mariecurieae* (n = 33) below (Figures 1, S1–3). Strains CMW 58691 and CMW 60930 showed variation in *TEF* by at least 11 bp but had similar *CaM* and *RPB2* sequences from other *F. goeppertmayerae* strains. *Fusarium goeppertmayerae* was described based on a single isolate (BRIP 64547d^T), and capturing this type of infraspecies variation is important to better establish its species boundaries. We provide a description of the species below in the Taxonomy section, because Tan and Shivas (2023) did not provide this when naming their species. Two additional new species were isolated, including *Fusarium* FIESC 27 (O'Donnell et al. 2009) (n = 1) and *Fusarium* sp. nov. 1 (n = 2). However, due to the absence of key microscopic characteristics, we opted to not introduce names for these until additional strains are collected.

Equiseti-clade — Five of our species were resolved in the *Equiseti*-clade, from which *F. brevicaudatum* (FIESC 6; n = 2), *F. clavus* (FIESC 5; n = 19), *F. croceum* (FIESC 10; n = 55) and *F. heslopieae* (n = 1) are known species, while *F. cumulatum* (n = 4) is described below as a new species (Figures 1, S1–3). The *F. clavus* clade contains a lot of variation. In the *TEF* phylogeny, *F. clavus* strains form a unique group with *F. tangerrinum*, its closest relative. However, in *RPB2*, both *F. tangerrinum* and *F. extenuatum* resolve inside the broader *F. clavus* clade. In the *CaM* phylogeny, *F.*

tangerrinum also resolves inside *F. clavus*, but *F. extenuatum* is a distant relative. Future work is needed on this group. Our *F. croceum* strains consistently formed a distinct clade closely related to other *F. croceum* strains (including the ex-type CBS 131777^T), with ours differing by at least 9, 8 and 27 bp for *CaM*, *RPB2* and *TEF*, respectively. Based on these findings, we could introduce a new species for the clade. However, at present we propose that our strains represent new genotypes of *F. croceum* with additional strains that will be needed in future. Finally, we identify strain CN071C8 as *F. heslopii*, a species originally introduced based solely on a *TEF* sequence, with no morphological description provided (Tan and Shivas 2024).

Camptoceras-clade — We identified a new species in the *Camptoceras*-clade, which we introduce below as *F. pasuum* (n = 17) (Figures 1, S1–3). The new species is a close relative of *F. fecundum*.

Taxonomy

Fusarium cumulatum Dewing, Visagie and Yilmaz, **sp. nov.**

MycoBank No: 855721

Figure 2

Etymology. Latin, *cumulatum*, meaning to accumulate or heap up, named for its abundant chlamydospore formation.

Type. SOUTH AFRICA, Eastern Cape, from mixed pasture samples, May 2020, collected by A. Davis (**holotype:** PRU(M) 4601, dried specimen in a metabolically inactive state); (**ex-type strain:** CBS 151773 = CMW 58688 = CN104D3).

Description. *Conidiophores* borne on aerial mycelium scarce, 13–71 µm tall, unbranched, bearing terminal phialides, often reduced to single phialides; *aerial phialides* scarce, monophialidic, subulate to subcylindrical, proliferating percurrently, smooth- and thin-walled, 2.5–20 × 2–4 µm, with inconspicuous thickening; *aerial conidia* absent. *Sporodochia* orange, present on the surface

of carnation leaves and on agar. *Sporodochial conidiophores* densely and irregularly branched, bearing apical whorls of 2–5 phialides; *sporodochial phialides* monophialidic, subulate to subcylindrical, 7–16.5 × 2–4 µm, smooth, thin-walled, with inconspicuous periclinal thickening; *sporodochial conidia* falcate, sometimes becoming sinuate, slender, curved dorsiventrally, tapering towards both ends, with an elongated or whip-like curved apical cell and a barely notched to prominently extended basal cell, 1–5-septate, hyaline, smooth- and thin-walled; 1-septate conidia 16 × 4 µm (n = 1); 2-septate conidia 18–30 × 3–4 µm (av. 25.2 × 3.6 µm) (n = 3), 3-septate conidia 23–42 × 2.5–4 µm (av. 25.2 × 3.5 µm) (n = 15), 4-septate conidia 25.5–54.5 × 2.5–4 µm (av. 43.0 × 3.4 µm) (n = 14), 5-septate conidia 38–57 × 3–4.5 µm (av. 49.1 × 3.8 µm) (n = 17). Chlamydospores abundant, globose to subglobose, subhyaline, smooth- to slightly rough-walled, terminal or intercalary, solitary or in pairs forming chains, 8–19 µm diam.

Culture characteristics. Colonies on PDA incubated at 25 °C in the dark with an average radial growth rate of 2–8 mm/d, reaching 44–46 mm diam at 25 °C; surface white, flat, felty to velvety, radiate, with abundant aerial mycelium, margin irregular. Additional colony diam (after 7 d, in mm): PDA 10 °C 13–15; PDA at 15 °C 22–26; PDA at 20 °C 27–32; PDA at 30 °C 64–75; PDA at 35 °C 0–2. Odour absent. Reverse yellowish white (2A2). Diffusible pigments absent. On OA in the dark, occupying an entire 90 mm Petri dish in 7 d; surface white to pale yellow, flat, felty to velvety, radiate, with abundant aerial mycelium, margin irregular, filiform. Reverse yellowish white (4A2). Diffusible pigments absent. On SNA with sparse aerial mycelium, sporulation moderate on the surface of the medium.

Additional material examined. SOUTH AFRICA, Eastern Cape, from mixed pasture samples, May 2020, collected by A. Davis, isolated by C. Dewing, Humansdorp area: CMW 58686 = CN071B9, CMW 58687 = CN071E5, close to Villa Fonte: CMW-IA 002138 = CMW 60936 = CN071G4.

Notes. *Fusarium cumulatum* belongs to the *Equiseti*-clade and is closely related to *F. arcuatisporum* (FIESC 7), (Wang et al. 2019), *F. brevicaudatum* (FIESC 6), (Xia et al. 2019), *F. heslopieae*, (Tan and Shivas 2024), *F. longicaudatum* (Xia et al. 2019), *F. khuzestanicum* and *F. oryzicola* (Afzalnia et al. 2024). No aerial phialides or conidia were observed for the closely related

species (Wang et al. 2019; Xia et al. 2019; Afzalnia et al. 2024) compared to the few scarce monophialides we recorded for *F. cumulatum*. Sporodochia and chlamydospores were present in *F. cumulatum* and its closely related species, whereas *F. oryziphila* lacked chlamydospore formation (Wang et al. 2019; Xia et al. 2019; Afzalnia et al. 2024). Sporodochial conidia of *F. cumulatum* (1–5-septate; 16–57 × 2.5–4 µm) are similar in length to *F. arcuatissporum* (5-septate; 29–49.5 × 4–6 µm) (Wang et al. 2019) and *F. brevicaudatum* (1–5-septate; 8–64 × 3–5 µm) (Xia et al. 2019), while generally being shorter than those observed in *F. khuzestanicum* (4–7(–9)-septate; 48.5–82 × 2.7–4.3 µm) (Afzalnia et al. 2024), *F. longicaudatum* ((3–)5–6(–7)-septate; 45–81 × 4–5 µm) (Xia et al. 2019) and *F. oryziphila* (4–7-septate; 33.5–77.9 × 3–4 µm) (Afzalnia et al. 2024). Colony colour on PDA differs between *F. cumulatum* and closely related species (Wang et al. 2019; Xia et al. 2019; Afzalnia et al. 2024) as other species show more colour across the surface and reverse compared to the white surface and yellowish white (2A2) reverse of *F. cumulatum*, whereas the colony colour of *F. khuzestanicum* and *F. oryziphila* is white to pale grey. The growth rate after 7 d on PDA for *F. cumulatum* (44–46 mm) is slower than that of *F. arcuatissporum* (48–53 mm) (Wang et al. 2019), *F. brevicaudatum* (50–58 mm) (Xia et al. 2019) and *F. longicaudatum* (full 90 mm plate) (Xia et al. 2019). The growth rate for *F. khuzestanicum* (74–76 mm) (Afzalnia et al. 2024) and *F. oryziphila* (74 mm) (Afzalnia et al. 2024) was measured after 5 d on PDA but appears to be faster than that of *F. cumulatum*. No morphological data is currently available for *F. heslopiae* to compare with. Pairwise comparisons revealed that *F. cumulatum* differs from other species by at least 3, 6 and 16 bp for *CaM*, *RPB2* and *TEF*, respectively.

Fusarium goeppertmayerae Y.P. Tan and R. G. Shivas, Index of Australian Fungi 5: 7. 2023.

MycoBank No: 900363

Figure 3

Type. AUSTRALIA, Queensland, Bongeen, from the peduncle of *Zea mays* (*Poaceae*), 25 Feb. 2016, B. Thrift (**holotype**: BRIP 64547d, **ex-type strain**: CBS 150772).

Description. *Conidiophores* borne on aerial mycelium, 8.5–98 μm tall, unbranched, sympodial, bearing terminal or lateral phialides, often reduced to single phialides; *aerial phialides* mono- and polyphialidic, subulate to subcylindrical, proliferating percurrently, smooth- and thin-walled, 4–22 \times 1.5–5 μm , with inconspicuous thickening; *aerial conidia* mostly fusiform, slender, curved dorsiventrally, no apparent tapering observed at ends, blunt to conical and straight to slightly curved apical cell and a blunt to papillate basal cell, 0–3-septate, 0-septate conidia: 7–22 \times 2–5 μm (av. 15.0 \times 3.4 μm) (n = 9); 1-septate conidia: 12–19 \times 2.5–4 μm (av. 15.6 \times 3.4 μm) (n = 13); 2-septate conidia: 16–20 \times 3.5–4 μm (av. 18.2 \times 3.8 μm) (n = 2); 3-septate conidia: 21–31 \times 3.5–4 μm (av. 23.9 \times 3.9 μm) (n = 6). *Sporodochia* pale yellow to white, formed between aerial mycelia around the carnation leaves. *Sporodochial conidiophores* densely and irregularly branched, bearing apical whorls of 2–3 phialides; *sporodochial phialides* monopialidic, subulate to subcylindrical, 6–12 \times 1.5–4 μm , smooth, thin-walled, with inconspicuous periclinal thickening; *sporodochial conidia* falcate, curved dorsiventrally, tapering towards both ends, with a slightly curved apical cell and a blunt to foot-like basal cell, (1–)3–5-septate, hyaline, smooth- and thin-walled; 1-septate conidia: 12–17 \times 3 μm (av. 14.4 \times 3.2 μm) (n = 2); 3-septate conidia: 19–36 \times 3 \times 4 μm (av. 30.0 \times 3.8 μm) (n = 23); 4-septate conidia: 30.5–36 \times 4–5 μm (av. 33.2 \times 4.3 μm) (n = 4); 5-septate conidia: 30 \times 5 μm (n = 1). *Chlamydospores* not observed.

Culture characteristics. Colonies on PDA incubated at 25 °C in the dark with an average radial growth rate of 1–15 mm/d and occupying an entire 90 mm Petri dish in 7 d; surface white, radiate, aerial mycelium felty to velvety, margin irregular, filiform. Additional colony diam (after 7 d, in mm): PDA at 10 °C 14–19; PDA at 15 °C 37–43; PDA at 20 °C 63–70; PDA at 30 °C 40–75; PDA at 35 °C 0–2. Odour absent. Reverse pale yellow. Diffusible pigments absent. On OA in the dark, occupying an entire 90 mm Petri dish in 7 d; surface white, flat, slightly felty to velvety, aerial mycelium scant, margin irregular, filiform. Reverse pale luteous, without diffusible pigments. On SNA with sparse aerial mycelium, sporulation moderate on the surface of the medium.

Material examined. SOUTH AFRICA, Eastern Cape, from mixed pasture samples, May 2020, collected by A. Davis, isolated by C. Dewing, Close to Gamtoos River Mouth: CBS 151775 = CMW 58689 = CN04015, Outside

Humansdorp, close to Clarkson: CMW 58690 = CN070F3, CMW 58696 = CN071I8, CMW-IA 003340 = CMW 61384 = CN071H2, CMW 58693 = CN071H8, Humansdorp area: CMW 58691 = CN070G8, CMW 58692 = CN070G9, CMW-IA 002132 = CMW 60930 = CN070H9, CMW 58697 = CN104D4, CMW 58698 = CN106F2, CMW 58699 = CN106F3, CMW 58700 = CN106F4, close to Tsitsikamma on Sea: CMW 58694 = CN071I6, CMW 58695 = CN071I7, CMW 58696 = CN071I8.

Notes. *Fusarium goeppertmayerae* belongs to the *Incaratum*-clade and is closely related to the undescribed *Fusarium* FIESC 22 isolated from the human sinus cavity (O'Donnell et al. 2009) and *F. sylviaearleae* isolated from a leaf lesion of *Sporobolus natalensis* (*Poaceae*) (Tan and Shivas 2023). No morphological data are available for *Fusarium* FIESC 22 or *F. sylviaearleae*. Furthermore, we demonstrate that strains NRRL 32865 and NRRL 13335, previously considered to belong to *F. guilinense*, belong to *F. goeppertmayerae*, with *F. guilinense* (LC12160^T) a distant relative.

Fusarium mariecurieae Dewing, Visagie and Yilmaz, **sp. nov.**

MycoBank No: 855722

Figure 4

Etymology. Latin, *mariecurieae*, named after Maria Salomea Skłodowska-Curie (known simply as Marie Curie) (1867–1934), who was a renowned physicist and chemist known for her pioneering research on radioactivity. We also chose this name, as this study was supported by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) grant (number 101008129), project acronym “Mycobiomics”.

Type. SOUTH AFRICA, Eastern Cape, from mixed pasture samples, May 2020, collected by A. Davis (**holotype:** PRU(M) 4611, dried specimen in a metabolically inactive state; **ex-type strain:** CBS 152079 = CMW 58673 = CN072A3).

Description. *Conidiophores* borne on aerial mycelium, 13–106 µm tall, unbranched, sympodial or irregularly branched, bearing terminal or lateral phialides, often reduced to single phialides; *aerial phialides* mono- and polyphialidic, subulate to subcylindrical, proliferating percurrently, smooth- and thin-walled, 3.5–28.5 × 1.5–4 µm, with inconspicuous thickening; *aerial conidia*

ellipsoidal, fusiform, slightly allantoid to falcate, slender, curved dorsiventrally and more pronounced on the apical half, tapering towards both ends, with a blunt to conical and straight to slightly curved apical cell and a blunt to papillate basal cell, 0–3(–5)-septate; 0-septate conidia: $8\text{--}11 \times 2.5\text{--}3 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $9.6 \times 2.6 \mu\text{m}$) ($n = 2$); 1-septate conidia: $11\text{--}20 \times 3\text{--}4 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $15.6 \times 3.3 \mu\text{m}$) ($n = 11$); 2-septate conidia: $15\text{--}23 \times 3\text{--}4 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $18.7 \times 3.6 \mu\text{m}$) ($n = 6$); 3-septate conidia: $18.5\text{--}30.5 \times 3\text{--}5 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $23.2 \times 3.8 \mu\text{m}$) ($n = 26$); 5-septate conidia: $33 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ ($n = 1$). *Sporodochia* peach to pale straw, formed abundantly on carnation leaves. *Sporodochial conidiophores* densely and irregularly branched, bearing apical whorls of 2–3 phialides; *sporodochial phialides* monophialidic, subulate to subcylindrical, $6\text{--}22 \times 2\text{--}4 \mu\text{m}$, smooth, thin-walled, with inconspicuous periclinal thickening; *sporodochial conidia* falcate, curved dorsiventrally, tapering towards both ends, with a slightly curved apical cell and a blunt to foot-like basal cell, (1–)3–5-septate, hyaline, smooth- and thin-walled; 1-septate conidia: $12\text{--}17 \times 3 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $14.4 \times 3.2 \mu\text{m}$) ($n = 2$); 3-septate conidia: $19\text{--}36 \times 3\text{--}4 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $30.0 \times 3.8 \mu\text{m}$) ($n = 23$); 4-septate conidia: $31\text{--}36 \times 4\text{--}5 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $33.2 \times 4.3 \mu\text{m}$) ($n = 4$); 5-septate conidia: $30 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ ($n = 1$). *Chlamydoconidia* not observed.

Culture characteristics. Colonies on PDA incubated at 25 °C in the dark with an average radial growth rate of 5–9 mm/d, occupying an entire 90 mm Petri dish in 7 d; surface white, flat, felty to velvety around the center, floccose towards the margins, radiate, with abundant aerial mycelium, margin irregular, filiform. Additional colony diam (after 7 d): PDA 10 °C 12–17; PDA at 15 °C 29–40; PDA at 20 °C 48–70; PDA at 30 °C 68–76; PDA at 35 °C 4–6. Odour absent. Reverse yellowish white (3A2). Diffusible pigments absent. On OA in the dark, occupying an entire 90 mm Petri dish in 7 d; surface white, floccose around the center, flat, felty to velvety towards the margin, radiate, with abundant aerial mycelium, margin irregular, filiform. Reverse yellowish white (2A2). Diffusible pigments absent. On SNA with sparse aerial mycelium, sporulation moderate on the surface of the medium.

Additional material examined. SOUTH AFRICA, Eastern Cape, from mixed pasture samples, May 2020, collected by A. Davis, isolated by C. Dewing, Humansdorp area: CMW 58664 = CN070E5, CMW-IA 002131 = CMW 60929 = CN070F5, CMW-IA 003328 = CMW 61372 = CN070G5, CMW 58666 =

CN070H6, CBS 151774 = CMW 58667 = CN070I7, CMW 58668 = CN071B2, CMW 58669 = CN071C1, CMW 58670 = CN071E4, CMW-IA 002136 = CMW 60934 = CN071F2, CMW-IA 002137 = CMW 60935 = CN071F3, CMW 58671 = CN071F4, CMW 58676 = CN072E2, CMW 58677 = CN104C2, CMW 58678 = CN104E1, CMW 58679 = CN106F1, CMW 58680 = CN106F8, CMW 61535 = CN106F9, CMW 58681 = CN106G1, CMW 58682 = CN106G2, CMW 58683 = CN106G3, CMW 58684 = CN106G4, CN106G5, CMW-IA 003764 = CMW 61536 = CN110D9, CMW 58685 = CN110E2, CN115C6, CN115C9, CN115D4, CN115E8, CMW 61371 = CN070G1, Outside Humansdorp, close to Clarkson: CMW 58665 = CN070G2, CMW 58672 = CN071H1, CMW 58674 = CN072B2, Close to Villa Fonte: CMW 58675 = CN072B6.

Notes. *Fusarium mariecurieae* belongs to the *Incaratum*-clade and is most similar to an unsupported clade containing the following species: *F. caatingaense* (FIESC 20) (Santos et al. 2019), *F. citrullicola* (nom. inval.) (Khuna et al. 2022), *F. irregulare* (FIESC 15) (Wang et al. 2019), *F. luffae* (FIESC 18) (Wang et al. 2019), *F. mianyangense* (Han et al. 2023), *F. multiceps* (FIESC 19) (Xia et al. 2019), *F. pernambucanum* (FIESC 17) (Santos et al. 2019) and *F. sulawesiense* (FIESC 16) (Maryani et al. 2019). *Fusarium mariecurieae* produces both aerial mono- and polyphialides compared to *F. irregulare* that only produces monophialides (Wang et al. 2019), *F. luffae* that produces only polyphialides (Wang et al. 2019) and *F. mianyangense* that lacks aerial phialides (Han et al. 2023). Aerial conidia from *F. mariecurieae* (0–3(–5)-septate; 8–30.5 × 3–5 µm) are smaller than that of *F. irregulare* (mostly 3-septate; 16–38.5 × 3–5 µm) (Wang et al. 2019), *F. luffae* (3–5)-septate; 26.5–46 × 4–5 µm) (Wang et al. 2019), *F. multiceps* (1–)3–4(–5)-septate; 16–37 × 3–4 µm) (Xia et al. 2019), *F. pernambucanum* (1–7)-septate; 7–57 × 2.5–5 µm) (Santos et al. 2019) and *F. sulawesiense* (3–5(–9)-septate; 20.5–67 × 3.5–6 µm) (Maryani et al. 2019). Aerial conidia from *F. caatingaense* (0–6-septate; 6–45 × 2.5–5 µm) (Santos et al. 2019) and *F. citrullicola* (1–5-septate; 8–39 × 2–4.9 µm) (Khuna et al. 2022) were, at their largest, bigger than those of *F. mariecurieae*, while aerial conidia were absent from *F. mianyangense* (Han et al. 2023). Sporodochia were absent from *F. citrullicola*, *F. irregulare* and *F. luffae* (Wang et al. 2019), while chlamydospores were absent from *F. irregulare*, *F. luffae*, *F. mianyangense*, *F. multiceps* and *F. sulawesiense* (Maryani et al. 2019;

Wang et al. 2019; Xia et al. 2019; Han et al. 2023). Sporodochial conidia from *F. mariecurieae* (1–3(–5)-septate; 12–36 × 3–5 µm) were smaller than that of *F. caatingaense* (1–5-septate; 15–50 × 2–4.5 µm) (Santos et al. 2019), *F. mianyangense* (3(–5)-septate; 24.5–36.6 × 2.5–4.9 µm) (Han et al. 2023), *F. multiceps* ((1–)2–5-septate; 16–46 × 3–4 µm) (Xia et al. 2019) and *F. sulawesiense* ((3–)5(–6)-septate; 29.5–43.5 × 4–5.5 µm) (Maryani et al. 2019). Colony colour on PDA differs between *F. mariecurieae* and closely related species (Maryani et al. 2019; Santos et al. 2019; Wang et al. 2019; Xia et al. 2019; Han et al. 2023) as most other species show more colour across the surface and reverse compared to the white surface and yellowish white (3A2) reverse of *F. mariecurieae*. Growth rate after 7 d on PDA for *F. mariecurieae* is faster (>90 mm plate) than that of *F. citrullicola* (68–74.5 mm) (Khuna et al. 2022), *F. irregulare* (53–59 mm) (Wang et al. 2019), *F. luffae* (53–57 mm) (Wang et al. 2019) and *F. mianyangense* (74–80 mm) (Han et al. 2023). The growth of *F. multiceps* (>90 mm plate) (Xia et al. 2019) is similar to that of *F. mariecurieae*, while the growth rate in terms of diameter was not reported for *F. caatingaense*, *F. pernambucanum* and *F. sulawesiense* (Maryani et al. 2019; Santos et al. 2019). Pairwise comparisons revealed that *F. mariecurieae* differs from other species by at least 1, 4 and 12 bp for *CaM*, *RPB2* and *TEF*, respectively.

Fusarium pascuum Dewing, Visagie and Yilmaz, **sp. nov.**

MycoBank No: 855720

Figure 5

Etymology. Latin, *pascuum*, meaning pasture, referring to the species isolated from grass pastures.

Type. SOUTH AFRICA, Eastern Cape, from mixed pasture samples, May 2020, collected by A. Davis (**holotype:** PRU(M) 4600, dried specimen in a metabolically inactive state; **ex-type strain:** CBS 151772 = CMW 58653 = CN159G4 = CN071C4).

Description. *Conidiophores* borne on aerial mycelium, 15.5–101 µm tall, unbranched, sympodial or irregularly branched, bearing terminal or lateral phialides, often reduced to single phialides; *aerial phialides* mono- and

polyphialidic, subulate to subcylindrical, proliferating percurrently, smooth- and thin-walled, $4\text{--}43 \times 1\text{--}4.5 \mu\text{m}$, with inconspicuous periclinal thickening; *aerial conidia* fusiform, falcate, slender, curved dorsiventrally and more pronounced on the apical half, tapering towards both ends, with a blunt to conical and straight to slightly curved apical cell and a blunt to papillate basal cell, 0–3-septate conidia; 0-septate conidia: $7\text{--}17 \times 2\text{--}5 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $11.7 \times 3.2 \mu\text{m}$) (n = 34); 1-septate conidia: $12\text{--}26 \times 3\text{--}6 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $19.2 \times 3.8 \mu\text{m}$) (n = 14); 2-septate conidia: $23\text{--}32 \times 4\text{--}6 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $26.9 \times 4.5 \mu\text{m}$) (n = 7); 3-septate conidia: $27\text{--}32 \times 3\text{--}5 \mu\text{m}$ (av. $29.5 \times 4.4 \mu\text{m}$) (n = 2). *Sporodochia* and *chlamydospores* not observed.

Culture characteristics. Colonies on PDA incubated at 25 °C in the dark with an average radial growth rate of 3–10 mm/d and reaching 80 mm diam at 25 °C; surface white, flat, felty to velvety, radiate, with abundant aerial mycelium, margin irregular, filiform. Additional colony diam (after 7 d, in mm): PDA at 10 °C 13–15; PDA at 15 °C 36–42; PDA at 20 °C 63–65; PDA at 30 °C 34–39; PDA at 35 °C no growth. Odour absent. Reverse yellowish white (3A2). Diffusible pigments absent. On OA in the dark, occupying an entire 90 mm Petri dish in 7 d; surface white, flat, felty to velvety, radiate, with abundant aerial mycelium, margin irregular, filiform. Reverse yellowish white (3A2). Diffusible pigments absent. On SNA with sparse aerial mycelium, sporulation moderate on the surface of the medium.

Additional material examined. SOUTH AFRICA, Eastern Cape, from mixed pasture samples, May 2020 collected by A. Davis, isolated by C. Dewing, Humansdorp area: CMW-IA 003320 = CMW 61364 = CN056A8, CMW 58649 = CN070E7, CMW 58650 = CN070F7, CMW-IA 002133 = CMW 60931 = CN070I3, CMW 58651 = CN070I4, CMW 58652 = CN071B8, CMW 58654 = CN071D3, CMW 58655 = CN071E9, CMW 58662 = CN104D6, CMW 58663 = CN104D7, close to Kou-Kamma: CMW 58656 = CN071F9, Outside Humansdorp, close to Clarkson: CMW 58657 = CN071G8, CMW 58660 = CN071I9, CMW 58661 = CN072A1, close to Tsitsikamma on Sea: CMW 58658 = CN071I3, CMW 58659 = CN071I5.

Notes. *Fusarium pasuum* belongs to the *Camptoceras*-clade (as introduced by Han et al. (2023)) and is closely related to *F. fecundum*. Both *F. pasuum* and *F. fecundum* produce aerial mono- and polyphialides. Aerial conidia from

F. pascuum (0–3-septate; 7–32 × 2–6 µm) are comparably smaller than those of *F. fecundum* ((1–)2–4(–6)-septate; 3.6–35.8 × 3.6–6.8 µm) (Han et al. 2023). Sporodochia and chlamydospores are absent in both *F. pascuum* and *F. fecundum*. Colony colour on PDA differs between *F. pascuum* and *F. fecundum*, where the former is completely white across the surface and the latter is greyish yellow in the centre, while the reverse of *F. pascuum* is yellowish white and *F. fecundum* just white (Han et al. 2023). Growth rate after 7 d on PDA in *F. pascuum* (reaching 80 mm) is slightly slower than that of *F. fecundum* (84–90 mm) (Han et al. 2023). Pairwise comparisons revealed that *F. pascuum* differs from other species by at least 8, 8 and 23 bp for *CaM*, *RPB2* and *TEF*, respectively.

Discussion

In a 2020 survey exploring fungal diversity in dairy pastures, 95 mixed pasture samples were collected across 14 dairy farms in the Eastern Cape of South Africa. A total of 155 *Fusarium* strains, belonging to the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC), were isolated from 12/14 dairy farms. Strains were analysed using a multigene phylogenetic approach, leading to the identification of 11 species, including five that are new. Of these, we opted to formally describe and name *F. cumulatum*, *F. mariecurieae* and *F. pascuum*. *Fusarium croceum* (n = 55) and *F. mariecurieae* (n = 33) were the most commonly isolated species, followed by *F. clavus* (n = 19), *F. pascuum* (n = 17), *F. goeppertmayerae* (n = 14), *F. coffeatum* (n = 7), *F. cumulatum* (n = 4), *F. brevicaudatum* (n = 2), *Fusarium* sp. nov. 1 (n = 2), *F. heslopieae* (n = 1) and *Fusarium* FIESC 27 (n = 1). Due to a lack of morphological character development in our strains, two of the new species were not described (e.g., *Fusarium* FIESC 27, *Fusarium* sp. nov. 1). In the future, it will be important to obtain additional isolates of the species and name them. Several recently FIESC-introduced species did not include morphological descriptions. This include *F. goeppertmayerae* that was introduced based on sequence differences of a *TEF* sequence in a single isolate (Tan and Shivas 2023). We found several new isolates of this species in pasture samples,

and here we provided a morphological description for the species and capture infraspecies variation in its DNA sequences.

Fusarium species are well-known for their frequent association with *Poaceae* (grasses), but of the 11 species identified, only five had previously been reported from this plant family. *Fusarium clavus* was reported from *Phalaris minor* (little seed canary grass), *Leucopoa sclerophylla*, *Secale montanum* (wild perennial rye) and *Triticum* (wheat) from Iran (Xia et al. 2019). *Fusarium coffeatum* and *F. heslopiae* were reported from *Cynodon nlemfuensis* (African Bermuda-grass) and *Sporobolus creber* (Western Rat-Tail grass), respectively (Lombard et al. 2019; Tan and Shivas 2024), while *F. croceum* has been isolated from wheat (*Triticum* sp.) from Iran (Xia et al. 2019). *Fusarium goeppertmayerae* has not previously been reported from grass species but was reported from maize peduncles from Australia (Tan and Shivas 2023). Given the diverse impacts of FIESC species, especially with regards to their ability to cause plant and animal diseases and produce mycotoxins (Kosiak et al. 2005; Desjardins 2006; O'Donnell et al. 2013; Villani et al. 2016; Munkvold 2017; O'Donnell et al. 2018; Gallo et al. 2022), it is crucial to investigate the potential implications that species present in our dairy pastures could have for animal health. This is especially relevant considering the growing evidence of *Fusarium* species contributing to toxic effects in livestock grazing on certain grasses (Kellerman et al. 2005; Bourke 2007).

Species previously implicated in kikuyu poisoning were identified in our study. Previous studies have identified *Fusarium* species as potential causal agents of kikuyu poisoning, a condition characterised by toxic effects in livestock, like cattle, that consume kikuyu grass (*Pennisetum clandestinum*) (Kellerman et al. 2005; Bourke 2007). Reports of kikuyu poisoning are sporadic in South Africa and Australia and it pose significant economic concerns in dairy farming due to high cattle mortality rates (Kellerman et al. 2005; Bourke 2007). While the exact cause of kikuyu poisoning remains uncertain, Ryley et al. (2007) hypothesised that mycotoxins like wortmannin and butenolide produced by species like *F. torulosum* (*Fusarium tricinctum* species complex (FTSC)) may be involved. Botha et al. (2014) studied the *Fusarium* present in Eastern Cape (South Africa) dairy pastures where cattle intoxication outbreaks occurred. Strains were identified based on *TEF* sequences, and similar to our survey (Dewing et al. 2025), they mostly detected FIESC species and did not detect *F.*

torulosum. Both studies, Botha et al. (2014) and Dewing et al. (2025), detected *F. brevicaudatum*, *F. clavus*, *F. croceum* and the two species we describe above as *F. pasuum* and *F. mariecurieae* (Figure S4). Additionally, our study identified *F. cumulatum*, *F. heslopieae*, *Fusarium* FIESC 27 and *Fusarium* sp. nov. 1, which were not detected in the study by Botha et al. (2014). Conversely, Botha et al. (2014) identified *F. tangerrinum* and *Fusarium* FIESC 34 (undescribed), which were not found in our survey.

Although the mycotoxigenic potential of the species described in this study is unknown, members of the FIESC have been reported to produce various mycotoxins (Phillips et al. 1989; Logrieco et al. 1998; Hestbjerg et al. 2002; Kosiak et al. 2005; Villani et al. 2016; O'Donnell et al. 2018). Many of these, especially deoxynivalenol, fumonisins and zearalenone, can adversely affect cattle health, leading to symptoms such as decreased conception rates, reproductive disorders, feed refusal, gastrointestinal problems, immunosuppression, reduced animal performance, tremors, weight loss and even death (Trenholm et al. 1985; European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) 2004; Morgavi and Riley 2007; Fink-Gremmels 2008). However, toxicological information and their effects on animals for some commonly produced secondary metabolites, such as beauvericin, remain unavailable (De Felice et al. 2023; Hasuda and Bracarense 2024). This lack of information is often due to the absence of regulations for these mycotoxins, resulting in a lack of standardised testing methods, as well as limited monitoring and reporting requirements. It is also crucial to consider the potential synergistic, additive, or antagonistic interactions between emerging mycotoxins and other toxins in animal feed, as these combinations could pose unexpected health risks (Křížová et al. 2021). This is particularly true for the FIESC that has only occasionally been linked to cattle poisoning, possibly due to a lack of sufficient studies on pasture fungal diversity. Therefore, the presence of FIESC species in dairy pasture still poses a potential risk of mycotoxin contamination when these grasses are used for animal feed (Botha et al. 2014), and research into their mycotoxins is urgently needed.

Our study provides a valuable insight into the diversity of the FIESC in dairy pastures in the Eastern Cape. The presence of *Fusarium* species, seemingly in a consistent community in this environment, underscores the importance of further studying these

species. Further research must focus on what secondary metabolites, including mycotoxins, these species produce. This will provide insights into their potential impact on cattle health in dairy pastures.

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Figures

Figure 1. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex based on a concatenated dataset, *CaM*, *RPB2* and *TEF*. Strains of species isolated from this study are shown in black bold text; strains of new species are indicated in red bold text. The tree was rooted to *Fusarium concolor*. Branch support in nodes higher than 80% are indicated at relevant branches (^T = ex-type, ^{ET} = epitype, ^{NT} = neotype).

Figure 2. *Fusarium cumulatum* (CBS 151773, ex-type culture) **A** colonies front (top row) and reverse (bottom row) on PDA after 7 d at 25 °C light, dark and nUV and OA after 7 d at 25 °C dark (from left to right), respectively **B** sporodochial formation on the surface of carnation leaves **C, D** sporodochial conidiophores and phialides **E–G** aerial conidiophores and phialides **H–M** intercalary and terminal chlamyospores **N** sporodochial conidia. Scale bars: 10 µm.

Figure 3. *Fusarium goeppertmayerae* (CBS 151775) **A** colonies front (top row) and reverse (bottom row) on PDA after 7 d at 25 °C light, dark and nUV and OA after 7 d at 25 °C dark (from left to right), respectively **B** sporodochial formation on the surface of carnation leaves **C** sporodochial conidiophores **D–I** aerial mono- and polyphialides **J–K** aerial conidia **L** sporodochial conidia. Scale bars: 10 µm.

Figure 4. *Fusarium mariecurieae* (CBS 152079, ex-type culture) **A** colonies front (top row) and reverse (bottom row) on PDA after 7 d at 25 °C light, dark and nUV and OA after 7 d at 25 °C dark (from left to right), respectively **B** sporodochial formation on the surface of carnation leaves **C**, **D** sporodochial conidiophores and phialides **E–G** aerial conidiophores **H–I** mono- and polyphialides **J–K** aerial conidia **L** sporodochial conidia. Scale bars: 10 μm.

Figure 5. *Fusarium pascuum* (CBS 151772, ex-type culture) **A** Colonies front (top row) and reverse (bottom row) on PDA after 7 d at 25 °C light, dark and nUV and OA after 7 d at 25 °C dark (from left to right), respectively **B–J** aerial conidiophores and phialides **K** aerial microconidia **L, M** aerial macroconidia. Scale bars: 10 µm.

Supplementary figures

All data and supporting materials are available on Figshare (<https://figshare.com/s/9b182337df860da61cc4>)

Figure S1. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of *the Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex based on the *CaM* dataset. Strains of species isolated from this study are shown in black bold text; strains of newly described species are indicated in red bold text. Tree was rooted to *Fusarium concolor*. Branch support in nodes higher than 80% are indicated at relevant branches (^T = ex-type, ^{ET} = epitype, ^{NT} = neotype).

Figure S2. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of *the Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex based on the *RPB2* dataset. Strains of species isolated from this study are shown in black bold text; strains of newly described species are indicated in red bold text. Tree was rooted to *Fusarium concolor*. Branch support in nodes higher than 80% are indicated at relevant branches (^T = ex-type, ^{ET} = epitype, ^{NT} = neotype).

Figure S3. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of *the Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex based on the *TEF* dataset. Strains of species isolated from this study are shown in black bold text; strains of newly described species are indicated in red bold text. Tree was rooted to *Fusarium concolor*. Branch support in nodes higher than 80% are indicated at relevant branches (^T = ex-type, ^{ET} = epitype, ^{NT} = neotype).

Figure S4. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex based on the *TEF* dataset obtained from Botha et al. (2014) and relevant references sequences. Strains of species isolated from this study are shown in black bold text; strains of newly described species are indicated in red bold text. Tree was rooted to *Fusarium concolor*. Branch support in nodes higher than 80% are indicated at relevant branches (^T = ex-type, ^{ET} = epitype, ^{NT} = neotype).

Tables

Table 1. *Fusarium* strains from the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC) isolated from mixed dairy pastures from the Eastern Cape, South Africa.

Species	Strain	TEF	CaM	RPB1	RPB2
Camptoceras-clade (FIESC; Han et al. (2023) = originally the FCAMSC)					
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW-IA 003320 = CMW 61364 = CN056A8	OR670986	OR669177	PP187127	PP235233
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58649 = CN070E7	PP187098	—	PP187129	PQ467747
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58650 = CN070F7	OR670991	OR669181	PP187132	PP158160
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW-IA 002133 = CMW 60931 = CN070I3	PP187102	PP187122	—	PQ467748
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58651 = CN070I4	OR671007	OR669194	PP187144	PQ467749
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58652 = CN071B8	OR671025	OR669210	PP187152	PP158176
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CBS 151772 = CMW 58653 = CN159G4 = CN071C4	OR671027	OR669212	PP187155	PP158178
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58654 = CN071D3	OR671033	OR669216	PP187158	PQ467750
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58655 = CN071E9	OR671039	OR669221	PP187161	PP158183
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58656 = CN071F9	OR671044	OR669225	PP187166	PP235238
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58657 = CN071G8	OR671051	OR669229	PP187168	PQ467751
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58658 = CN071I3	OR671057	OR669233	PP187173	PQ467752
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58659 = CN071I5	OR671058	OR669234	PP187175	PP158189
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58660 = CN071I9	OR671061	OR669237	PP187179	PQ467753
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58661 = CN072A1	OR671062	OR669238	PP187180	PP158191
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58662 = CN104D6	OR671090	OR669265	PP187190	PP158199
<i>F. pascuum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58663 = CN104D7	OR671091	OR669266	PP187191	PQ467754
Equiseti-clade (FIESC)					
<i>F. brevicaudatum</i>	CMW-IA 003335 = CMW 61379 = CN071C6	OR671028	—	—	—
<i>F. brevicaudatum</i>	CMW-IA 003765 = CMW 61537 = CN110E5	OR671114	—	—	—

Table 1. (continue)

Species	Strain	TEF	CaM	RPB1	RPB2
<i>F. clavus</i>	CMW-IA 001930 = CMW 60748 = CN041D2	OR670983	—	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CMW-IA 003330 = CMW 61374 = CN070H4	OR671001	OR669189	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN070H7	PP187101	PP187121	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN070I8	OR671010	OR669197	—	PP158167
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071A3	OR671013	OR669200	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071A4	OR671014	OR669201	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071B3	OR671020	OR669205	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071B4	OR671021	OR669206	—	PP158174
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071D1	OR671031	OR669215	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071D2	OR671032	—	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071D8	OR671034	OR669217	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071E1	OR671035	OR669218	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071E2	OR671036	—	—	PP158180
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071G5	OR671049	OR669227	—	PP158187
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071G6	OR671050	OR669228	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN071H6	OR671054	-	—	—
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN072A6	OR671066	OR669241	—	PP158193
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN072A9	OR671069	OR669244	—	PP158195
<i>F. clavus</i>	CN072E4	OR671076	OR669251	—	PP158196
<i>F. croceum</i>	CMW-IA 001923 = CMW 60732 = CN040I7	OR670982	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CMW-IA 001934 = CMW 60752 = CN041D9	OR670984	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN048C3	OR670985	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070F6	OR670990	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CMW-IA 003326 = CMW 61370 = CN070F8	OR670992	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070F9	PP187099	—	—	PQ467755

Table 1. (continue)

Species	Strain	TEF	CaM	RPB1	RPB2
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070G4	OR670995	OR669184	PP187135	PP158162
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070G6	OR670997	—	PP187137	PQ467756
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070G7	OR670998	OR669186	PP187138	PQ467757
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070H1	OR671000	OR669188	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070H5	OR671002	OR669190	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070I1	OR671005	OR669193	PP187143	PQ467758
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070I2	OR671006	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070I5	OR671008	OR669195	PP187145	PP158165
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN070I9	OR671011	OR669198	PP187147	PP158168
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN071B1	OR671018	OR669203	PP187148	PP158173
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN071C7	OR671029	OR669213	PP187156	PQ467759
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN071F1	OR671040	OR669222	PP187162	PP158184
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN071G1	OR671045	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN071G2	OR671046	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN071G3	OR671047	—	PP187167	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN071H3	PP187104	—	PP187170	PQ467760
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN071H7	OR671055	OR669231	PP187171	PP158188
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN071I4	PP187105	PP187124	PP187174	PP235239
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN072A5	OR671065	OR669240	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN072A8	OR671068	OR669243	PP187182	PP158194
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN072B1	OR671070	OR669245	PP187183	PQ467761
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN072B4	OR671072	OR669247	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN072B8	OR671074	OR669249	—	PP235242
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN103E5	OR671077	OR669252	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN103E6	OR671078	OR669253	—	—

Table 1. (continue)

Species	Strain	TEF	CaM	RPB1	RPB2
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104B9	OR671079	OR669254	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104C1	OR671080	OR669255	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104C3	OR671082	OR669257	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104C4	OR671083	OR669258	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104C5	OR671084	OR669259	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104C7	OR671085	OR669260	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104C9	OR671086	OR669261	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104D5	OR671089	OR669264	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104D8	OR671092	OR669267	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104E4	OR671094	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN104E8	OR671095	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN106E9	OR671096	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN110D4	OR671107	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN110D6	OR671109	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN110D8	OR671110	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN110E1	OR671112	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN115A2	PP187108	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN115A3	PP187109	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN115A4	PP187110	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN115B2	PP187111	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN115B6	PP187112	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN115C8	PP187114	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN115D9	PP187117	—	—	—
<i>F. croceum</i>	CN119E7	PP187119	—	—	—
<i>F. cumulatum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58686 = CN071B9	OR671026	OR669211	PP187153	PP158177

Table 1. (continue)

Species	Strain	TEF	CaM	RPB1	RPB2
<i>F. cumulatum</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58687 = CN071E5	OR671038	OR669220	PP187160	PP158182
<i>F. cumulatum</i> sp. nov.	CMW-IA 002138 = CMW 60936 = CN071G4	OR671048	OR669226	—	PP158186
<i>F. cumulatum</i> sp. nov.	CBS 151773 = CMW 58688 = CN104D3	OR671087	OR669262	PP187188	PP158197
<i>F. heslopieae</i>	CN071C8	OR671030	OR669214	PP187157	PP158179
Incarnatum-clade (FIESC)					
<i>F. coffeatum</i>	CMW-IA 003332 = CMW 61376 = CN071A2	OR671012	OR669199	—	PP158169
<i>F. coffeatum</i>	CN071A5	OR671015	OR669202	—	PP158170
<i>F. coffeatum</i>	CN071A6	OR671016	—	—	PP158171
<i>F. coffeatum</i>	CN071A7	OR671017	—	—	PP158172
<i>F. coffeatum</i>	CMW-IA 003334 = CMW 61378 = CN071B5	OR671022	OR669207	—	PP158175
<i>F. coffeatum</i>	CMW-IA 003341 = CMW 61385 = CN072A4	OR671064	—	—	—
<i>F. coffeatum</i>	CN072A7	OR671067	OR669242	—	—
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CBS 151775 = CMW 58689 = CN040I5	OR670981	OR669176	PP187126	PP158159
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58690 = CN070F3	OR670988	OR669179	PP187130	PP235234
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58691 = CN070G8	OR670999	OR669187	PP187139	PP158163
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58692 = CN070G9	PP187100	PP187120	PP187140	PP235236
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW-IA 002132 = CMW 60930 = CN070H9	OR671004	OR669192	PP187142	PP158164
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW-IA 003340 = CMW 61384 = CN071H2	OR671053	—	—	—
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58693 = CN071H8	OR671056	OR669232	PP187172	PQ467762
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58694 = CN071I6	OR671059	OR669235	PP187176	PP158190
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58695 = CN071I7	PP187106	PP187125	PP187177	PQ467763
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58696 = CN071I8	OR671060	OR669236	PP187178	PP235240
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58697 = CN104D4	OR671088	OR669263	PP187189	PP158198
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58698 = CN106F2	OR671098	OR669270	PP187194	PP158201
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58699 = CN106F3	OR671099	OR669271	PP187195	PP235244

Table 1. (continue)

Species	Strain	TEF	CaM	RPB1	RPB2
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58700 = CN106F4	OR671100	OR669272	PP187196	PP158202
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58664 = CN070E5	OR670987	OR669178	PP187128	PQ467764
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW-IA 002131 = CMW 60929 = CN070F5	OR670989	OR669180	PP187131	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58665 = CN070G2	OR670994	OR669183	PP187134	PP158161
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW-IA 003328 = CMW 61372 = CN070G5	OR670996	OR669185	PP187136	PP235235
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58666 = CN070H6	OR671003	OR669191	PP187141	PQ467765
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CBS 151774 = CMW 58667 = CN070I7	OR671009	OR669196	PP187146	PP158166
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58668 = CN071B2	OR671019	OR669204	PP187149	PQ467746
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58669 = CN071C1	PP187103	PP187123	PP187154	PQ467766
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58670 = CN071E4	OR671037	OR669219	PP187159	PP158181
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW-IA 002136 = CMW 60934 = CN071F2	OR671041	—	PP187163	PP235237
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW-IA 002137 = CMW 60935 = CN071F3	OR671042	OR669223	PP187164	PQ467767
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58671 = CN071F4	OR671043	OR669224	PP187165	PP158185
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58672 = CN071H1	OR671052	OR669230	PP187169	PQ467768
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CBS 152079 = CMW 58673 = CN072A3	OR671063	OR669239	PP187181	PP158192
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58674 = CN072B2	OR671071	OR669246	PP187184	PP235241
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58675 = CN072B6	OR671073	OR669248	PP187185	PQ467769
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58676 = CN072E2	OR671075	OR669250	PP187186	PQ467770
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58677 = CN104C2	OR671081	OR669256	PP187187	PP235243
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58678 = CN104E1	OR671093	OR669268	PP187192	PQ467771
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58679 = CN106F1	OR671097	OR669269	PP187193	PP158200
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58680 = CN106F8	PP187107	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW-IA 003763 = CMW 61535 = CN106F9	OR671101	OR669273	PP187197	PP235245
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58681 = CN106G1	OR671102	OR669274	PP187198	PP158203
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58682 = CN106G2	OR671103	—	PP187199	PQ467772

Table 1. (continue)

Species	Strain	TEF	CaM	RPB1	RPB2
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58683 = CN106G3	OR671104	—	PP187200	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58684 = CN106G4	OR671105	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CN106G5	OR671106	OR669275	PP187201	PP235246
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW-IA 003764 = CMW 61536 = CN110D9	OR671111	OR669277	PP187202	PP235247
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CMW 58685 = CN110E2	OR671113	OR669278	PP187203	PP158204
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CN115C6	PP187113	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CN115C9	PP187115	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CN115D4	PP187116	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i> sp. nov.	CN115E8	PP187118	—	—	—
<i>Fusarium</i> FIESC 27	CMW-IA 003327 = CMW 61371 = CN070G1	OR670993	OR669182	PP187133	PQ276899
<i>Fusarium</i> sp. nov. 1	CMW-IA 002134 = CMW 60932 = CN071B6	OR671023	OR669208	PP187150	PQ467773
<i>Fusarium</i> sp. nov. 1	CMW-IA 002135 = CMW 60933 = CN071B7	OR671024	OR669209	PP187151	PQ467774

Table 2. Primer pairs and PCR conditions used in this study.

Locus	PCR amplification procedure	Primer	Primer sequence (5'-3')*	Reference
<i>TEF</i>	95 °C 5 min; 35 cycles of 95 °C 45 s, 52 °C 45 s, 72 °C 90 s; 72 °C 8 min; 10 °C soak	EF1	ATGGGTAAGGARGACAAGAC	O'Donnell et al. (1998)
		EF2	GGARGTACCAGTSATCATG	O'Donnell et al. (1998)
<i>CaM</i>	94 °C 90 s; 35 cycles of 94 °C 45 s, 50 °C 45 s, 72 °C 1 min; 72 °C 10 min; 10 °C soak	CL1	GARTWCAAGGAGGCCTTCTC	O'Donnell et al. (2000)
		CL2A	TTTTTGCATCATGAGTTGGAC	O'Donnell et al. (2000)
<i>RPB1</i>	94 °C 90 s; 5 cycles of 94 °C 45 s, 54 °C 45 s, 72 °C 2 min; 5 cycles of 94 °C 45 s, 53 °C 45 s, 72 °C 2 min; 35 cycles of 94 °C 45 s, 52 °C 45s, 72 °C 2 min; 72 °C 10 min; 10 °C soak	Fa	CAYAARGARTCYATGATGGGWC	Hofstetter et al. (2007)
		R8	CAATGAGACCTTCTCGACCAGC	O'Donnell et al. (2010)
	94 °C 90 s; 5 cycles of 94 °C 45 s, 56 °C 45 s, 72 °C 2 min; 5 cycles of 94 °C 45 s, 55 °C 45 s, 72 °C 2 min; 35 cycles of 94 °C 45 s, 54 °C 45s, 72 °C 2 min; 72 °C 10 min; 10 °C soak	F8	TTCTTCCACGCCATGGCTGGTCG	O'Donnell et al. (2010)
		G2R	GTCATYTG DGT DGC DGGYT CDCC	O'Donnell et al. (2010)
<i>RPB2</i>	95 °C 5 min; 40 cycles of 94 °C 30 s, 51 °C 90 s, 68 °C 2 min; 68 °C 5 min; 10 °C soak	5F2	GGGGWGAYCAGAAGAAGGC	Reeb et al. (2004)
		7Cr	CCCATRGCTTGYTTRCCCAT	Liu et al. (1999)

Table 2. (continue)

Locus	PCR amplification procedure	Primer	Primer sequence (5'-3')*	Reference
<i>RPB2</i>	95 °C 5 min; 40 cycles of 94 °C 30 s, 51 °C 90 s, 68 °C 2 min; 68 °C 5 min; 10 °C soak	7Cf	ATGGGYAARCAAGCYATGGG	Liu et al. (1999)
		11ar	GCRTGGATCTTRTCRTCSACC	Liu et al. (1999)

* R = A or G; S = C or G; W = A or T; Y = C or T.

Supplementary table

All data and supporting materials are available on Figshare (<https://figshare.com/s/9b182337df860da61cc4>)

Table S1. Strains examined in this study, with information about substrate, country and GenBank accessions of sequences.

Chapter 4:

Comparative analysis and variation of secondary metabolite biosynthesis gene clusters in the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex and other *Fusarium* lineages

Abstract

The *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC) is known to produce a wide range of secondary metabolites, including several mycotoxins. However, the secondary metabolite biosynthesis gene clusters within the FIESC remain understudied compared to other species complexes. In this study, we investigated the secondary metabolite production potential of four recently described FIESC members: *F. cumulatum*, *F. goeppertmayerae*, *F. mariecurieae* and *F. pasuum*. In vitro chemical analyses enabled the detection of 16 secondary metabolites, including the widely regulated mycotoxins such as deoxynivalenol, nivalenol and zearalenone, as well as emerging mycotoxins like beauvericin, diacetoxyscirpenol and equisetin. Additionally, the comparative genomics analyses revealed the presence of biosynthesis gene clusters encoding specific metabolites, despite these compounds not being detected under in vitro conditions. These results enabled a comparative assessment of the prevalence and diversity of secondary metabolite biosynthesis gene clusters among FIESC members and other *Fusarium* lineages. Our findings contribute to the current understanding of secondary metabolism within the FIESC and underscore its potential roles in pathogenicity, ecological adaptation, and mycotoxicosis in animals.

Key words

Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti species complex, Secondary metabolites, Mycotoxins, Comparative genomics

Introduction

Fusarium comprises a relatively diverse group of filamentous fungi, many of which are plant pathogens responsible for significant agricultural losses worldwide (Crous et al. 2021). These species infect a wide range of economically important crops, where it can also contaminate our food with secondary metabolites, including mycotoxins, that pose serious health risks to humans and animals upon ingestion (Wu et al. 2014; Becker-Algeri et al. 2016). Among the most studied mycotoxins are trichothecenes, fumonisins and zearalenone (ZEA), all of which have been linked to severe health effects, including immune suppression, carcinogenicity and reproductive toxicity (Desjardins 2006; Moretti et al. 2013).

Secondary metabolites serve functions beyond pathogenesis, often providing a competitive advantage to the fungi that produce them. Some of these bioactive compounds include chrysogine, fusapyrone, deoxyfusapyrone and sphingofungin B, each of which plays a role in fungal survival and adaptation. Chrysogine, for example, a yellow pigment produced by many filamentous fungi, offers protection against environmental stressors such as ultraviolet radiation (Frisvad and Samson 2004; Frisvad et al. 2004). While pigments often have antimicrobial activity, chrysogine lacks this property (Yunianto et al. 2014; Pagano and Dhar 2015). Fusapyrone and deoxyfusapyrone, known for their broad-spectrum antifungal properties, have been reported in *Fusarium mangiferae* (Atanasoff-Kardjalieff et al. 2021) and *F. incarnatum* (Altomare et al. 2004). These metabolites are believed to contribute to ecological fitness, survival and colonisation of the producing fungus (Kil et al. 2023). Sphingofungin B, which inhibits sphingolipid biosynthesis, plays a critical role in membrane integrity and cellular function (Horn et al. 1992; Van Middlesworth et al. 1992; Pruetz et al. 2008; Duan and Merrill 2015; Zhang et al. 2019). Together, these secondary metabolites highlight the diverse biochemical strategies employed by *Fusarium* species, not only for survival and adaptation but also for ecological dominance in their respective niches.

Comparative studies between the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex (FIESC) and other *Fusarium* lineages suggest substantial variation in secondary

metabolite biosynthesis pathways, pointing to evolutionary divergence in metabolic capabilities (Villani et al. 2019). While some *Fusarium* species share core mycotoxin biosynthesis genes, others possess unique gene clusters that may influence pathogenicity, host specificity and ecological adaptation. In particular, polyketide synthase (*PKS*) and non-ribosomal peptide synthetase (*NRPS*) genes play a critical role in mycotoxin biosynthesis (Hansen et al. 2015). Additionally, trichothecene (*TRI*) genes involved in its biosynthesis have been extensively studied for their impact on mycotoxin production (McCormick et al. 2011). However, it is important to recognise that the presence of a gene cluster does not guarantee metabolite production, just as the absence of a secondary metabolite in chemical analyses does not necessarily indicate the absence of the gene cluster (Hansen et al. 2015).

The FIESC has been increasingly recognised for its diverse range of mycotoxins (Krogh et al. 1989; Phillips et al. 1989; Haese et al. 1993; Singh et al. 1996; Hestbjerg et al. 2002; Kosiak et al. 2005; Villani et al. 2016; O'Donnell et al. 2018). Despite the increasing interest in the FIESC, the secondary metabolite profiles and biosynthesis gene clusters of the FIESC remain mostly underexplored. Further investigations into the FIESC secondary metabolism have highlighted notable differences in the *TRI* gene cluster compared to other trichothecene-producing *Fusarium* species, such as *F. graminearum* and *F. sporotrichioides* (Proctor et al. 2009). Proctor et al. (2009) demonstrated that in some FIESC strains, genes within the *TRI* cluster have been translocated, either within the cluster itself or from other genomic locations. Furthermore, the *TRI* transporter gene, responsible for trichothecene translocation, appears to be absent in the FIESC, while a novel transcription factor gene was identified within the cluster, a feature not observed in other trichothecene-producing *Fusarium* species (Proctor et al. 2009). These variations suggest that horizontal gene transfer, chromatin-based regulation, and environmental adaptation could be driving the structural and functional differences in the FIESC secondary metabolism (Campbell et al. 2012; Proctor et al. 2013; Qiu et al. 2016). Addressing these gaps requires an integrative approach that combines genomics, transcriptomics and metabolomics to uncover the full spectrum of secondary metabolites produced by the FIESC and their implications for agriculture, food safety and fungal ecology.

Dewing et al. (2025a) identified three novel *Fusarium* species during a survey of fungal diversity in mixed pastures of the Eastern Cape, South Africa, where a facial eczema outbreak had occurred in dairy cattle (Davis et al. 2025). These species were formally described based on morphological and phylogenetic analyses, yet their secondary metabolite profiles remain unexplored. The present study aims to characterise the secondary metabolite production profiles of these three newly identified *Fusarium* species, alongside *F. goeppertmayerae* (Tan and Shivas 2023), which has been previously described. Additionally, this study seeks to compare the prevalence and diversity of secondary metabolite biosynthesis gene clusters among FIESC species and other *Fusarium* lineages, as well as to investigate the presence or absence of core biosynthesis genes, especially in cases where expected secondary metabolites are not detected. Through these investigations, we aim to expand the understanding of secondary metabolism within the FIESC and its potential role in pathogenicity, ecological adaptation and mycotoxin-related animal diseases.

Materials and methods

Fungal isolates, genome sequencing and assembly

Representative strains of each species (*F. cumulatum*, *F. goeppertmayerae*, *F. mariecurieae*, *F. pascuum*) were selected for this study (Table 1). All strains are stored in the culture collection (CMW) of the Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI) at the University of Pretoria. Representative strains of *F. cumulatum* (CMW 58688), *F. mariecurieae* (CMW 58667), *F. pascuum* (CMW 58653) and *F. goeppertmayerae* (CMW 58689) were selected for genome sequencing. These strains are also deposited at the Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute (CBS) in Utrecht, the Netherlands.

For sequencing, cultures were grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA) (Van Waters and Rogers (VWR) International, Leuven, Belgium, Austria), and genomic DNA was extracted using the DNeasy Plant Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. DNA libraries were then prepared by the sequencing facility, which involved fragmenting the DNA, adding adapters, and performing quality

control. The libraries were sequenced using the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 S4 PE150 XP platform at Eurofins Genomics (Konstanz, Germany), providing the genomic data needed for further analysis.

The method employed for the quality trimming and filtering of raw sequence reads was similar to what was described by Aylward et al. (2024). Briefly, trimming was performed with Trimmomatic v0.36 (Bolger et al. 2014). SPAdes v3.15.4 (Bankevich et al. 2012) was used to assemble the trimmed reads. This initial assembly was referred to as assembly v1.0. Contigs of less than 500 bp were filtered out using bioawk (<https://github.com/lh3/bioawk>) to produce assembly v1.1. The default parameters were used for both the trimming, assembling and filtering steps. We used BUSCO v5 (Manni et al. 2021) to determine the genome statistics and evaluate the completeness of assembly v1.1. To assess genome completeness, the sordariomycota_odb10 lineages were used for BUSCO (Benchmarking Universal Single Copy Orthologs) analyses on all four genomes. Gene predictions for each genome were done with the program WebAUGUSTUS using *F. graminearum* as the species parameter (Hoff and Stanke 2013).

Secondary metabolite profiling

To determine the chemical diversity among *Fusarium* species, selected strains were cultured on PDA and yeast extract sucrose agar medium (YES, Frisvad (1981)) at 25 °C in the dark for 14 d. Secondary metabolites were extracted from approximately 1 g of each sample (\pm 5 agar plugs \approx 1 × 1 cm) using 3 mL of an acetonitrile/water/acetic acid solution (79:20:1, v/v/v) and thoroughly mixed on a vortex. Extracts were diluted 1:50 in acetonitrile/water (20:79, v/v) with 1% acetic acid. A volume of 5 μ L aliquot of the diluted extract was injected for analysis via a liquid chromatography/tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) system (QTrap5500, Applied Biosystems, Foster City, California, United States of America), while remaining extracts were stored at -25 °C (Sulyok et al. 2006).

Detection and quantification were performed using a Chromatographic separation was carried out with a reverse phase C18 column (Gemini, NX-C18, 5 μ m, 110 Å, 150 × 2 mm, Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) in an ultra-HPLC (UHPLC) system (Vanquish-

Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany). The gradient elution used water and acetonitrile, each containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid, as eluent A and B, respectively. The flow rate was set to 0.3 mL/min and the column was kept at 25 °C. The 45 min chromatographic method included a 2 min linear elution with 15% B, followed by a 30 min gradient to 95% B, 3 min at 95% B and a 10 min re-equilibration at 15% B. The UHPLC-system was coupled to a QExactive HF Orbitrap mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) via a heated electrospray ionisation (ESI) source (TurboIonSpray, Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany) in fast-polarity switching mode (positive/negative ionisation). Full MS/TopN MS/MS scans were performed in both positive and negative ionisation mode with a scan range of 100–1000 m/z and a resolution of 120 000 FWHM (at 200 m/z). MS/MS was triggered for ions in the inclusion list with a ± 1 m/z isolation window and collision energies of 25, 35, and 45 eV. Data were analysed using Thermo Scientific Xcalibur software. All analyses were only run once with no repeats.

Phylogenetic analysis

A phylogenetic tree was constructed using the coding sequences of 12 housekeeping genes (see Table S1) from 14 members of the FIESC and eight additional *Fusarium* species, covering the phylogenetic diversity of the genus for which publicly available genome sequences exist. For this purpose, sequences for the FIESC were retrieved using BLASTn searches against individual genome sequence databases in Geneious Prime 2019.2.3 (Biomatters Ltd., New Zealand). All sequences were aligned using MAFFT in Geneious Prime, and a maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree was generated in IQ-TREE (v2.1.2) (Nguyen et al. 2015) with 1 000 bootstrap replicates based on concatenated coding region sequences of all 12 housekeeping genes. Each region was treated as separate partitions in the analyses, while also applying substitution models specific to each partition. The phylogenetic tree was visualised in FigTree v. 1.4.4 and edited using Affinity Designer v. 1.6.1 (Serif (Europe) Ltd, Nottingham, UK).

Secondary metabolite biosynthesis genes comparison

To evaluate the genetic potential of each species for producing mycotoxins and other secondary metabolites, we conducted a comprehensive BLAST analysis on each genome sequence. In the BLAST analysis, we employed both BLASTn and tBLASTn methods in Geneious Prime but found that BLASTn often delivered no results. BLAST query sequences consisted of representative genes from previously described *PKS*, *NRPS* and *TRI* genes obtained from reference genomes/strains (Table S2). In cases where the secondary metabolite biosynthesis gene cluster was characterised in a strain without a provided genome and deposited to GenBank, we only used the cluster in the Clinker figures (see below) for comparative purposes but excluded this information from our phylogeny. These included *F. heterosporum* for equisetin, *F. graminearum* strains 88H1 and F15 for nivalenol (NIV) and *Aspergillus fumigatus* for sphingofungin B.

Clinker 0.0.21 (Gilchrist and Chooi 2021) was used to evaluate the global alignment of the cluster regions, with the display order optimised based on cluster similarity. An interactive synteny visualisation was also produced using Clinker and clustermap.js under default settings. Genes were grouped according to cluster similarity as identified by Clinker and labelled based on their annotated identities from NCBI. We also used Clinker to assess the homology of core biosynthesis genes and correlated this data with our secondary metabolite production data. Figures were manually edited in Affinity Designer v. 1.6.1 (Serif (Europe) Ltd, Nottingham, UK), where necessary.

Results

Genome sequencing and assembly

The genomic information obtained for our *Fusarium* species focused on assembly completeness, genome size, contig count and GC content (Table 1). The genomes analysed were similar in size, ranging from 37.3 Mb in *F. pascuum* to 38.6 Mb in *F. mariecurieae*. These genome sizes were consistent with those reported for other *Fusarium* species from different lineages, such as 43.9 Mb for *F. fujikuroi* (Wiemann et al. 2013), 36 Mb for *F. graminearum* (Cuomo et al. 2007) and 41.8 Mb for *F. verticillioides* (Ma et al. 2010). The GC content was relatively consistent across

species, ranging from 47.9% to 48.3%, indicating a close genetic composition within these *Fusarium* species.

Phylogenetic analysis

The phylogenetic analysis recovered four major *Fusarium* species complexes as distinct, well-supported clades (Figure 1). The *Fusarium sambucinum* species complex (FSAMSC), represented by *F. graminearum* and *F. poae*, was positioned basal in the tree, indicating it diverged earliest from the other lineages included in the analysis. The FIESC formed a monophyletic group comprising three well-resolved clades: *Incarnatum*, *Equiseti* and *Camptoceras*. This complex was recovered as a sister group to a clade comprising the *Fusarium fujikuroi* species complex (FFSC) and the *Fusarium oxysporum* species complex (FOSC), suggesting a closer evolutionary relationship between FIESC and the FFSC–FOSC group than with FSAMSC. Among the more derived lineages, FFSC and FOSC clustered together, indicating they share a more recent common ancestor with each other than with FIESC or FSAMSC. This overall topology reflects a clear phylogenetic separation among the four species complexes, with FSAMSC as the most distantly related and FFSC and FOSC as the most closely related.

Secondary metabolite profiling

Our strains produced 16 secondary metabolites against the available standards that were tested (Table 2, Figure 2). From these, we detected known mycotoxins such as deoxynivalenol (DON), NIV and ZEA. We also identified so-called “emerging mycotoxins” for which toxicological data and regulatory thresholds are still lacking (Vaclavikova et al. 2013; EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM) 2014). These included compounds such as beauvericin (BEA), diacetoxyscirpenol (DAS), equisetin and fusarisetin A, as well as the modified form(s) of DON (15-acetyldeoxynivalenol: 15-ADON), NIV (4-acetylnivalenol: 4-ANIV) and ZEA (alpha-zearalenol: α -ZOL, beta-zearalenol: β -ZOL and zearalenone-14-sulfate: ZEN-14-S) for which limited toxicological information is available. In addition, other secondary metabolites were also detected such as chrysogine, fusapyrone, deoxyfusapyrone and sphingofungin B.

Secondary metabolite production often differed depending on the growth medium used. In general, the growth on PDA stimulated higher production of fusarisetin A, sphingofungin B and ZEA (and its modified forms), while the growth on YES was optimal for the production of BEA, chrysogine, deoxyfusapyrone, DON, fusapyrone and NIV (and its modified form 4-ANIV). Intra- and interspecific differences were also observed in terms of secondary metabolite production. The section below describes the production patterns observed for the respective compounds detected.

BEA was only produced by strains of *F. mariecurieae* and *F. goeppertmayerae*. In many strains, the growth on PDA resulted in BEA concentrations either below the limit of detection or at lower levels compared to the growth on YES. For instance, *F. mariecurieae* CMW 58673 produced 1 036 µg/kg on PDA but production increased to 21 399 µg/kg on YES, highlighting the impact of growth medium on BEA production. Another example is *F. mariecurieae* CMW 58672 which produced no BEA on PDA but the concentration on YES was 5 714 µg/kg. Overall, growth on YES generally resulted in higher BEA production across strains, as illustrated by *F. mariecurieae* CMW 58679 and *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58694, which reached concentrations of 42 466 µg/kg and 44 135 µg/kg, respectively.

Chrysogine was produced by strains of *F. cumulatum* and *F. goeppertmayerae*. For the other two FIESC species, chrysogine levels were below the limit of detection on both media, indicating minimal or no production. In the case of *F. cumulatum*, strains CMW 58686 and CMW 58688 exhibited detectable chrysogine levels, with higher concentrations on YES. For example, *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686 produced 2 456 µg/kg on PDA and 5 651 µg/kg on YES, while *F. cumulatum* CMW 58688 produced 2 102 µg/kg on PDA and 8 191 µg/kg on YES, suggesting that fungal growth on YES may enhance chrysogine production for certain strains. In *F. goeppertmayerae*, strains like CMW 58689 and CMW 58694, only produced detectable chrysogine levels on YES media.

DON and 15-ADON were produced by only two *F. pasuum* strains, resulting in detectable levels of deoxynivalenol and 15-ADON on PDA and YES, with higher levels often observed on YES. For example, *F. pasuum* CMW 58652 produced 481 µg/kg

of DON and 1 130 µg/kg of 15-ADON on PDA, which increased to 8 592 µg/kg and 2 382 µg/kg, respectively, on YES. Strain CMW 58656 of *F. pascuum* showed a similar trend with higher DON production on YES, although its 15-ADON production was decreased from 807 µg/kg on PDA to 573 µg/kg on YES.

NIV and 4-ANIV were only detected in the two examined strains of *F. cumulatum*. In particular, *F. cumulatum* CMW 58688 produced 917 µg/kg of NIV on PDA, which increased to 1 403 µg/kg on YES, with detectable 4-ANIV production only on YES (1 080 µg/kg). In contrast, *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686 produced 2 144 µg/kg of NIV on PDA, which reduced to 1 610 µg/kg on YES, with detectable 4-ANIV production only on YES (910 µg/kg).

Deoxyfusapyrone and fusapyrone were detected in some strains of all four species. Most strains produced both compounds on both media, with generally higher production on YES. For instance, *F. pascuum* CMW 58652 produced 17 334 µg/kg of deoxyfusapyrone and 12 388 µg/kg of fusapyrone on PDA, which increased to 26 715 µg/kg and 13 742 µg/kg, respectively, on YES. Some strains exhibited substantial increases in production on YES, for example, *F. mariecurieae* CMW 58671 produced 45 752 µg/kg of deoxyfusapyrone and 65 814 µg/kg of fusapyrone on PDA, which increased to 137 051 µg/kg and 197 007 µg/kg on YES, respectively. Notably, *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58690 showed one of the highest increases, with deoxyfusapyrone production increasing from 22 510 µg/kg on PDA to 233 270 µg/kg on YES and fusapyrone from 33 302 µg/kg to 266 720 µg/kg. Conversely, some strains showed undetectable levels of both compounds across both media types.

DAS production was only detected in *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686 (573 µg/kg) when grown on YES. In the case of *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58690 and CMW 58694, both strains were producing DAS on both media used. The production detected for CMW 58690 was quite similar for both media types (965 µg/kg on PDA and 962 µg/kg on YES), whereas production in CMW 58694 doubled from 471 µg/kg on PDA to 832 µg/kg on YES.

Equisetin and fusarisetin A were only detected in *F. cumulatum* strains. For most strains, levels of both compounds were below the limit of detection on both media. In

the case of *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686, 2 002 µg/kg of fusarisetin A was produced on PDA but had undetectable levels on YES. Similarly, *F. cumulatum* CMW 58688 had 2 462 µg/kg of fusarisetin A production on PDA but with undetectable production levels on YES. Equisetin production remained below the detection limit across almost all strains and media, except for *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686 which produced 2 021 µg/kg on PDA and undetectable levels on YES.

Sphingofungin B levels were below the limit of detection on both media for most strains. The only exception was *F. cumulatum* that exhibited measurable levels. Specifically, strains CMW 58686 and CMW 58688, produced 990 µg/kg and 922 µg/kg of sphingofungin B on PDA, respectively. However, neither produced detectable levels on YES.

ZEA, α-ZOL, β-ZOL and ZEA-14-S were mostly below the limit of detection, particularly for α-ZOL, β-ZOL and ZEA. However, some strains of *F. goeppertmayerae* demonstrated notable production on both media. For instance, *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58689 showed high production levels of ZEA-14-S on PDA at 663 034 µg/kg, with lower production levels on YES at 12 219 µg/kg. Similarly, strain CMW 58690 produced 818 055 µg/kg of ZEA-14-S on PDA, with a decrease to 292 103 µg/kg on YES. In contrast, *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58698 produced 47 187 µg/kg of β-ZOL and 30 295 µg/kg of ZEA on PDA, which reduced on YES to 589 µg/kg and 9 866 µg/kg, respectively. Only one strain of *F. pascuum* (CMW 58652) produced ZEA-14-S on YES.

Secondary metabolite biosynthesis genes

The Clinker figures (Figures 3–9) showed high conservation of gene clusters involved in secondary metabolite biosynthesis across different *Fusarium* species, which in many cases correlated with metabolite production. Genes with no shared homology (indicated in grey) are considered not to share the same function as the reference gene. We have not attempted a Clinker analysis with genomes in cases where the core biosynthesis gene from our species showed no similarity (based on BLAST analysis) towards the core biosynthesis reference gene and therefore considered that

these strains/species do not have the genetic capacity to produce this secondary metabolite (Table S2).

The core gene for BEA synthesis (*NRPS22*) was not found/observed in *F. pascuum* CMW 58653^{RG} (^{RG} = reference genome generated from our study) or *F. cumulatum* CMW 58688^{RG}. This corresponds with the non-detection of this metabolite in both strains and other strains of these species' secondary metabolite production data (Figures 2 and 3, Tables 2 and S2). The production of this metabolite correlated with the shared homology of *NRPS22* in *F. mariecurieae* CMW 58667^{RG} (*g757*) and *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58689^{RG} (*g10264*). Furthermore, other strains from both *F. mariecurieae* and *F. goeppertmayerae* also produced this secondary metabolite. The *NRPS22* gene was absent in *F. oxysporum* (FOSC), *F. graminearum* (FSAMSC) and species from the *Camptoceras* and *Equiseti* clades of the FIESC.

Chrysogine was only produced by strains of *F. goeppertmayerae* and *F. cumulatum* and this was confirmed by the shared homology of *NRPS14* in *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58689^{RG} (*g12149*) and *F. cumulatum* CMW 58688^{RG} (*g11709*) (Figures 2 and 4, Tables 2 and S2). The *NRPS14* gene was absent in species from the FFSC, FOSC and *Camptoceras*-clade of the FIESC.

The equisetin biosynthesis gene cluster was characterised in *F. heterosporum* strain ATCC 74349 (*Fusarium heterosporum* species complex; FHSC) (Kakule et al. 2013). In the current study, equisetin production was only detected in *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686, with fusarisetin A produced by both *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686 and CMW 58688^{RG}, suggesting equisetin biosynthesis despite the absence of *PKS18* (Figures 2 and 5, Tables 2 and S2). The equisetin cluster and *PKS18* was only conserved in the FFSC and FOSC, while it was absent in species from the FSAMSC and FIESC.

Fusarium pascuum CMW 58653^{RG} showed no fusapyrone or deoxyfusapyrone detectable production despite having the *PKS40* gene (*g6502*), which could potentially be activated under favourable conditions (Figures 2 and 6, Tables 2 and S2). Some other strains of *F. pascuum* did produce these two secondary metabolites providing evidence to the fact that strain CMW 58653 might be able to produce these compounds under certain conditions. *PKS40* (*g2098*) was absent in *F. cumulatum*

CMW 58688^{RG}, although fusapyrone was observed in another strain of *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686. Unfortunately, no genome sequence was available for CMW 58686 to investigate the presence/absence of *PKS40*. The fusapyrone or deoxyfusapyrone production observed for *F. mariecurieae* CMW 58667^{RG} and *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58689^{RG} was correlated with the presence of the genes *g10525* and *g3733*, respectively, which were homologous to *PKS40*. The *PKS40* gene was absent from *F. oxysporum* (FOSC) and species from the *Equiseti*-clade of the FIESC.

The *TRI5* gene is important for the synthesis of trichothecenes and was first characterised in *F. sporotrichioides* (Hohn and Beremand 1989). *TRI5* was present in all genomes from the FSAMSC and FIESC but was not present in species from the FFSC and FOSC (Figure 7). NIV and 4-ANIV were detected in *F. cumulatum* strains, and DON and 15-ADON in some *F. pascuum* strains (Figure 2, Table 2). The synthesis of NIV and DON (and their derivatives) is dependent on the activity of *TRI8* (Alexander et al. 2011), which was homologous to *g3129* in *F. cumulatum* CMW 58688^{RG} (Figures 2 and 7, Tables 2 and S2). The remaining three reference genomes generated from our study also contain genes with homology to *TRI8* and likely have the potential to produce NIV, 4-ANIV, DON and 15-ADON under favourable conditions (Villafana et al. 2019). Since all the genomes in this study have genes homologous to *TRI8*, it might be possible that all four of our species can produce DON and 15-ADON from nivalenol. The *TRI12* gene also appeared to be present in all species from the FSAMSC but was lost in the FIESC, while *TRI13* was also lost in species from the *Camptoceras*-clade (FIESC).

The *PKS SphB* gene product is known to be involved in sphingofungin B production (Kim et al. 2020). The shared homology of *PKS SphB* to *g8590* in *F. cumulatum* CMW 58688^{RG} correlates with the production data (Figures 2 and 8, Tables 2 and S2). Furthermore, the other strain of *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686 also produces this secondary metabolite. We also observed that the genes, *g1553* in *F. pascuum* CMW 58653^{RG}, *g8643* in *F. mariecurieae* CMW 58667^{RG} and *g7900* in *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58689^{RG} all share similarity with the *PKS SphB* gene based on the Clinker figure, but all have very low query coverage values based on BLAST results (Table S2). The *PKS SphB* gene was not present in any of the FFSC or FSAMSC species analysed.

The gene products of *PKS13* and *PKS4* are important for ZEA biosynthesis (Kim et al. 2005; Gaffoor and Trail 2006). However, there are no genes with significant similarity to these genes in the *F. pascuum* CMW 58653^{RG} genome. This correlates with the non-detection of ZEA production in this species (Figures 2 and 9, Tables 2 and S2). However, despite the absence of genes with significant similarity in *F. pascuum* CMW 58653^{RG}, ZEA-14-S production was observed in *F. pascuum* CMW 58652. There were no genes with significant similarity to *PKS13* and *PKS4* in the genomes of *F. mariecurieae* and *F. cumulatum*, which also correlates with non-production of ZEA in vitro. With the exception of the one *F. pascuum* strain, the production of ZEA, α -ZOL, β -ZOL and ZEA-14-S was restricted to strains of *F. goeppertmayerae*, where two genes, *g2211* and *g2210*, from *F. goeppertmayerae* CMW 58689^{RG} shared homology to *PKS13* and *PKS4*, respectively. ZEA production seems to be absent in species of the FOOSC, FFOSC and *Camptoceras*-clade of the FIESC, as these species lacked the *PKS13* and *PKS4* genes in their genomes.

Discussion

In this study, we examined the secondary metabolite production potential of 19 strains across four *Fusarium* species of the FIESC: *F. pascuum* (n = 6) (Dewing et al. 2025a), *F. cumulatum* (n = 2) (Dewing et al. 2025a), *F. goeppertmayerae* (n = 5) (Tan and Shivas 2023) and *F. mariecurieae* (n = 6) (Dewing et al. 2025a). These strains were collected from dairy pastures in the Eastern Cape as part of a broader investigation into the fungal diversity associated with these pastures during a facial eczema outbreak in cattle (Dewing et al. 2025b). The results of our current study revealed that members of the FIESC have the potential to produce diverse secondary metabolites based on the chemical analyses and comparative genomics. Comparative genomics revealed genes homologous to core biosynthesis genes, including *NRPS*, *PKS* and *TRI* genes, confirming the genetic potential in species for which in vitro analyses had not detected metabolite production. We correlated our genomic data with the chemical data since we were able to link the major genes that have been shown to be involved in the biosynthesis of specific secondary metabolites in other fungi with the metabolites we tested for.

We expected to detect BEA, DAS, trichothecenes (and modified forms) and ZEA in the four species that we studied, as these mycotoxins were previously reported to be common in other members of the FIESC (Phillips et al. 1989; Logrieco et al. 1998; Hestbjerg et al. 2002; Kosiak et al. 2005; Villani et al. 2016; O'Donnell et al. 2018; Villani et al. 2019). When a secondary metabolite was detected in our analyses, we expected to find the responsible core biosynthesis gene within our genomes. By starting, and mainly focusing on the *PKS*, *NRPS* and *TRI* genes, we occasionally found some of the other genes known to be in these biosynthesis gene clusters. Unfortunately, sometimes we were unable to find a complete cluster on one contig perhaps due to the fact that many of the *PKS*, *NRPS* and *TRI* genes were found on small contigs resulting in larger gene clusters to be split across different contigs. These additional cluster genes might be present in the genome but not assembled together, making their detection challenging. This then resulted in missing genes or incomplete biosynthesis gene clusters in some of the figures. As an alternative, long-read sequencing (e.g., PacBio or Oxford Nanopore) can be implemented to generate more contiguous genome assemblies. Longer reads can span repetitive regions and link genes that are currently split across contigs, potentially recovering the missing parts of the pathway.

From our comparative genomics analysis, we observed variability in the presence of *PKS* and *NRPS* genes across FIESC strains. The homologs of some cluster genes were sometimes present in all the FIESC strains examined but did not always show homology to the reference genes, as observed for chrysogine and fusapyrone. Instead, these genes showed homology towards each other in the FIESC demonstrating conserved homology in the FIESC that was somehow lost between members of the FIESC and other *Fusarium* species. We also discovered that the homologous genes were sometimes only present in members of either the *Equiseti* or *Incaratum*-clade, as observed for BEA, for example. Our finding regarding the *NRPS22* BEA gene is in line with what was previously reported, since *NRPS22* was only reported and detected from species in the *Incaratum*-clade (O'Donnell et al. 2018; Villani et al. 2019). Our study also indicated that some cluster genes are more prevalent in members of either the *Equiseti* or *Incaratum*-clade, as observed for fusapyrone where the majority of species containing the *PKS40* belonged to the *Incaratum*-clade.

The FIESC rarely harbours unique secondary metabolite gene clusters, as all characterised clusters within this group have already been identified in other *Fusarium* species complexes (Villani et al. 2019; Lin et al. 2023). In the current study, the trichothecene biosynthesis cluster was the only one consistently present across all FIESC strains, highlighting its conserved role within the complex. In contrast, other secondary metabolite biosynthesis gene clusters, such as those responsible for the production of BEA and ZEA, exhibited a discontinuous distribution across different *Fusarium* genomes. This variation suggests that while some secondary metabolite pathways are well-conserved, others may be subjected to lineage-specific gene loss, horizontal gene transfer, or regulatory differences affecting their presence and expression (Villani et al. 2019). Additionally, the *PKS SpB* gene cluster, which is associated with sphingofungin B biosynthesis, displayed some sequence homology to genes within FIESC genomes. However, the low query coverage and identity similarity observed in BLAST analyses indicate that this secondary metabolite is likely absent from the FIESC, despite its detection in two *F. cumulatum* strains during chemical analysis.

Discrepancy between genetic data and metabolite detection could be explained by several factors. One possibility is horizontal gene transfer, as sphingofungin B biosynthesis genes were originally characterised in *Aspergillus fumigatus* (Fedorova et al. 2008) and genetic divergence from known *Fusarium* sequences could account for the weak BLAST results (low sequence similarity and few significant hits) observed. The presence of partial homology in Clinker analysis further supports the potential involvement of horizontal gene transfer in the distribution of this cluster. Alternatively, the detection of sphingofungin B in *F. cumulatum* strains may be the result of contamination. Given the complexity of fungal secondary metabolism and the potential for cross-contamination in laboratory settings, further verification is required to determine whether the metabolite is genuinely produced by *F. cumulatum*. Another plausible explanation is that the genome assemblies used in this study are too fragmented, leading to incomplete representation of the sphingofungin B biosynthesis cluster. If core genes in the pathway were located on unassembled contigs or misassembled regions, it could result in a failure to detect the full cluster through BLAST analysis.

Similar to sphingofungin B results, fusarisetin A production in *F. cumulatum* CN104D3^{RG} was detected despite the absence of a homologous *PKS18* gene in this species. Equisetin is a precursor for fusarisetin A production (Kato et al. 2015), and therefore, without equisetin, the production of fusarisetin A is unlikely to occur, as they share a common biosynthesis pathway. As noted above, detection of equisetin and fusarisetin A production may be due to contamination. However, it is possible that fusarisetin A could be produced by an alternative biosynthesis pathway that is different from the expected one. Alternatively, some fungi modify secondary metabolites enzymatically or chemically after initial biosynthesis, meaning the responsible genes may not match known pathways. A solution for this uncertainty is to repeat the chemical analyses to gain more certainty about the results.

PKS40 was absent in *F. cumulatum* CMW 58688^{RG}, although fusapyrone was observed in another strain of *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686. Unfortunately, no genome was available to assess the presence of the *PKS40* gene in strain CMW 58686. It can happen where different strains of the same species show variation in the production of the same secondary metabolite. Villani et al. (2019) mentioned a similar observation for *F. clavus* ITEM 11348 and CS3069 where the latter contained an intact *PKS42-NRPS34* gene cluster which was absent in the former strain. Villani et al. (2019) hypothesised that the *PKS42-NRPS34* cluster may have been lost in ITEM 11348 as a result of selective pressures. Alternatively, the *PKS42-NRPS34* could exist as two distinct allelic forms within *F. clavus* – one allele containing the cluster and another lacking it. This would mean some individuals carry the *PKS42-NRPS34* cluster, while others naturally lack it due to allelic variation. Similar cases have been reported for fumonisin and ochratoxin biosynthesis gene clusters in *Aspergillus* species (Susca et al. 2014; Susca et al. 2016). However, it is also possible that the detection of fusapyrone in *F. cumulatum* CMW 58686 is due to an experimental artefact but would need to be confirmed upon further testing and repeating the analysis.

The trichothecene biosynthesis gene cluster is the only secondary metabolite consistently present across all examined members of the FIESC strains, a pattern also observed in previous studies (Villani et al. 2019). This cluster is known for its structural and functional variability in trichothecene production within the FIESC (Hestbjerg et al. 2002; Morrison et al. 2002; Villani et al. 2016). The biosynthesis of trichothecene

mycotoxins in *Fusarium* is influenced by the presence and functionality of *TRI13* and *TRI7*, which catalyse hydroxylation and acetylation at the C4 position of the trichothecene backbone (Lee et al. 2002). Villani et al. (2019) found that *TRI13* was absent and *TRI7* was pseudogenised in *F. camptoceras* (FIESC), suggesting that it produces unmodified trichothecenes (e.g., DON, 15-ADON) similar to certain species in the *F. sambucinum* species complex (FSAMSC) (Brown et al. 2002; Kimura et al. 2007). Our study supports these findings as the genome of our *Camptoceras*-clade species, *F. pascuum*, also did not have the *TRI13* or *TRI7* genes. Villani et al. (2019) hypothesised that the loss of these genes in both complexes (FIESC, FSAMSC) occurred independently, likely pointing to convergent evolution due to the lack of selective pressure for C4 modifications. The *TRI13* gene product plays a later role in the trichothecene pathway, where it is also required for the conversion of the calonectrin precursor molecule into DAS (Villafana et al. 2019).

Beyond biosynthesis, the variation in *TRI* gene content and structure has broader ecological and evolutionary implications. These genetic shifts may reflect adaptations to specific ecological niches, where complex trichothecene modifications are not advantageous. Given that trichothecenes function as virulence factors during host infection, such changes could alter the pathogenic potential of *Fusarium* strains and influence their interactions with plant hosts or microbial competitors. Thus, the architecture of the *TRI* cluster is not only a marker of metabolic capacity but also a potential driver of ecological specialisation and agricultural relevance within the FIESC.

In this study, we applied bioinformatics-based methods to investigate the core genes involved in secondary metabolite biosynthesis in four *Fusarium* genomes, representing three newly described species and one previously known species. Through in vitro chemical analyses, we identified 16 secondary metabolites, including both well-known and emerging mycotoxins. We found that some strains exhibited the genetic capacity to produce specific metabolites, despite these compounds not being detected under in vitro conditions. Future research will include repeating the chemical analyses to resolve inconsistencies, as well as gene knockout experiments to clarify the role of specific biosynthesis genes – especially those lacking homology to well-characterised reference clusters. We also aim to better understand how the presence

of these divergent genes relates to metabolite production, especially when the corresponding compounds are not observed.

These findings have important implications for agriculture, food safety and animal health. By identifying biosynthesis gene clusters such as *TRI*, *PKS* and *NRPS*, we can better predict a strain's potential to produce harmful mycotoxins. Strains lacking key genes for toxins like ZEA or BEA may pose a lower contamination risk, while those with complete clusters warrant closer monitoring. Molecular diagnostics targeting these genes can improve the detection of toxigenic *Fusarium* species in routine testing, enabling earlier and more targeted responses. Importantly, our results also support the potential involvement of these *Fusarium* species in cattle mycotoxicosis, given their capacity to produce both known and emerging mycotoxins. Together, our integrative genomic and chemical approach provides a practical framework for improving mycotoxin risk assessment, pathogen monitoring and mitigation strategies in agricultural systems.

Data availability

The genome sequence data for *F. cumulatum*, *F. goeppertmayerae*, *F. mariecurieae* and *F. pascuum* are available from the authors upon reasonable request and will be submitted to GenBank at a later stage.

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Figures

Figure 1. *Fusarium* species tree constructed with 12 housekeeping genes, including *CAL1*, *DPA1*, *DPE1*, *GDP1*, *HIS3*, *MCM7*, *PGK1*, *RPB1*, *RPB2*, *TEF1*, *TUB1* and *TUB2*.

Strain	Media	15-ADON ^{EM}	DON ^{RM}	4-ANIV ^{EM}	NIV ^{RM}	α-ZOL ^{EM}	β-ZOL ^{EM}	ZEA ^{RM}	ZEA-14-S ^{EM}	BEA ^{EM}	Chrysozine	Deoxyfusapyrone	Fusapyrone	DAS ^{EM}	Equisetin ^{EM}	Fusarisetin A ^{EM}	Sphingofungin B	
<i>F. cumulatum</i>	CMW 58686	PDA	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	
	CMW 58686	YES	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	
	CMW 58688 ^{RG}	PDA	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	
	CMW 58688 ^{RG}	YES	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58689 ^{RG}	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58689 ^{RG}	YES	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58690	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	
	CMW 58690	YES	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	
	CMW 58693	PDA	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	
	CMW 58693	YES	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	
	CMW 58694	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	
	CMW 58694	YES	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	
	CMW 58698	PDA	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
	CMW 58698	YES	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-
<i>F. mariecurieae</i>	CMW 58665	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58665	YES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58667 ^{RG}	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58667 ^{RG}	YES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58671	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58671	YES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58672	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58672	YES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58673	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
	CMW 58673	YES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
<i>F. pasuum</i>	CMW 58652	PDA	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58652	YES	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58653 ^{RG}	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58653 ^{RG}	YES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58655	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58655	YES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	CMW 58656	PDA	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
	CMW 58656	YES	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
	CMW 58659	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
	CMW 58659	YES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
CMW 58660	PDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
CMW 58660	YES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

15-ADON = 15-acetyldeoxynivalenol; DON = Deoxynivalenol; 4-ANIV = 4-acetylnivalenol; NIV = Nivalenol; α-ZOL = alpha-zearalenol; β-ZOL = beta-zearalenol; Zearalenone = ZEA; ZEA-14-S = Zearalenone-14-sulfate; BEA = Beauvericin; DAS = Diacetoxyscirpenol
^{RG} = Reference genomes generated from our study
^{EM} = Emerging mycotoxins
^{RM} = Regulated mycotoxins

Figure 2. Secondary metabolite profiles detected for the *Fusarium* species used in this study.

Figure 3. Comparative synteny plot of a conserved gene cluster for BEA production, with a special interest in the *NRPS22* gene, across *Fusarium* species from the FFSC, FOSC, FSAMSC and FIESC. Species names in red represent the newly described species for which genomes were supplied. Arrows represent individual genes, oriented in the direction of transcription. Grey genes suggest no homology to the reference genes. Coloured blocks between genes indicate regions of sequence homology. Gene identities correspond to annotated loci from each species.

Figure 4. Comparative synteny plot of a conserved gene cluster for chrysozine production, with a special interest in the *NRPS14* gene, across *Fusarium* species from the FSAMSC and FIESC. Species names in red represent the newly described species for which genomes were supplied. Arrows represent individual genes, oriented in the direction of transcription. Grey genes suggest no homology to the reference genes. Coloured blocks between genes indicate regions of sequence homology. Gene identities correspond to annotated loci from each species.

Figure 5. Comparative synteny plot of a conserved gene cluster for equisetin production, with a special interest in the *PKS18* gene, across *Fusarium* species from the *Fusarium heterosporum* species complex (FHSC), FFSC and FO SC. Species names in red represent the newly described species for which genomes were supplied. Arrows represent individual genes, oriented in the direction of transcription. Grey genes suggest no homology to the reference genes. Coloured blocks between genes indicate regions of sequence homology. Gene identities correspond to annotated loci from each species.

Figure 6. Comparative synteny plot of a conserved gene cluster for fusapyrone production, with a special interest in the *PKS40* gene, across *Fusarium* species from the FFSC, FSAMSC and FIESC. Species names in red represent the newly described species for which genomes were supplied. Arrows represent individual genes, oriented in the direction of transcription. Grey genes suggest no homology to the reference genes. Coloured blocks between genes indicate regions of sequence homology. Gene identities correspond to annotated loci from each species.

Figure 7. Comparative synteny plot of a conserved gene cluster for NIV production, with a special interest in the *TRI5* gene, across *Fusarium* species from the FSAMSC and FIESC. Species names in red represent the newly described species for which genomes were supplied. Arrows represent individual genes, oriented in the direction of transcription. Grey genes suggest no homology to the reference genes. Coloured blocks between genes indicate regions of sequence homology. Gene identities correspond to annotated loci from each species.

Figure 8. Comparative synteny plot of a conserved gene cluster for sphingofungin B production, with a special interest in the *PKS SphB* gene, across *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Fusarium* species from the FOSC and FIESC. Species names in red represent the newly described species for which genomes were supplied. Arrows represent individual genes, oriented in the direction of transcription. Grey genes suggest no homology to the reference genes. Coloured blocks between genes indicate regions of sequence homology. Gene identities correspond to annotated loci from each species.

Figure 9. Comparative synteny plot of a conserved gene cluster for ZEA production, with a special interest in the *PKS4* and *PKS13* genes, across *Fusarium* species from the FSAMSC and FIESC. Species names in red represent the newly described species for which genomes were supplied. Arrows represent individual genes, oriented in the direction of transcription. Grey genes suggest no homology to the reference genes. Coloured blocks between genes indicate regions of sequence homology. Gene identities correspond to annotated loci from each species.

Tables

Table 1. *Fusarium* strains used in the present study, along with the assembly statistics generated for the genomes of selected strains.

Species	Strain	Additional accessions	Genome size (Mb)	No. of core genes detected	No. contigs	Completeness (%)	Duplicates (%)	N50 (nt)	GC (%)
<i>F. cumulatum</i>	CMW 58686	CN071B9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. cumulatum</i>	CMW 58688 ^T	CBS 151773, CN104D3	37.6	3 751	51	98.2	0.2	1 590 025	48.2
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58689	CBS 151775, CN040I5	37.8	3 748	51	98.2	0.2	1 643 596	48.3
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58690	CN070F3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58693	CN071H8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58694	CN071I6	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58698	CN106F2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i>	CMW 58665	CN070G2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i>	CMW 58667	CBS 151774, CN070I7	38.6	3 741	82	98.0	0.3	1 041 873	47.9

Table 1. (continue)

Species	Strain	Additional accessions	Genome size (Mb)	No. of core genes detected	No. contigs	Completeness (%)	Duplicates (%)	N50 (nt)	GC (%)
<i>F. mariecurieae</i>	CMW 58671	CN071F4	—		—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i>	CMW 58672	CN071H1	—		—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i>	CMW 58673 ^T	CBS 152079, CN072A3	—		—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. mariecurieae</i>	CMW 58679	CN106F1	—		—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. pasuum</i>	CMW 58652	CN071B8	—		—	—	—	—	
<i>F. pasuum</i>	CMW 58653 ^T	CBS 151772, CN159G4, CN071C4	37.3	3 749	202	98.3	0.2	667 985	47.9
<i>F. pasuum</i>	CMW 58655	CN071E9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. pasuum</i>	CMW 58656	CN071F9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. pasuum</i>	CMW 58659	CN071I5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
<i>F. pasuum</i>	CMW 58660	CN071I9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

^T = ex-type strains; The N50 is the length of the shortest contig among the longest contigs that together make up at least 50% of the total genome length; The genome completeness was assessed by evaluating how much of the expected gene content is present in the genome assembly and was evaluated by using BUSCO; Duplicates in the genome assembly was determined by identifying repeated or multiple representations of genomic content that are expected to be single-copy, such as single-copy orthologs or unique regions of the genome and was determined by using BUSCO

Table 2. Fungal metabolites and estimated concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) detected from *Fusarium* species.

Group	Strain	Media	15-ADON ^{EM}	DON ^{RM}	4-ADON ^{EM}	NIV ^{RM}	α -ZOL ^{EM}	β -ZOL ^{EM}	ZEA ^{RM}	ZEA-14-S* ^{EM}	BEA ^{EM}	Chrysofine	Deoxyfusapyrone	Fusapyrone	DAS ^{EM}	Equisetin ^{EM}	Fusarisetin A ^{EM}	Sphingofungin B
<i>F. cumulatum</i>	CMW 58686	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	2 144	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	2 456	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	2 021	2 002	990
	CMW 58686	YES	<LOD	<LOD	910	1 610	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	5 651	<LOD	573	358	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58688 ^{RG}	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	917	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	2 102	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	2 462	922
	CMW 58688 ^{RG}	YES	<LOD	<LOD	1 080	1 403	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	8 191	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
<i>F. goeppertmayerae</i>	CMW 58689 ^{RG}	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	155 923	663 034	<LOD	<LOD	32 130	59 927	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58689 ^{RG}	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	464	389	12 219	7 161	348	131 312	166 979	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58690	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	7 251	818 055	<LOD	<LOD	22 510	33 302	965	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58690	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	578	292 103	15 067	562	233 270	266 720	962	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58693	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	2 801	1 867	48 508	<LOD	<LOD	49 089	59 432	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58693	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	9 372	10 706	2 100	230 205	267 191	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58694	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	6 432	544 862	990	<LOD	34 395	56 170	471	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58694	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	685	188 063	44 135	1 582	194 619	300 516	832	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58698	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	1 984	47 187	30 295	569 037	<LOD	<LOD	42 108	51 954	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58698	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	589	9 866	461 325	23 704	<LOD	116 431	115 107	735	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
<i>F. mariecuriae</i>	CMW 58665	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58665	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58667 ^{RG}	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	484	<LOD	63 579	70 560	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58667 ^{RG}	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	15 266	<LOD	67 086	123 174	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58671	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	792	<LOD	45 752	65 814	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58671	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	13 058	<LOD	137 051	197 007	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58672	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	4 697	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD

Table 2. (continue)

Group	Strain	Media	15-ADON ^{EM}	DON ^{RM}	4-ADON ^{EM}	NIV ^{RM}	α-ZOL ^{EM}	β-ZOL ^{EM}	ZEA ^{RM}	ZEA-14-S* ^{EM}	BEA ^{EM}	Chrysofine	Deoxyfusapyrone	Fusapyrone	DAS ^{EM}	Equisetin ^{EM}	Fusarisetin A ^{EM}	Sphingofungin B
<i>F. maricuriiae</i>	CMW 58672	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	5 714	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58673	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	1 036	<LOD	30 802	61 775	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58673	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	21 399	<LOD	129 576	280 615	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58679	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	715	<LOD	15 728	28 568	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58679	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	42 466	<LOD	22 050	61 622	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
<i>F. pasuum</i>	CMW 58652	PDA	1 130	481	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	17 334	12 388	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58652	YES	2 382	8 592	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	1 322	<LOD	<LOD	26 715	13 742	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58653 ^{RG}	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58653 ^{RG}	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58655	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58655	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58656	PDA	807	776	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	23 344	12 094	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58656	YES	573	5 972	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	19 087	4 072	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58659	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	24 451	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58659	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	15 231	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58660	PDA	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	CMW 58660	YES	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD

15-ADON = 15-acetyldeoxynivalenol; DON = Deoxynivalenol; 4-ADON = 4-acetylivalenol; NIV = Nivalenol; α-ZOL = alpha-zearalenol; β-ZOL = beta-zearalenol;

Zearalenone = ZEA; Zearalenone-14-sulfate = ZEA-14-S; BEA = Beauvericin; DAS = Diacetoxyscirpenol

*no quantitative standard - numbers are LC-MS peak area

LOD = limit of detection; <LOD = below the limit of detection

RG = Reference genomes generated from our study

EM = Emerging mycotoxins

RM = Regulated mycotoxins

Supplementary tables

All data and supporting materials are available on Figshare (<https://figshare.com/s/309eecbaec6519ca3391>)

Table S1. List of the eight housekeeping genes used in our study.

Table S2. BLAST results for all genes used for the Clinker figures.

Table S3. Genomes of the reference *Fusarium* species used in this study.

Summary

Pasture-based dairy farming plays an important role in South Africa's milk industry, yet limited information is available on the fungal communities associated with these pastures. In particular, the diversity of fungi in Eastern Cape pastures has not been systematically investigated, leaving uncertainty about which species occur there and whether they pose risks to cattle health. Many pasture-associated fungi are capable of producing mycotoxins, which, with long-term exposure, can impair immune responses, decrease fertility and reduce milk yields in cattle. Such effects result in significant economic losses for farmers and the broader dairy industry, both locally and globally.

In this study, I characterised the fungal communities in South African dairy pastures, isolating 708 strains representing 132 species across 55 genera. *Fusarium* was the most common genus, followed by *Penicillium*, *Pseudopithomyces*, *Cladosporium*, *Epicoccum* and *Bipolaris*. Some strains could not be identified to species and represent 28 potentially new or previously unsequenced species. Phylogenetic analyses confirmed the presence of *Pseudopithomyces toxicarius*, the fungus associated with SILD. I also formally described three new *Fusarium* species within the *Fusarium incarnatum-equiseti* species complex as *F. cumulatum*, *F. mariecurieae* and *F. pascuum*, highlighting the hidden diversity of pasture-associated fungi.

Using a combination of genomic and chemical analyses, I explored the mycotoxin production potential of these new *Fusarium* species. The chemical analyses revealed both regulated mycotoxins (deoxynivalenol (DON), nivalenol (NIV), zearalenone (ZEA)) and emerging mycotoxins (15-acetylDON, 4-acetylNIV, α - and β -zearalenol, ZEA-14-sulfate, beauvericin, diacetoxyscirpenol, equisetin, fusarisetin A). By linking the genomic data on secondary metabolite biosynthesis genes to the chemical data, I found that some strains had the genetic potential to produce specific metabolites despite these compounds not being detected under in vitro conditions. Overall, these results suggest that these *Fusarium* species, along with other mycotoxin-producing genera, could contribute to cattle mycotoxicosis. Understanding fungal diversity in dairy pastures is important for protecting animal health, improving pasture

management and supporting sustainable dairy farming. In South Africa, this research helps farmers and veterinarians better monitor and manage mycotoxigenic fungi, reducing mycotoxin risks and keeping cattle healthy. Healthier cattle lead to higher milk yields, improved fertility and reduced veterinary costs, improving profitability.

At the industry level, the outcome of this work provides information needed for monitoring, risk management and preventative action to enhance food safety and compliance with the required export standards, thus protecting market access and supporting the competitiveness of South African dairy products. The global relevance of this research is relevant to all regions with similar climates, such as New Zealand, South Australia and parts of South America, facing comparable risks from fungal pathogens and mycotoxins. Sharing knowledge through publications and conferences can build collaborative monitoring networks to prevent fungal outbreaks in pastures.

Climate change is another important factor that continues to intensify the challenges associated with fungal diversity in dairy pastures. The continued rising in temperatures and shifting of rainfall patterns are already altering fungal communities and mycotoxin production. This study provides baseline information to anticipate and manage these emerging challenges. Future work incorporating advanced sequencing technologies and metabolomics will allow even more precise identification and characterisation of fungal species and their mycotoxin production potential.

Overall, this research advances the current understanding of fungal diversity in dairy pastures. It also highlights future research directions and offers practical benefits for farmers, veterinarians and the dairy industry in South Africa and beyond. In doing so, it contributes to a safer and more resilient milk supply in a changing climate.